

**Assessment of Employee Engagement Practices in the Service
Sector - A study in Mangaluru city of Karnataka**

**Thesis submitted to Srinivas University in fulfillment of the requirements
for the award of the Degree of**

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN MANAGEMENT

By

V. T. Shailashri

Reg No: SUPHDMGMT2017/01

Under the guidance of

Dr. Sureka Shenoy, M.Com, Ph.D.,

**Professor,
Srinivas Institute of Management Studies,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru -575001**

Dr. P. S. Aithal, Ph.D., Post Doc.

**Professor,
College of Management and Commerce,
Srinivas University, Mangaluru-575001**

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, MUKKA, MANGALURU - 574 146

(KARNATAKA STATE), INDIA

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Certificate

RESEARCH SUPERVISOR'S REPORT

This is to certify that Thesis entitled “**Assessment of Employee engagement practices in the service sector - A study in Mangaluru city of Karnataka**”, submitted to **Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangaluru, Karnataka State, India**, by **V.T.Shailashri**, for the award of degree of **Doctor of Philosophy** in Business Management, is a record of bonafide research work carried out by her under our supervision. The Thesis has reached the standard of the regulations for the degree and it has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, associateship, fellowship or any other similar title to the candidate or any other person (s).

Signature of the Research Supervisors

Dr. Sureka Shenoy, M.Com, Ph.D.,
Professor,
Srinivas Institute of Management Studies,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru -575001

Dr. P. S. Aithal, Ph.D., Post Doc.
Professor,
College of Management and Commerce,
Srinivas University, Mangaluru-575001

City Campus, Pandeshwar-Mangaluru-575001

Karnataka State, India

Place: Mangaluru

Date: 05-11-2018

Declaration

DECLARATION

This thesis, “**Assessment of Employee engagement practices in the service sector - A study in Mangaluru city of Karnataka**”, is the result of my own study carried out under the supervision of **Dr. P. S. Aithal, Ph.D., Post Doc.**, Professor, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru and **Dr. Sureka Shenoy, M.Com., Ph.D.**, Professor, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru and has not been submitted earlier to any university for any degree, diploma or any other similar title. This Thesis is free from any kind of plagiarism.

Place: Mangaluru

Signature of the candidate

Date: 05-11-2018

V.T. Shailashri,

MHRM, PGDBA, M.Phil. (Management)

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Synopsis

SYNOPSIS/ PREPHASE

Assessment of Employee engagement practices in the service sector - A study in Mangaluru city of Karnataka

INTRODUCTION

The challenge today is not about retaining talented people, but fully engaging them, capturing their minds and hearts at every stage of their career. Employee engagement has become apparent as a crucial driver of business success in today's competitive environment. Further, employee engagement could be the deciding factor for organizational success. Not only the engagement has the potential to significantly affect employee retention, productivity and loyalty, it is also a link to customer satisfaction, company reputation and overall brand image of the company. Thus, to gain a competitive edge, organizations are turning to human resources practices and practitioners to set the agenda for commitment and employee engagement.

Employee engagement is defined as "the extent to which employees are committed to something or someone in their organization, how hard they are working and how long they stay as a result of that commitment." Research has indicated that the connection between an employee's job and organizational strategy, including understanding how important the job is to the firm's success, is the most prominent driver of employee engagement.

A company with "high" employee engagement might be expected to outperform and reach excellence than those with "low" employee engagement, all other things being equal. Therefore, the employee engagement is an organizational approach, which results in the right conditions for all employees of an organization to give their best every day, committed to the organization's values, goals and objectives, motivated to contribute to organizational mission, along with increased sense of their own well-being. Employee engagement is also based on mutual trust, integrity, and mutual commitment from an organization and the employees and to bring transparency in the organization. It is a modern approach the organizations adopt which intends to increase the chances of contributing to organizational and individual performance, business success productivity and well-being of both organization and individuals.

SERVICE SECTOR

The service sector in India plays a dominant role. In addition to the contribution to the economic growth, that is GDP, it has contributed in foreign direct investment, export and import of goods and services, and providing ample of opportunities in employment generation. The activities included in this sector are numerous. It includes hospitality, construction, retail, Banking and finance, education, social services and many more. The contribution to the GDP from this sector is around 54% [2017-18] and employee's around 29% of the total population. India has very distinctive competencies and competitive advantage because of its knowledge-based services which makes it more attractive than any other countries.

Eichengreen and Gupta have categorized the service sector into three subsectors based on their productivity. The last category is called as the Modern category and this includes education, financial intermediation, computer services, business services, communications, legal and technical services. Thus, the present study concentrates on three sectors namely banking, insurance and education sectors.

The review of literature has several insights to the concept of employee engagement. The inference drawn from all studies is that employee engagement is a very important aspect, particularly in the service sector. It has been observed in many studies that there is a linkage between employee engagement and organisational performance in terms of profitability, customer satisfaction and overall growth and sustainability of an organisation. This research is an attempt to combine the three sectors namely education, banking and insurance to study employee engagement. A study of this nature was not identified in the review of literature. This study would further provide sufficient information on determine if nature of work influences strongly on employee engagement. It is an attempt to identify if same factors influence employee engagement in the different sectors in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada. Mangalore is a hub of the above mentioned services, and the people of this region have their own characteristics. The study thus is an attempt to determine the engagement levels (%) particular to the three sectors and group factors as similar and dissimilar in the sectors studied. The research further has attempted to identify the strength of association of the various factors of engagement and proceed towards a regression model. Since a study of this nature has not been conducted in Mangalore city of DK with respect to the three sectors, this would definitely add value to the

knowledge of employee engagement theoretically and would be useful in driving engagement in the organisations.

The research design is **exploratory cum descriptive in nature**. The major emphasis of this study then, is on identification of engagement levels in the various service sectors and to develop a predictive model for employee engagement. The theoretical framework of the study attempts to identify various factors which influence employee engagement. The factors or constructs that influence engagement can be categorized under three heads namely individual, group (team) and organizational Sub factors within each of the constructs have been developed namely;

- ❖ Organizational leadership and planning.
- ❖ Organizational culture and communication.
- ❖ Organizational pay and benefits.
- ❖ Organizational training and development.
- ❖ Individuals work environment.
- ❖ Individual's role in the organization.
- ❖ Relationship with Immediate supervisors.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada in India is a hub of service sector. Therefore, the proposed research study has the following objectives.

- To identify the employee engagement levels in the service sector namely Banking, Insurance and Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.
- To build a decision rule to enable the classification of employees into one of the two groups, that is engaged or disengaged in each of these sectors.
- To explore the drivers [Factors]of employee engagement in the service sector, namely Banking, Insurance and Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.
- To compare the three service sectors in term of employee engagement.
- To develop a relationship model for employee engagement and its causal factors for each of the three sectors.

Hypothesis for Research objective 1

To identify the employee engagement levels in the service sector namely Banking, Insurance and Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.

- ❖ H₁: There is a significant difference in the level of engagement in the various service sectors namely Banking, Insurance, Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.

Hypothesis for Research objective 2

To develop a relationship model for employee engagement and its causal factors for each of these three sectors.

- ❖ H₂: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and gender in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₃: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and gender in the Insurance sector.
- ❖ H₄: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and gender in the Education sector.
- ❖ H₅: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and length of service in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₆: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and length of service in the Insurance sector.
- ❖ H₇: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and length of service in the Education sector.
- ❖ H₈: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and age in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₉: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and age in the Insurance sector.
- ❖ H₁₀: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and age in the Education sector.
- ❖ H₁₁: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and salary in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₁₂: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and salary in the Insurance sector.

- ❖ H₁₃: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and salary in the Education sector.

SAMPLING

For this study, 1312 members constitute the sampling units, with a split of 459 employees in the education sector, 413 in the Banking sector and 440 employees in the Insurance sector. Since equal importance is given to each of these sectors 25% employees of the sampling frame is chosen as the sampling size.

Sample Inclusion

Banking: Middle level employees. Scale 1 and 2 and office staff.

Insurance: General and health Insurance [Sales head and Agents].

Education: Faculty of Basic Under graduation courses.

A quota sampling technique is used in this study. Since the response rate was 84%, 364 completed questionnaires were collected and analyzed for the research study.

The response obtained from the employees has been coded and entered into the software as per the requirements of the objectives. The data is analyzed using SPSS Version 21. Descriptive statistics like mean, median, mode, range, standard deviation, percentage, cumulative percentage have been used. Also, inferential statistics like Chi-Square, ANOVA, correlation coefficient, factor analysis, curve estimation and Discriminant analysis is used in the study

Discriminant Analysis is used to classify respondents into two categories namely engaged and disengaged. The form of equation for a three variable discriminant analysis used was

$$Y=a+K_1X_1+K_2X_2+K_3X_3$$

Where Y is the dependent variable and X₁, X₂ and X₃ are independent variables a, K₁, K₂, and K₃ are constant and coefficients. The individual factors for classifying the employee into two categories are namely age, gender, length of service and salary. The discriminant scores are calculated for each of the respondents and a decision rule for prediction is arrived at. The analysis is done separately for each of the sectors.

Also factor analysis is applied and data reduction was done in order to formulate and draft a new questionnaire to each of the sectors.

MAJOR FINDINGS.

Engagement is seen highest in the banking sector and least in the insurance sector. The banking sector has transformed rapidly and India is marching towards a digitalized banking era. The insurance sector has seen disengagement among its employees. The work culture, nature of job and targets which are assigned are the main reason for disengagement.

The purpose of this study was to examine Employee Engagement in the service sector namely Indian Banking sector, Indian insurance sector, and Indian education sector since these sectors are booming and plenty of employment opportunities lay here. These sectors have contributed to the Indian economic growth. The study has further provided sufficient information on to determine if nature of work influences strongly on employee engagement.

Comparison of gender across the three sectors shows that the insurance sector is dominated by the male gender, followed by the banking sector and then the education sector. On a closer inspection we still see gender disparity in the insurance and banking sector when it comes to the middle and top-level management.

Median age of the respondents in the insurance sector is 26 years while the median age in the banking and education sector is 28 years. The insurance sector has a younger generation of workers when compared to the banking and education sector.

The percentage of engaged workforce is 72.3% in banking followed by education sector which is 68.4 % and least in the insurance sector which is 31.3%.

Length of service in the organization showed the highest for the banking sector followed by the education sector and finally Insurance sector.

The Number of factors elicited after the process of factor analysis is 15 for banking, 26 for insurance and 20 for the education sector.

It is observed that age is the best predictor followed by salary then followed by length of service and the last factor is gender in the banking sector.

From the output table of standardized canonical discriminate functions co-efficient table, it is observed that gender is the best predictor followed by salary then followed by length of service and the last factor is age in the insurance sector. Age has proved to be an insignificant factor in this sector.

In the education sector salary is the best predictor followed by age, then length of service and finally gender. Also discriminant equations and regression equations are elaborated in the study and the values of the same are annexed.

CONCLUSION

It is observed that there is a clear association between engagement levels and the various sectors. Individual factors which influence employee engagement in the various sectors are elaborated and their contributions are dealt in detail. Further the concept of factor analysis is applied to extract the most important factors contributing to employee engagement in each of these sectors. Also, the personnel opinion of respondents was complied with and certain strategic recommendations are drawn from the study. The research consists of chapters, and its framework is presented as follows.

Chapter 1: Introduction

It begins with the introduction of the subject of employee engagement, followed by the conceptualization of employee engagement. Multidimensional aspect of employee engagement; various models proposed in employee engagement are elaborated in detail.

Chapter 2: Service Sector Analysis

This chapter provides an understanding of the service sector in India. The contribution of the service sector towards economic growth of the country is elaborated. Further the Insurance sector, banking sector and Education sector are analyzed from the point of growth and contribution towards economic development to the country. Also, the HR implications in each of these sectors are reviewed.

Chapter 3: Review of Literature

The previous research work on the topic of employee engagement has been quoted in this chapter which is relevant for the study. The review of literature consists of journal articles of individual authors and the studies conducted by various organizations. Research gap is identified after an in-depth study is done on the available literature.

Chapter 4: Research Design

This Chapter deals with the research design analysis, theoretical frame work, sample design which includes sample size and sampling method, questionnaire design of the present study validity and reliability of the questionnaire. It also discusses the data collection methods and techniques used in interpretation of the data. Finally, the problems faced during survey have been discussed; chapters of the thesis and the benefits of this study at large are included in this chapter.

Chapter 5: Analysis and Interpretations

It deals with the application of Statistical techniques to the primary data collected. It is divided into three parts of analysis based on the sectors namely Insurance, Banking and Educational sector. It discusses the various statistical techniques with their results and interpretations.

Chapter 6: Findings and Recommendations

This Chapter discusses the major findings in all the three sectors. It provides with the discriminant scores, factors that are extracted and also the regression model for prediction in all the three sectors.

Chapter 7: Research Implication, Limitation of the study and scope of further research

This chapter discusses the research implications of the study, limitations of the study, scope of further research and conclusion.

Bibliography

It includes the references of secondary data which helps in identifying, formulating and solving a research problem.

Annexure

It includes questionnaire framed for the study, variables name, reliability statistics, the discriminant scores of the given data, and newly drafted questionnaire for each of the sector and regression values for the given set of data.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION TO THE CONCEPT OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION TO THE CONCEPT OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

1.1 INTRODUCTION TO EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

Today's increasing volatile and complex business environment characterized by liberalization, globalizations, and the transnational invasion has created a great amount of challenges to organizations. Efficient and effective human resources are the most essential requirements in an organization for the survival and growth in this competitive world. HRM practices in an organization are aimed at managing the human resources and ensuring that the resources are effectively utilized towards the fulfillment of individual aspirations and organizational goals (Tiwari and Saxena, 2012). Basically, HRM deals with manpower planning, acquiring the right people, retaining/developing the right people, and managing people separation/exit (Chakrabarty, 2012). Therefore, the challenge for an organization is to manage the human resources in such a manner that it can justify their need for the right jobs and the existence in the organization.

The challenge today is not about retaining talented people, but fully engaging them, capturing their minds and hearts at every stage of their career. Employee engagement has become apparent as a crucial driver of business success in today's competitive environment. Further, employee engagement could be the deciding factor for organizational success. Not only the engagement has the potential to significantly affect employee retention, productivity and loyalty, it is also a link to customer satisfaction, company reputation and overall brand image of the company. Thus, to gain a competitive edge, organizations are turning to human resources practices and practitioners to set the agenda for commitment and employee engagement.

Employee engagement is defined as “the extent to which employees are committed to something or someone in their organization, how hard they are working and how long they stay as a result of that commitment.” Research has indicated that the connection between an employee's job and organizational strategy, including understanding how important the job is to the firm's success, is the most prominent driver of employee engagement. It is seen that, employees with the highest levels of commitment perform 20% better and also 87% less likely to leave the organization, which indicates that engagement is linked to organizational performance (Bakker, Arnold B, ed., 2010). In contrast, job satisfaction—a term sometimes used interchangeably with employee

engagement—may be defined as how an employee feels about his or her job, work environment, pay, benefits, etc. The happier employees are within their job, the more satisfied they are said to be and thus being engaged to the organization.

Employee engagement is a property of the relationship and association between an organization and its employees. An "engaged employee" is one who is fully absorbed by and enthusiastic about his/her work and so takes positive actions to improve the organization's reputation and interests. Employee engagement is one of the ways to business success. An engaged workplace encourages productivity, enthusiasm and commitment from all those involved to help improve business performance.

A company with "high" employee engagement might be expected to outperform and reach excellence than those with "low" employee engagement, all other things being equal. Therefore, the employee engagement is an organizational approach, which results in the right conditions for all employees of an organization to give their best every day, committed to the organization's values, goals and objectives, motivated to contribute to organizational mission, along with increased sense of their own well-being. Employee engagement is also based on mutual trust, integrity, mutual commitment from an organization and the employees and to bring transparency in the organization. It is a modern approach the organizations adopt which intends to increase the chances of contributing to organizational and individual performance, business success productivity and well-being of both organization and individuals. Engagement can be quantified for an organization. It varies from great to poor (Wilkinson, Adrien; et al. (2004)). It can be created, nurtured and dramatically increased; or if not taken care by the organization, discarded.

Employee engagement is all about understanding one's role and goal in an organization, and being capable of visualizing on where it eventually fits in the organization's purpose and objectives. Employee engagement is also about having a clear knowledge of how an organization is fulfilling its goals and objectives, how it is moving ahead to fulfill these in the best manner, and being given a say in its journey to offer ideas and express views and opinions that are considered as decisions are made. Engaged organizations have strong and well stated values, clear evidence of mutual trust and fairness based on respect, where two-way promises and commitments, between employers and employees, are well understood and fulfilled.

Employee engagement is all about positive thoughts, attitudes and behaviors leading to improved business outcomes. Employee engagement is about employees feeling proud and loyal of working in an organization, being a great brand ambassador of the company and going the extra mile to finish work in the organization. Employee engagement is about extracting an employee's knowledge and ideas to improve services and products, and being creative and innovative about how an organization works. Employee engagement is about obtaining a deeper commitment from employees so fewer leave, accident rates decline, conflicts and grievances decline which will all lead to increased productivity. Employee engagement is about organization actions which remain consistent with the organization's values. It is about how organizations meet the kept promises or an explanation why promises cannot be kept.

Employee engagement cannot be achieved through a mechanistic approach which extracts discretionary effort by changing employees' commitment and emotions. Employees understand such attempts very quickly and can become critical and disillusioned. Employee engagement does not mean employee happiness in the organization. Employees might be happy at work, but that doesn't necessarily mean they are working hard, productively on behalf of the organization. While company game rooms, free massages, laundry facilities and Friday parties may bring joy in the workplace which are beneficial for other reasons but making employees happy is different from making them engaged. Employee engagement means much more than employee satisfaction. Many companies have "employee satisfaction" surveys and executives talk about "employee satisfaction", but the metric is set too low. A satisfied employee might show up daily to the workplace without complaint. But that same "satisfied" employee might not put the extra effort. Satisfaction only isn't enough in an organization which has to sustain.

Employee engagement is essential for any organization. If employees don't agree with the values of an organization, appreciate the contribution they can make or do not feel that their employer cares or values them; they will not feel committed to the organization or motivated to perform their best in the organization. Employee engagement is the emotional connect the employee has to the organization and its values. This commitment means engaged employees actually care about their work and their company. Engaged employees don't work just for a pay or just for the next career promotion, but work on behalf of the organization's so that the objectives and the goals are achieved.

Employee engagement is a vast topic and can take many forms. The Institute of Employment Studies defines engagement as: "A positive attitude held by the employee towards the organization and its values. An engaged employee is aware of the business context, and works with colleagues to improve performance within the job for the benefit of the organization. The organization must work to develop and nurture engagement, which requires a two-way relationship between employee and employer".

Flourishing business organizations have engaged employees profoundly. Employee engagement acts as driver of financial and market success. Engaged employees are more profitable, productive, focused, have fun and most likely to be retained in the organization because they are engaged. Employee engagement is closely linked to employee turnover, customer delight, loyalty, productivity, and safety and overall profitability criteria. Thus, Employee engagement is an extra emotional connection that an employee feels for his or her organization, that influences him / her to put the greatest discretionary effort to his or her work (Conference Board in Soldati, 2007).

1.1.1 A Multi dimension concept Engagement

Different researchers have studied engagement under different sets of Dimensions. Engagement is defined as a “positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind that is characterized by vigor (high energy levels and mental resilience while working), dedication (been involved in one’s work), and absorption (being fully concentrated in one’s work) (Harter et al., 2002).

It is also defined as the amount of discretionary effort exhibited by employees in the job (Frank et al., 2004). It is an innate human desire to contribute something of value in workplace (Bates, 2004) which involves emotional and intellectual commitment to the organization (Baumruk, 2004). When an employee wants to stay long with the organization and recommends his/ her organization to others, it means “a heightened emotional connection develops to the job and organization that goes beyond satisfaction” (Gubman, 2004). It is a measure of the energy and passion workers have for their organization, it involves cognitive, emotional and behavioral aspect. Engagement implies a mutual relationship between employer and employee where employee holds a positive attitude for the organization and its values (Robinson et al., 2004). Finally, in 2008, Macey & Schneider provided a framework for employee engagement, breaking down the construct into the state, trait, and behavioral engagement. The framework defined trait

engagement as positive views of life and work; state engagement as feelings of energy and absorption; and behavioral engagement as extra-role behavior. Employee engagement is sometimes referred to as engagement (Crawford et al., 2010), personal engagement (Kahn, 1990), work engagement (Saks, 2006), job engagement (Kong, 2009) and organizational engagement (Saks, 2006). The name disagreement creates confusion in the field, leading to different interpretations.

1.1.2 Personal disengagement and engagement

Personal engagement represents a mindset where employees “bring in” their personal selves during work role performances, investing personal energy and experiencing an emotional connection to their work. While the personal disengagement is defined as uncoupling of selves for work roles means people withdraw and defend themselves physically, cognitively and emotionally during role performance (Kahn, 1990).

1.1.3 Work Engagement

Work engagement is defined as a relatively enduring state of mind referring to the simultaneous investment of personal energies in the experience or performance of work (Christian et al., 2011).

Work engagement is a process of investing one’s self in work tasks that produces a positive and fulfilling work-related frame of mind characterized by vigor, dedication to and concentration on the job. It is shaped by organizational situation, organizational resources, task characteristics, meaningfulness of work and employee’s personal resources. Strong work engagement leads to positive organizational and personal outcomes, improved performance, self-efficacy, employee retention, and work-life balance (Popova, 2010).

Work engagement is also a social and organizational process in which individuals engage in negotiating the meaning of norms and practices, and employees express their “preferred selves in tasks and behaviors that promote connections to work and to others” (Billett & Somerville, 2004).

Work Engagement has been defined as a frame of mind, “a persistent and pervasive” work-related affective-cognitive state that is positive and fulfilling and is not related on any particular object, event, individual, or behavior” (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008; May et al., 2004).

It can be categorized in three ways: vigor, dedication and absorption. Engaged employees have a sense of energetic and effective connection with their work activities. Vigor is characterized by high levels of energy and mental resilience while working. Dedication refers to being strongly involved in one's work and experiencing a sense of significance and pride. Finally, absorption is characterized by being fully concentrated and happily engrossed in one's work (Shimazu et al., 2008).

1.1.4 Job engagement and Organizational engagement

Job engagement means feeling responsible for and committed to job performance; performance “matters” to the individual (Britt et al., 2007). The engagement reflects the extent to which an individual is psychologically present in a work place and also is definite about his / her organization role (Rothbard et al., 2001). The two dominant roles played by an employee are work role and role as a member of an organization (Saks, 2006). The responsibility and commitment to one's role ‘job engagement’, while towards one's organization is defined as organizational engagement. Though the definitions vary, certain themes are common to many of them: satisfaction with work, pride in employer, enjoyment in work, belief in work, and the perception that the employer values what the employee brings to the organization. Organizations' interested in building engagement are not guaranteed success, no matter how intently they pursue it—although it is possible for organizations to increase significantly their chances of building a more engaged workforce.

Employee engagement is a popular business concept today. A widespread lack of engagement is the root cause for many business problems. Over the year's organizations have invested a lot of resources and time in research, finding the satisfaction determinants and its extent. But they have realized that satisfaction isn't really that much of a driver of performance in the organization. Just because an employee is happy, doesn't mean that he/she has been working really hard or even working towards the direction of the organization's best interest.

Employee engagement is a strategic approach for driving improvement and encouraging organizational change. In spite of the few empirical researches on the factors that predict employee engagement, it is possible to identify a number of potential antecedents from the different studies conducted. Finally, a holistic view of employee engagement can be helpful to determine what is working and what is not. Predictors offer HR a way to better understand what

practices and policies in their organization effectively promote employee motivation, attendance, retention and productivity. By using a matrix of engagement predictors (organizational process, values, management, role challenges, work/life balance, information, reward/recognition, work environment and products/services), HR department can help the organization manage better engagement, foster motivation, productivity and retention. The level of employee engagement determines if employees are productive and stay with the organization—or quit and join the competitors.

1.1.5 Types of engaged employees

Three types of engaged employees as per the Gallup study:

- **Engaged employees** work passionately and feel a profound connection to their company. They drive creativity and innovation and move the organization to greater heights.
- **Not engaged employees** are those who are ‘checked out’. They’re sleepwalking through their workday, giving time – but not energy or passion – to their work.
- **Actively disengaged employees** aren’t just unhappy at work; they’re busy in voicing out their unhappiness. Every day these workers undermine and discourage what their engaged co-workers accomplish.

Another classification of engaged employees as suggested by Sirota:

- **Intellectually engaged** employees are constantly improving the company with new and creative ideas and innovations while maintaining a generally positive view of both the company itself, and their relationship with it.
- **Emotionally engaged** employees are proud, passionate and enthusiastic about the company.
- **Behaviourally engaged** employees are willing to go above and beyond ones roles and responsibility for the company, their customers, and their team members while advocating on behalf of company and remaining loyal.

1.1.6 Employee Engagement Aspects

According to the global studies three basic employee engagement aspects are: -

- The employees and their own unique psychological makeup and experience.
- The employers and their ability to create the conditions that promote employee engagement.

- Interaction between employees at all levels. Thus, it is largely the organization's responsibility to create an environment and culture conducive to this partnership, and a win-win equation.

Categories of Employee Engagement: - According to the Gallup the Consulting organization there are different types of people: -

Engaged - "Engaged" employees are builders. They want to know the desired expectations for their role so they can meet and exceed them. They're naturally curious about their company and their place in it. They perform at consistently high levels. They want to use their talents and strengths at work every day. They work with passion and they drive innovation and move their organization forward.

Not Engaged - Not-engaged employees tend to concentrate on tasks rather than the goals and outcomes they are expected to accomplish. They want to be told what to do just so they can do it and say they have finished. They focus on accomplishing tasks vs. achieving an outcome. Employees who are not-engaged tend to feel their contributions are being overlooked, and their potential is not being tapped. They often feel this way because they don't have productive relationships with their managers or with their co-workers.

Actively Disengaged - The "actively disengaged" employees are the "cave dwellers." They're "Consistently against Virtually Everything." They're not just unhappy at work; they're busy acting out their unhappiness. They sow seeds of negativity at every opportunity. Every day, actively disengaged workers undermine what their engaged co-workers accomplish. As workers increasingly rely on each other to generate products and services, the problems and tensions that are fostered by actively disengaged workers can cause great damage to an organization's functioning.

1.2 FACTORS LEADING TO EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

Studies have identified some critical factors which lead to Employee engagement. Some of them identified are shown in the fig below (Robinson, D. & S. Perryman, S. Hayday (2004)).

Career Development - Opportunities for Personal Development.

Organizations with high levels of employee engagement provide employees with opportunities to develop their knowledge and abilities, learn newer skills, acquire new methods and realize their potential. These organizations try to create a learning culture within the organization. Employees

are encouraged to take up training and developmental sessions so as to enhance their knowledge. Mandatory training modules and compulsory training sessions become a part and parcel of employees work life.

Career Development – Effective Management of Talent.

Organizations’ should have clear job descriptions. When companies plan for the career paths of their employees and invest in them, the employees might see a future in the organization and think of staying back in the organization. This is a two-way process where the organization can retain the talented human resources and also the employees can plan their future.

Fig 1.1 Factors Leading to Employee Engagement

Leadership - Clarity of Company Values – Leaders of the organization must have clarity on company values. These values need to be discussed at the lower levels in the organization. The vision, mission of the company should be displayed in appropriate places and communicated to all the stakeholders of the organization.

Leadership – Respectful Treatment of Employees – Employees should be treated with respect whatever is their nature of job in the organization. Trust and loyalty should be built in the organization. Belief in the employees will take the organization towards realizing its goals.

Leadership – Company’s Standards of Ethical Behaviors–The Company should have its own values and ethics. The employees need to be aware of all the standard policies of the organization. They should know the do’s and don’ts. Also, the consequences of not being ethical should be communicated to the employees.

Empowerment - Employees like to be involved in decisions which will affect their work and workplace. The top management of high engagement workplaces creates a challenging and trustful environment, in which employees are motivated to come out from the prevailing orthodoxy and to provide valuable inputs so that the organization can move forward.

Image – Image can be of two types. Image created by the product of the company and image created by the employer. In both the cases the employee feels good about the company he is working. If the employee is happy about the product and the company for which he/she is working they usually recommend it to friends and relatives.

Other factors

Equal Opportunities and Fair Treatment- Employee engagement increases if the top management treats everybody as equals. Fair treatment should be provided to all levels in the hierarchy and equal opportunity should be provided for growth and career advancement.

Performance appraisal –A good performance management system should be followed in the organization. Standards need to be set, communicated on a regular basis, appropriate appraisal methods should be adopted, and feedback should be provided. The feedback system need to be a transparent one so that the meritorious will be benefited. Performance based appraisal must be considered in the organization.

Pay and Benefits –Pay and benefits need to motivate employee to work in the organization. This should be above the industry standards so that the best talent can be attracted. Financial and non-financial rewards should motivate employees to remain in the organization and should not be a reason to exit from the organization.

Health and Safety –Studies have shown that employee engagement increases when the employee feels secure in the workplace. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct safety training programs in the organization. Employees should be provided with ergonomically tested workstations so that

they are not prone to certain occupational diseases. Apart from this the organization should provide adequate health care facilities.

Job Satisfaction –Job satisfaction is important for any employee to work in the organization. Challenging job roles, authority with responsibility, proper work environment, motivating employer –employee relationships lead to job satisfaction.

Open Communication - The Company should allow an open-door policy of communication. Both upward and downward communication with the appropriate communication channels in the organization should be encouraged. Employees need to be heard in decision making and the importance of employee suggestions should be communicated to the employees.

Family Friendliness – Employees need to balance both family and professional life. Organization should make efforts to include family friendly policies in the organization. This will increase the employee engagement levels.

Co-operation –Good superior subordinate relationship should flourish in the organization. Members in the organization should work as a team and all should aim at achieving organizational objectives.

1.2.1 Hygiene and Motivation Factors for Employee Engagement

Employee engagement has been identified and linked with every part of management in some or other way. Even though enough evidences are not available to support these direct relationships between engagement and other factors, but they show that they are indirectly connected with one another. In a similar manner, the hygiene and motivational factors are seen in association with employee engagement. In fact, these factors have shown to be dependable and used as predictors of the engagement level and involvement of employees towards their jobs.

Motivational factors are intrinsic factors and conditions that influence the level of involvement and employee engagement. These factors have the ability to satisfy an individual’s psychological needs including personal and professional growth, sense of achievement, proficiency and status in the organization. The psychological fulfillment at any point of an individual’s career plays a crucial role in determining his or her commitment towards ones work as well as the organization they are working for.

Hygienic factors are the extrinsic conditions that can motivate workforce to perform their very best and feel motivated and committed towards their work and organization. The factors included here are working conditions, remuneration, organizational culture, perks and benefits, security of job and relationship with colleagues and immediate supervisors and subordinates.

Fig 1.2 Hygiene and Motivation Factors for Employee Engagement

1.2.2 Motivation Factors

- **Recognition:** Recognition for an achievement in an organization is very important. Organizations should have a structured recognition method thereby appreciating the achievement by the employees. Recognition need to be provided both in the form of financial and non-financial incentives to the right employees.
- **Employee Empowerment:** Employees should be given the power and autonomy to decide on their own. This makes the employees more creative. When autonomy is given employees are encouraged to think from out of the box. Empowering employees gives the employees the freedom to plan and execute their work in a better way.

- **Career Progression:** Organizations should have clear career paths communicated to the employees. Employees should see a future in the organization. It is vital for the HR department to motivate employees to train themselves. Career progression should be based on the performance of the employees.
- **Personal and Professional Growth:** Along with achieving organizational goals personal growth of employees need to be taken care of. Enough scope and encouragement should be provided to enhance individual skills and develop newer knowledge.
- **Interesting and Challenging Work:** Jobs can become routine in nature. Boredom might set in the minds of the employees. Therefore, the HR must create a challenging work environment. The organization should be an interesting place to work. Challenging environment should be provided so that employees look forward to coming to the organization.
- **Sense of Achievement:** Employees should feel that they are part of the organization. Periodic appraisals should be provided and constant motivation is needed. Praise and recognition at the right time will motivate the employees to achieve greater heights.

1.2.3 Hygiene Factors

- **Remuneration and Benefits:** Remuneration and Benefits play an important role in maintaining the employees in the organization. There should be equity in the wage and salary administration of the organization. Clear cut pay grades should be maintained in the organization.
- **Job Security:** Human nature believes in security. Employees need a kind of job security in the organisation. Employees can remain loyal to the organisation and employers can acknowledge loyalty.
- **Relationships with Peers, Subordinates and Seniors:** Employees cannot achieve the organizational goals individually. They need to work as a team and also contribute to the overall success of the organization.
- **HR Policies and Procedures:** HR policies and practices should be drafted properly and communicated to the workers of the organization. Policies and Practices should be uniform and should not create ambiguity in the employees.

1.3 STRATEGIES OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

To have engaged workforce in any organization, employers need to look at the below mentioned points. These issues can be termed as “starters of engagement” because it is observed and believed that these will reduce the employee disengagement diseases (Bockerman, Petri; Ilmakunnas, Pekka (2012)).

1. Begin it on day one: Organizations have talent acquisition strategies, but most of them fail to have an effective retention strategy. Effective recruitment, selection and orientation programs need to be formulated as the first foundation blocks to be laid on day one of the newly recruited. Human Resource Managers should have effective staffing policy so that they will be able to choose the right candidate and also be able to extract the inherent and potential talents of the newly recruited candidate. The new employees who are hired should be given a general as well as job specific orientation. The general orientation should acquaint them with the goals objectives, vision, mission and values of the company. The job specific orientation should provide the potential candidate with realistic job previews, introduction to the department which they belong to, proper job descriptions and job expectations so that there will not be any role ambiguity and conflicts. After selection decisions are made the HR Manager needs to see that there is a proper fit between the job and person so that the individual will remain in the organization and will not find it difficult during the course of on boarding.

2. Involvement from the top management: Top management support is required for employee engagement and should be established with clear vision, mission and values. The top management should believe in it, own it and pass it to the employees. They need to change their management style and enhance their leadership skills so that employee engagement will not only be a “corporate HR fad” or “another HR slogan”. Employee engagement should not only be a word of mouth and a “lip-service” slogan, it needs a team of dedicated leaders and people who are action oriented in the organization. It requires “Leading by being an example and a role model”.

3. Open two-way communication: HR Managers need to provide a platform where two-way and open communication in the organization is possible. Employees should not be burdened with ideas which only originated from the top levels in the organization; instead employee should be given an opportunity and a chance to put forth their ideas and suggestions. The suggestions

should be acknowledged and appreciated. Involving the employees in decision making and having a clear and transparent communication will engage the employees in the organization.

4. Opportunities for career development: Independent decision making should be encouraged in the organization. Employees should be allowed and given the freedom to think differently and innovatively. The Key results should be focused rather than the methods of achieving the results. Autonomy should be the way of work life in the organization. This will surely engage the workforce in the organization.

5. Availability of resources: It is necessary to see to it that the employees are provided with all the necessary resources at the right time. Resources can be physical, material, financial, infrastructure related and information too. Resources need to be provided at the right time so that it does not hamper the effectiveness of the employee's performance and productivity.

6. Training at the appropriate time: Encouraging learning is a part of any good employer. Training should be made mandatory in the organization. Employees need to improve their skill, knowledge and also be able to develop their potential skills. The organizations should provide the necessary training platform and encourage the employees. It is generally seen that when employees know their work, when they are well trained confidence increases and commitment to the work and organization can be expected to increase. This will also lead a way forward to employee engagement.

7. Performance management and good feedback system: Organizations should develop a good performance management system. The system should be open and hold managers and employees accountable at their individual levels. Periodic surveys should be conducted so that the managers are aware of the factors important to key result areas. Also, these surveys can highlight areas of employee engagement. Driving factors of engagement can be prioritized in the organization and communicated to the top-level managers. A strong and open feedback should be encouraged to make employees and all in the organization accountable.

8. Reward immediately: HR Managers need to work out the benefits and services which will motivate employees. It should both in the form of monetary and nonmonetary rewards. Rewarding immediately and appreciating employee will go a long way in engaging employees in

the work place. Praise, appreciation and recognition do have a link with performance in the organization.

9. **Build a corporate identity:** A strong work culture should be built which is in tune with the corporate ethos. Company goals and values should be ingrained in the top-level officials and the same should flow downwards. Culture of mutual trust and respect should be built in the organization. Positive thoughts need to be encouraged in the workplace so that there is a constant motivation to work in the organization.

10. **Build on top performers:** Watson Wyatt Worldwide (2004/05) conducted a study with fifty US organizations and found out that companies that perform very well focus on the top performers of their company. They treasure these performers and follow a strategy of retaining them. By focusing on the top performer's organizations are able to meet their goals. The engagement drivers of these performers are concentrated rather than of all employees.

There is insufficient information on what are the challenges faced by leaders to improve employee engagement scores. All researchers generally focus on the drivers of employee engagement but they fail to recommend strategies to improve employee engagement in the organization. Definitely the above mentioned strategies would increase employee engagement scores, but at the same time organization should spend certain financial resources to derive the benefit.

1.4 MODELS OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

1.4.1 Zinger Model of Employee Engagement

David Zinger is an expert on engagement and is a consultant from Canada whose research work is designed and developed to foster relationships of employees and to increase employee engagement in the organisation. With above 25 years' experience in the field, he was successful in combing the past and present research work so as to bring out workable and practical approaches to achieve positive and substantial results.

On the basis of his thorough and exhaustive work on the idea of employee engagement, he has been able to introduce a practical model that focuses on various areas of employee involvement, engagement and dedication. This model is called the Zinger Model of Employee Engagement.

The findings provide organisations insights of twelve key findings that a manager should incorporate to achieve desired results.

Fig 1.3 Zinger Model of Employee Engagement [Source David Zinger 2009]

1. Achieve Results: Zinger model aims at higher levels of employee engagement and believes this will result in achieving and accomplishing the desired organisational objectives. Employees need to be motivated individually and also need to craft their own strategies to achieve personal goals and also achieve business goals.
2. Craft Strategies: Employee engagement could be achieved in the organisation if planning is appropriate. It requires top management to consider the employee well-being and also achieve organisational objectives. A balancing act between employer and employee is needed to craft strategies towards growth.
3. Enliven Roles: Jobs in the organisation should be interesting. Employees enjoy their work when they do what is interesting to them. Therefore, organisations should allow employees to take their decisions regarding their work and encourage employees to come with new ideas and creativity.

4. **Excel at Work:** Employees should be motivated to do their job and excel in whatever they do. When employee's performance meets standards and achieve results they need to be recognised in the organisation for their achievements. Excellence towards work should be the guiding force of each employee in the organisation.
5. **Get Connected:** Communication is crucial in an organisation. A two-way transparent communication should exist in the organisation. Superiors need to be associated with the subordinates and there should be open discussions in the organisation. Two-way communication should be encouraged for the development of the organisation.
6. **Be Authentic:** Top management, HR managers need to be authentic. They should be realistic and understand the problems of the employees. Values of the organisation should be passed onto the employees from the top. Ethics should be followed in the organisation.
7. **Live Recognition:** Recognition of employees for their good work in the organisation is important. Recognition of good work in front of other employees and peers so that a sense of pride is instilled in the minds of the employees.
8. **Fully Engage:** Results are accomplished in the organisation if employees are fully engaged and committed to do their work. Organisations should conduct studies on engagement and plan appropriate strategies to engage workforce since an engaged workforce is a great asset to the organisation.
9. **Identify with Organisation:** Employees need to feel a part of the organisation. If a sense of belongingness is felt within an employee he/she would work to the best of the ability and be loyal to the organisation.
10. **Serve Customers:** Customer service is the most important aspect organisations strive at. It is generally believed that happy employees pass on this to the customers. Serving the customer with delight is the order of the day.
11. **Develop Personally:** Along with the organisation growing it is important, an individual's career also grows. Enhancement of one's skill plays a vital part in career planning and development. Organisations should provide time and motivation to individuals to pursue their liking that can be linked to performance.
12. **Attain Happiness:** Satisfied and happy employees are the greatest assets of the organisation. The success behind any productive organisation is their engaged employees.

Thus, organisations should motivate the employees to involve themselves in the organisation and keep them engaged.

David Zinger Model identified these twelve aspects for developing an engaged workforce who are committed, involved and work towards the growth of the organisation.

1.4.2 Aon Hewitt’s Employee Engagement Model

Aon Hewitt’s model is a contribution towards the drivers of employee engagement. According to his findings six drivers enable to shape the outcomes within the organization or establishment, called “Engagement Drivers.”

Aon Hewitt defines engagement through three main attributes namely;

- Say - speak positively about the work place to potential employees, co-workers and customers.
- Stay - have an intense sense of belonging and desire to be a part of the organization.
- Strive - are motivated and exert effort toward success in their job and for the company.

Fig 1.4 Aon Hewitt’s Employee Engagement Model

Say, Stay and Strive are the results of employee engagement. These can be accomplished when the work experience of the employees is great. The work experience is dependent on a number of internal factors within the organization. Quality of work, company practices, the job, relationships in the organization, opportunities for growth, the total reward system all these factors contribute to the engagement levels in the organization. Thus, Aon Hewitt Model discusses on the drivers of employee engagement.

1.4.3 X Model of Employee Engagement

Organizations usually intend to maximize the contribution of each and every employee towards corporate business imperatives and goal metrics. Individual employees, in the meanwhile, try to find a purpose and satisfaction in and from their work.

Consequently, Blessing White's model on engagement showcases on an individual's:

- Contribution to achieving organisational goals and marching towards the company's success.
- Personal satisfaction of employees in the job role.

Based on White Model employee engagement theory, it is observed that aligning employees' goals, values, and aspirations with that of the organization is one of the best methods for achieving the organisational goals with engaged employees. Complete engagement represents an alignment of maximum job satisfaction ("I do my work because I like it") with maximum job contribution ("Through my job I achieve the organisational goals"). The index used to determine an employee's level of engagement contains items that reflect the two axes of contribution and satisfaction. By plotting a given population against the two axes on the engagement model diagram, 5 distinct employee segments are identified.

Full Engagement occurs at the alignment of maximum job satisfaction and job contribution

Fig 1.5 X Model of Employee Engagement

	Levels	Description for each level
A	The Engaged: High contribution & satisfaction	These employees in the organisation are at “the apex” of engagement where organisational and personal interests align with one another. They contribute fully to the organizations success and achieve great satisfaction in their job and nature of work. They are known for their discretionary effort and commitment. They know their job very well and value the organisation they are working for. Organizations must take care of these employees and keep them engaged, because any transition of these employees to three adjacent segments overtime would likely impact workforce morale commitment.
B	Almost Engaged: Medium satisfaction and medium contribution	This is a critical group, where employees are reasonably satisfied with their job and are also high performers in the organisation. Organizations should pay more attention and invest in them for mainly two reasons: They are more likely to be poached away by the competitors as they are highly employable; they are easily converted to engage employees as they have the shortest route and this is a huge benefit to the company.
C	Honeymooners & Hamsters: Medium to high	Honeymooners are new employees to the organization and their role are very happy to be in the organisation. They are yet to find their stride and role in the organisation. They are yet to clearly understand how

	satisfaction and low contribution	they can best contribute to the organisational development. Priority should be given to move these employees out of this temporary holding phase and to full align them with the organisation. Hamsters are employees who may be hard working, but are in reality “spinning their wheels,” and working on tasks which are non-essential. They contribute little to the success of the organisation. Employees at this stage may hide out and might be content in the current positions without any contribution to the organisation. Therefore, it is necessary for an organization to deal with them otherwise other employees may follow them.
D	Crash & Burners: Medium to high contribution but low satisfaction	Potentially exhausted and Disillusioned, these employees are top achievers who aren’t working to their fullest potential. These employees are the ones who contribute negatively in the organisation and usually voice their opinions against the top management. They keep voicing their opinion and quit the job or put very less efforts and contribute negligently to the organisation. With this mind set they may bring in negativity in workforce which is really not motivating.
E	The Disengaged: Low to medium contribution & satisfaction	Disengaged employees contribute very less to the organisational goals. They are disconnected with the organisation and do not know their role in the workplace. Their capacity to work is underutilized. They spread wrong information to customers or to other stake holders.

1.5 CONCLUSION

In the discussion from this chapter it is seen that employee engagement concept has a wide and varied meaning. Various definitions are put forward by many researchers in this area. Drawing a conclusion from all the researchers, employee engagement is identified as a psychological connect of the employees towards their organization. It can be measured as an outcome of customer delight, productivity and employer brand perception of the organization. Further the discussion moves towards classification of employees in terms of engagement and concludes that there are two basic classifications namely engaged employees and disengaged employees.

Characteristics of these employees are discussed at length. Employee engagement has gained strategic importance in the organization and therefore organizations should adopt effective strategies to plan and implement the same. Organizations which are able to implement these engagement strategies will be able to sustain in the competitive market. A number of employee engagement models are elaborated to understand the views of different authors so as to obtain a sound foundation in the concept.

CHAPTER TWO

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CHAPTER TWO

SERVICE SECTOR ANALYSIS

2.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE SERVICE SECTOR IN INDIA

The service sector in India plays a dominant role. In addition to the contribution to the economic growth, that is GDP, it has contributed in foreign direct investment, export and import of goods and services, and providing ample of opportunities in employment generation. The activities included in this sector are numerous. It includes hospitality, construction, retail, Banking and finance, education, social services and many more. The contribution to the GDP from this sector is around 54% [2017-18] and employee's around 29% of the total population. India has very distinctive competencies and competitive advantage because of its knowledge-based services which makes it more attractive than any other countries.

Globalization has contributed to a massive growth in the service sector. Globalization has been accompanied with digital revolution. Use of internet world wide has increased to a great extent. The Indian youth too are connected with the digital world which is a big asset to the county's growth.

Fig 2.1 Sector wise contribution to the GDP of India

Source: Ministry of statistics and program implementation Planning commission India

The above graph clearly depicts that there is a steady growth in the service sector. The contribution to GDP is growing year on year from this sector.

2.1.1 Growth of the service sector in India

The reasons for the growth of service sector are

Economic affluence: The middle-income households are growing at a faster pace and the very low-income groups are on a decline. The process of liberalization has had a strong positive influence on the Indian homes. The rise in income and expenditure creates a demand for the goods and services sector.

Changing Role of Women: Women are no longer confined to the four walls of the house. They are provided with higher education and encouraged to have a career of their own. This has given opportunity for a number of newer service providers. Working women prefer to hire the extra services as they cannot manage the multiple roles and tasks.

Cultural Changes: There have been vast changes in the cultural outlook of the people of India. Nuclear families have emerged. The past joint family system is slowly vanishing and giving rise to new service providers. The way people spend their leisure time, the pattern of investment, the outlook on eating habits have led to a new set of service providers.

Digital Revolution: The information sector has grown enormously and changed the nature of many businesses activities. The Indian population has highly skilled professionals who have been an asset to the entire globe. The boom in the IT sector has created many new businesses. At the same time this massive growth has also made negative imbalance in nature.

Development of New Markets: In the earlier days the wholesalers and retailers played an important place in the market. Today the market place has become a global village. At the finger tips people can access whatever they need and the entire gamut of marketing is changing.

Rapid Migration: People are moving to the urban areas for want of livelihood. They are in search of newer jobs. This migration has given rise to new set of business and services like growth in real estate, infrastructure etc.

Export orientation: India has a great potential to export many of its services. The country has knowledge-based employee set which is always in great demand. Tourism and software are the two famous services among foreign exchange.

Service Tax: The growth of this sector has also fetched income to the government. Therefore, the government encourages these sectors and provides additional benefits.

Life Expectance: The advances in the medical field has in general influenced and enhanced the life expectancy of a normal human being. This increased number of retired people who might seek newer and better services.

2.1.2 Services Categories based on Productivity Growth

Group 1 Traditional Services	Group 2 Hybrid [Traditional and Modern]	Group3 Modern
Wholesale and retail trade, storage facilities and public administration, defence.	Education, healthcare and social work, hotels and restaurants, other community, social, and personal services.	Financial intermediation, computer services, business services, communications, legal and technical services.

Source: Author's compilation from Eichengreen and Gupta (2010).

Eichengreen and Gupta have categorized the service sector into three subsectors based on their productivity. The fastest growing groups are three. Amongst this there is tremendous growth seen in banking, insurance, business communication and technical services of group3. Group 1 has least productivity whereas group 2 has a cost defective problem which leads to lower production. It is observed that the modern category of services provides more employment compared to others. Thus, the present study concentrates on three sectors namely banking, insurance and education sectors.

2.2 INSURANCE SECTOR

The Insurance sector in India has 53 Insurance companies out of which 24 are in life insurance business & 29 are in non-life insurance business. LIC is the sole public sector in the life insurance sector.

In India only 30% of the population is insured. i.e. 36 crore people are covered under the health insurance schemes. This sector has a huge potential to grow. The stake holders of this sector include agents, individuals, corporates, surveyors, third party administrators and brokers. There are 33 non-life insurance companies out of which five are registered to underwrite health, travel and personnel accident cases. They are Star Health and Allied Insurance Company Ltd, Apollo Munich Health Insurance Company Ltd, Religare Health Insurance Company Ltd, Cigna TTK Health Insurance Company Ltd and Max Bupa Health Insurance Company Ltd. There are two more specialized insurers belonging to public sector namely, Export Credit Guarantee Corporation of India for Credit Insurance and Agriculture Insurance Company Ltd for crop insurance.

2.2.1 Government Initiatives in the Insurance sector

The Indian Government has taken initiatives to encourage the rapid growth of the insurance industry. To name a few initiatives: [www.ibef.org]

- More than hundred million families were provided coverage under the National Health Protection Scheme launched under Ayushman Bharat.
- Under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Beem Yojana in the year 2017-18 about a 47.9 million farmers benefitted.
- New guidelines for insurance companies in India who are divesting equity through IPO is being redesigned by the Insurance regulatory and development authority of India (IRDAI).
- Insurers are allowed to invest up to 10% in addition tier 1 bonds that are being issued by the banks to augment tier 1 capital so as to expand the pool of investors in the Banks.

The General insurance in India has reached Rs. 78,000/- Crore, and is growing at a rate of 17 percent. The future of the insurance sector looks promising. The regulatory framework [IRDAI] in the insurance sector is bringing in a lot of changes and the Indian demographic characteristics may add to the future business.

Table 2.1 Life insurance Business Performance

Life Insurance Business Performance:	2015-16		2014-15	
	Public Sector	Private Sector	Public Sector	Private Sector
Premium Underwritten (Rs in Crores)	266444.21	100499.02	239667.65	88433.49
New Policies Issued (in Lakhs)	205.47	61.92	201.71	57.37
Number of Offices	4892	6179	4877	6156
Benefits Paid (Rs in Crores)	141201.05	60565.05	144125	67054
Individual Death Claims (Number of Policies)	761983	114697	755901	121927
Individual Death Claims Amount Paid (Rs in Crores)	9690.17	2946.49	9055.18	2733.49
Group Death Claims (Number of lives)	247504	297833	273794	192989
Group Death Claims Amount Paid (Rs in Crores)	2494.03	2303	2037.27	1483.55
Individual Death Claims (Figures in percent of policies)	98.33	91.48	98.19	89.4
Group Death Claims (Figures in percent of lives covered)	99.69	94.65	99.64	91.2
No. of Grievances reported during the year	64750	139951	80944	198048
Grievances resolved during the year	64750	145125	80944	193119
Grievance Resolved (in percent)	100	103.69[Last year included]	100	97.51

Source: Annual Report (2015-16 & 2014-15)

The above table clearly shows that the public sector has more than two times the insurance premium underwritten than the private sector. It is evident that the new policy issued by the

public sector is more than three times that of the private sector. The number of private sector offices is greater when compared to the public sector. This implies that the private sector is trying to reach out to a greater number of people. The data above also clearly indicates that the private sector is also very definite about solving the grievances of their clients.

Table 2.2 Non-Life Insurance Business Performance

Non-Life Insurance Business Performance:	2015-16		2014-15	
	Public Sector	Private Sector	Public Sector	Private Sector
Premium Underwritten (Rs in Crores)	47691	39694	42549.48	35090.09
New Policies Issued (in Lakhs)	8414	2389	8207	2200
Number of Offices	4892	6179	4877	6156
Net Incurred Claims (Rs in Crores)	38104.27	21764.44	31567.75	19430.46
No. of Grievances reported during the year	17808	41802	15860	44828
Grievances resolved during the year	17718	42493	16105	43318
Grievance Resolved (in percent)	99.49	101.65	101.54	96.63

Source: Annual Report (2015-16 & 2014-15)

The above table depicts that the non-life insurance business performance is identical to that of the life insurance business. The public sector has a huge market share but the private sector with the number of increased offices are trying to have an inclusive growth.

The number of private players in the insurance sector is increasing. Below is the list of private insurance companies;

2.2.2 Private Sector Life Insurance Companies

- Aegon Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Aviva Life Insurance Co. India Ltd.
- Bajaj Allianz Life Insurance Co. Ltd.

- Bharti AXA Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Birla Sun Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Canara HSBC Oriental Bank of Commerce Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- DHFL Pramerica Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Edelweiss Tokio Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Exide Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Future Generali India Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- HDFC Standard Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- ICICI Prudential Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- IDBI Federal Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- India First Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Kotak Mahindra Old Mutual Life Insurance Ltd.
- Max Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- PNB MetLife India Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Reliance Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Sahara India Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- SBI Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Shriram Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Star Union Dai-Ichi Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Tata AIA Life Insurance Co. Ltd.
- General Insurance Companies:

2.2.3 Private Sector Companies [General Insurance]

- Aditya Birla Health Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Bajaj Allianz General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Bharti AXA General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Cholamandalam General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Future Generali India Insurance Co. Ltd.
- HDFC ERGO General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- ICICI Lombard General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- IFFCO-Tokio General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Kotak General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- L&T General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Liberty Videocon General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Magma HDI General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Raheja QBE General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Reliance General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Royal Sundaram Alliance Insurance Co. Ltd.
- SBI General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Shriram General Insurance Co. Ltd.

- TATA AIG General Insurance Co. Ltd.
- Universal Sompo General Insurance Co. Ltd.

2.2.4 Drivers of Indian Insurance Industry

There are few factors that need to be considered for the growth of this sector (Shrutikeerti Kaushal, Amlan Ghosh, 2017);

- **Social Factors:** The new social trends are shaking up the present and traditional business models and the customer expectation is increasing. Customers today want transparency, and speed in the delivery of their products and services.
- **Technological Factors:** There has been a big wave of automation which has led to the development of knowledgeable customers. Use of smart phones, tablets and computers provide continuous information and access to the internet and customers have a bargaining power.
- **Environmental Factors:** There has been severe and frequent catastrophe of events both man-made and natural. A large portion of claims result from these calamities. Therefore, to manage these risks, the insurers should build new models of risk sharing and risk transfer deals.
- **Economic Factors:** The insurance sector can become globalised as a whole and for these countries can have harmonized regulations and standardized products. This will increase the market share and create more business in the value chain of the insurance sector.

2.2.5 Role of HRM in Insurance sector

The HR department should withstand the internal and external pressures. The internal pressure may include changing nature of job, demographic changes of workforce in the organization, training & development, cost management and many more. The external factors include changing regulatory framework, changing customer needs workforce diversity and so on.

Apart from these factors the insurance sector is not a destination for top scorers in the colleges. Therefore, it is necessary to the HR department to have policies which will attract the best talent and at the same time reconstruct and innovate to keep in pace with changing times. The insurance sector job comprises more of a marketing task that is selling of the insurance products. The basic qualification to get into this job is a graduation, and it is important for individuals to

have good communication skills so as to achieve their targets. The employers of this sector make aggressive recruitment. Insurance sectors invest in training of workforce and since the targets and work pressure increases the trained employees quit the organization. Thus, necessary measures are to be taken by insurance companies to retain employees after they are trained.

2.3 BANKING SECTOR

The Indian banking system is well organized, adequately capitalized and well regulated. There are a number of innovations in this sector in terms of payments & small finance banks. The RBI is also bringing in a lot of restructuring and helps to grow this sector. The Indian banking industry has 27 Public sector banks, 26 Private sector banks, 46 foreign banks, 56 Regional Rural banks, 1,574 Urban Co-operative banks and 93,913 Rural Co-operative banks. The market share of the Public sector banks is almost 70 percent. The growth in infrastructure projects, speedy implementation of technology has made the banking sector to come with new products and services. The mobile & internet banking has revolutionized the entire banking activities.

2.3.1 Indian Banking Sector - Structure

The Indian banking sector has its foundation way back from the 18th century and undergone drastic changes. Presently a large number of private and foreign players have entered the market and revolutionized this sector. The Reserve bank of India is the central bank of the country and holds the Apex Position in the country. It is called the bankers bank and has the monopoly of issuing notes. Commercial banks are institutions which accept deposit, provide business loans and offer related services like accepting deposits and lending loans and advances to individuals and industry. They exist to make profits. Commercial Banks include Public Sector Banks, Private Banks, Foreign Banks and Regional Rural Banks.

Fig 2.2 Structure of Indian Banking System [Source RBI]

Below is the list of Public Sector Banks with their Headquarters;

S No	Bank Name	Head Quarter/Office
1	Allahabad Bank	Kolkata
2	Andhra Bank	Hyderabad
3	Bank of Baroda	Vadodara
4	Bank of India	Mumbai
5	Bank of Maharashtra	Pune
6	Canara Bank	Bangalore
7	Central Bank of India	Mumbai
8	Corporation Bank	Mangalore
9	Dena Bank	Mumbai
10	Indian Bank	Chennai
11	Indian Overseas Bank	Chennai
12	Oriental Bank of Commerce	Gurugram
13	Punjab National Bank	New Delhi
14	Punjab & Sind Bank	New Delhi
15	Syndicate Bank	Manipal
16	UCO Bank	Kolkata
17	Union Bank of India	Mumbai
18	United Bank of India	Kolkata
19	Vijaya Bank	Bangalore
20	IDBI Bank Ltd	Mumbai
21	Bharatiya Mahila Bank	New Delhi

State Bank and its Associates;

1	State Bank of India	Mumbai
2	State Bank of Bikaner & Jaipur	Rajasthan
3	State Bank of Hyderabad	Hyderabad
4	State Bank of Mysore	Bangalore
5	State Bank of Patiala	Punjab
6	State Bank of Travancore	Thiruvananthapuram

All are Merged with State Bank of India

The Majority of the stake in Public Sector Banks is held by the government. They are listed in the stock exchanges and there are 27 of them.

The list of Private Banks in India is as Follows;

S. No	Bank Name	Head quarter
1	AXIS Bank Ltd.	Mumbai
2	Capital Local Area Bank Ltd.	Punjab
3	Citi Union Bank Ltd.	Tamilnadu
4	Coastal Local Area Bank Ltd.	Andhra Pradesh
5	DCB Bank Limited	Maharashtra
6	Dhanlaxmi Bank Ltd	Kerala
7	ICICI Bank Ltd	Mumbai
8	IndusInd Bank Ltd.	Mumbai
9	ING Vysya Bank Ltd.	Bangalore
10	Karnataka Bank Ltd.	Mangalore
11	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	Mumbai
12	Krishna Bhima Samruddhi Local.	Mahbubnagar
13	RBL Bank.	Kolhapur
14	Tamilnadu Mercantile Bank Ltd.	Tuticorin
15	The Catholic Syrian Bank Ltd.	Thrissur
16	The Federal Bank Ltd.	Kerala
17	The HDFC Bank Ltd.	Mumbai
18	The Jammu & Kashmir Bank Ltd.	Jammu and Kashmir
19	The Karur Vysya Bank Ltd.	Tamilnadu
20	The Lakshmi Vilas Bank Ltd.	Tamilnadu
21	The Nainital Bank Ltd.	Uttaranchal
22	The south Indian Bank Ltd.	Kerala
23	Yes Bank Ltd.	Mumbai

2.3.2 Growth of the Banking Sector

The steady economic growth, increasing disposable income, increased consumerism and easy accessibility to credit has made bank credits to grow at a faster pace. In march 2016 the credit extended surged to USD 1016 billion and growth has been seen from the retailers and corporate. The banking sector has seen an increased growth in deposits. The deposits have reached 1.54 trillion by the financial year 2017. Despite global instability the Indian banking sector has retained the confidence in the public for the past many years. Strong growth in savings with the disposable income has made banking deposits to grow. The government is also promoting banking with technology and pushing towards financial inclusion. Deposits by the Pradhan Mantra Jan Dhan Yojna have also increased deposits. Karnataka bank has been awarded twice by the Indian Banking Association for digitalization of banking activities and financial inclusion. The below graph shows the growth of deposits.

Fig 2.3 Growth in Bank Deposits

Source Reserve bank of India

The interest income has seen a Robust Growth in the Indian Banking sector. The contribution of the various banks is depicted in the graph below.

Fig 2.4 Interest income in Indian Banking sector

Source: Reserve Bank of India

From the above graph it is very clear that the Public sector banks contribute to 71.7% of interest income in the sector. The contribution of the private sector is also increasing year on year.

Private Banks lead in maintaining low NPA [Non-Performing Assets] level.

Despite global crisis the Indian banking sector has been able to lower the NPA. Gross NPA to gross advances stood at 9.39% in the public sector banks and a low of 2.90% in the private sector banks and 4.26% in the foreign banks. Thus, the private sector banks are making their presence felt in the Indian Banking Sector.

2.3.3 HRM practices in Banking Sector

To deal with customers any organization should have a very good Human resource management system for the efficient working of its human resources. Banking is a business which deals with knowledgeable people. Thus, an effective and efficient human resource management department will make the organization competitive.

Banking is a service oriented industry and the nature of banking business has changed and grown drastically, thereby making it a necessity to have a strong human resources management system. At present, management of knowledge workforce, along with handling economic and financial risks is the greatest challenge of the banking industry in the present time frame. Talented workforce in the banking sector is the need of the hour and the HR department should make all efforts to tap the skilled manpower. Finding the right talent and placing them in the right job is the responsibility of the HR department and this should be done with great care in this sector.

Apart from the financial and economic risks in this sector, customer satisfaction is also a key concern. Customers mindset should be understood while dealing with their banking activities. Thus, the front office staff who deal with the clients should be approachable and they are the face of the banks. Therefore, it is a necessity to select candidates who have the right aptitude and attitude. Once, selected candidates should go through the necessary training modules and be acquainted with the nuances of the industry and build a strong and motivated workforce. The HR department should strategically work along with the top management and see to that the right mix of employees is available at all point of times in the organization.

2.3.4 Importance of Human Resource Management in Banking Sector

- **Planning ahead for selection and recruitment:** The banking industry is ever changing and with a speedy growth, nature of banking business too has seen a sea change. Both the private sector and public sector banks are increasing the number of branches and moving towards total financial inclusion thus creating more and more vacancies. The HR department of these banks are responsible to provide the required manpower skills by estimation and looking into the future requirements of the organization.
- **Maintaining a balance of youth and experienced in the workforce:** With the Information technology revolution the banking sector has seen a major shift in the nature of business. Online banking and core banking are taking a stride in this sector and there needs a youth energy to keep pace with digitalization. At the same time the experienced staff are required to think strategically and there should be a balance strike off between the youth and older generation in the banks. Here the HR is responsible to maintain a balance between the two groups, fit both categories into the organization and keep them engaged.

- **Training of the workforce:** Technology has influenced the way business transactions happen in the banking sector. Apart from the traditional banking activities banks are coming out with new policies, schemes, and products which keep changing from time to time. The employees need to be updated with the banking activities and thus HR has a role to provide them with the latest training modules. Once these training activities are conducted HR needs to empower employees and measure their performances so as to meet the industry standards.
- **Talent spotting and Performance management:** The HR department is responsible to have an efficient performance management system in the organization. The performance management system should be transparent. Performance standards need to be communicated to the employees followed with a good performance appraisal. Timely feedback should be provided, so that the weaker employees can concentrate on their weakness and the good performance need to be praised and appreciated.
- **Keeping a watch on the personal requirements of the employee:** The employees of the company should feel valued. Perks and incentives need to be given, at the same time it is necessary to keep them informed about the whereabouts of the organization. Once a sense of belongingness is felt employees will work harder because they will feel proud to be associated with the organization.
- **Taking care of retirements and resignations:** Talent retention is the responsibility of the HR. Strategies need to be followed to maintain the best talent of the organization. When employees retire, exit interviews can be conducted to get better insights and suggestions. When positions are vacant the HR department should see to that succession planning is done and the right employees fill in the positions.

Thus, it can be concluded that the banking sector is a very wide financial and economic industry, which depends on the efficiency and effectiveness of its workforce. Thus, managing and maintaining this group of dynamic workforce becomes the major priority for the HR department in all the banks.

2.4 EDUCATION SECTOR

The Indian higher education system is growing at fast pace. The sector has the largest number of universities with approximately 850 universities [April 2018] and 42026 colleges. The

enrollment to higher education has reached to 35.7 million people for the year 2016-17. The government of India has also allowed 100% FDI in this sector. This sector is rapidly changing with private players entering the field. Also, the Indian demographic profile means a lot to this sector. Almost fifty percent of India’s population is youth. With an increase in household income, separate funds are created for the purpose of education of the children. The government initiatives too are encouraging more enrollments in the higher education in India.

Fig 2.5 Number of Universities in India
Source UGC

The above graph shows the year on year development of education sector in terms of number of universities. The University can be spilt in state university, deemed to be University, central university and private university. Below is the graph that shows the composition Universities.

Fig 2.6 Type of Universities in India
Source UGC

2.4.1 Investment and Recent Development in the Education sector

As per the data by the department of industrial Policy and promotion (DIPP) the amount of foreign direct investment inflow was \$1.67 Billion to the Indian education sector during the period of April 2000 to 2017 December. It is also seen that there have been major investments in the education and training sector. The major developments include:

- There have been more than 18 major merger and acquisitions in the Indian Education sector during the period of 2017.
- To develop the infrastructure needed for education and training the Human resources Ministry is planning to raise one lakh crore from individuals who have high net worth and also from private companies who are doing well.
- The World Bank and India have come in for an agreement under “Skills Acquisition and Knowledge Awareness for Livelihood Promotion’ (SANKALP) Project to enhance and develop institutional mechanisms for skill development in the country”.
- A Foreign country Singapore has come forward to open a skill development centre in India which will provide skill development and vocational training to the Indian youth.

2.4.2 Government Initiatives in education sector

The Government of India has taken some major initiatives in the education sector:

- The funds allocated for education in the schools during the present Union budget is predicted to increase by fourteen percent and also the government is focussing on improving the quality of education.
- With Rs. 6655 crores being sanctioned by the Government two new skill development programmes are initiated “Skills Acquisition and Knowledge Awareness for Livelihood Promotion (SANKALP) and Skill Strengthening for Industrial Value Enhancement (STRIVE)” with the help of World Bank
- India has had a financial agreement with the world bank for a credit of US\$ 125 TO execute “Skills Strengthening for Industrial Value Enhancement Operation (STRIVE) Project”.
- “NITI Aayog” has launched the “Mentor India Campaign” which aims to bring industrial leaders and students together which has become a part of the “Atal innovation mission”

in about 900 labs. Many school children across India are a part of this event and benefited tremendously. This is a continuous programme to reduce the industry academy gap.

- Funds are allocated to build institutes of repute in the country. Premium institutes like the IITs and IIMs are considered under this scheme.
- “Ek Bharat Shreshtha Bharat (EBSB) campaign” is promoted in the country so that there is unity between states, ministries, education institutes, universities, students and citizens of the country.
- “Kushal Bharat” is a program launched by the Prime Minister of India to train millions of youth so that they can develop certain skills and find a job for themselves.
- “Kushal Bharat” includes various schemes like: “Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY), National Policy for Skill Development and Entrepreneurship 2015, Skill Loan scheme, and the National Skill Development Mission”.

2.4.3 Human Resource Practices in Education Sector

An education institute is known by the employees who perform the main function of teaching. Teaching and developing new knowledge are the prime focus for which higher education institutes exist. Highly motivated teaching staff is an asset to the organization. Today universities are finding it difficult to get the required human resources. They are also facing the challenges of the corporate world. The HR department needs to strike a balance between faculty, students and other members in the organization. Retention of talented faculty, motivating them and managing them are key issues concerned with the HR department.

The education system plays a very dominant role in building the society. Teachers who are a part of this system play or occupy a key position to mould and influence the younger generation of the country. Higher education institutes therefore must give great concern to select the right kind of resources to the teaching profession. The HR initiatives in these universities should be able to procure the right mix of people so that they are retained and build the right values in the students. Quality education should be the concern for any developing country.

Attracting talented workforce and retaining them is a key concern for many colleges and universities. Therefore, it is necessary to build strong HR policies in the education sector so that the best talent is acquired.

Eminent faculty should remain in the institutes. The higher education institutes should foster the concept of succession planning. Too much turn over in the institutes will bring in negative thoughts in the students and they may lose focus. Therefore, the HR needs to plan in such a manner that their talented workforce remains with them and can gain a competitive advantage.

Talent management strategies should be initiated in the organization. Training should be a part and parcel of the institution's strategy. Faculty should be encouraged to refresh their knowledge and keep themselves updated with the latest trends. This will create a pool of talented workforce in the organization.

The goals of the individual faculty must be recognized. The strengths of each one should be identified. These should be matched with the organizational needs. Therefore, the organization should benefit from the individual learning. Education Institutions should develop a strong HRM policy and practices which will enable them to find the right person to the job and also retain the same. Commitment from the teaching fraternity can be obtained if regular incentives, motivation, recognition and constructive feedback are given.

Thus, the Education sector has seen a number of reforms. The government has also invested heavily and further funds are allocated to improve this sector. With such initiation India is possibly going to be one of the destinies for higher education. As this sector is gaining importance we see an increase in the talented workforce. Presently it is observed that more and more funds are allocated for the infrastructure development in this sector. Also, the educated human resources are gaining prominence in the developing country like India.

2.5 CONCLUSION

As discussed above, it is seen that the service sector has definitely contributed to the economic growth of our country. It is a major sector contributing to the GDP of the country. This sector is providing plenty of job opportunities to the youth of the country. Tremendous growth opportunities are seen in the banking, insurance and educational sector. The government initiatives are still driving these sectors to greater heights. The change in nature of service and business depends on the influence of external factors which keep changing from time to time. To generate profits and sustain in the turbulent business scenario organizations need to have diverse

workforce who can adapt to the changes and engage themselves to the organization they are working for.

CHAPTER THREE

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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CHAPTER THREE

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

3.1 REVIEW OF RESEARCH ARTICLES

3.1.1 Harter, Schmidt, and Hayes (2002) in their study performed a meta-analysis of the previous studies that were conducted on employee engagement by the Gallup group of organizations. The study examined the relationship between employee satisfaction and engagement and the various business outcomes namely productivity, customer satisfaction, profit, employee turnover and employee safety aspects in the organization. From the study it was noted that employee engagement was related to actionable quality of measured concepts. The study showed a positive relationship between satisfaction and engagement. It was also observed that the business units which had high engagement score had higher percentage of profitability and also depicted lesser employee turnover. (Harter et al., 2002).

3.1.2 May, Gilson, and Harter (2004) These researchers conducted a survey in one of the largest mid-western insurance agencies. Using a questionnaire, they were able to explore why some employees engage themselves in work while others get alienated and disoriented in work place. This study came up with a conclusion that engagement is different from job satisfaction. The study supported that engagement means the active use of emotions and behavior along with cognition. The study supported KAHNS work and definition. In addition to this job enrichment, role fit, having good peer's colleagues and superiors brought about a feeling of safety in the work place and job as such.

3.1.3 Ulrika Eriksson Hallberg (2005) The study explained the relationship of “being on fire” and total burn out in the organization. This study focused on two very important aspects namely involvement in work which is termed as Work Engagement and the type a behavior of employees. The study was conducted with samples from Healthcare sector and Information communication consultants. The findings of this study were similar to a Swedish version which indicated burnout as the result of bad health condition of the employee rather than involvement and organizational commitment. It also indicated that burnout is more to do with emotional

exhaustion of employees. This study further proceeds to find out the ways and methods to explore how job redesigning can enhance work engagement.

3.1.4 David S. Gill (2007), “Employee Selection and Work Engagement: Do Recruitment and Selection Practices Influence Work Engagement?”, the objectives were to identify if the employees staffing practices namely selection and recruitment had an impact on work engagement and also to measure the impact of these selection tools on engagement, organizational policies and practices. The study supported the existing literature on antecedents and outcome of employee engagement which insisted to include human resources practices such as selection test, realistic job previews as antecedent of employee engagement. Further a study was conducted to predict employee engagement on the individuals in organization and employee engagement on organizational outcomes (customer satisfaction, profit etc.). The study concluded that human resources practices should be included in the work engagement model.

3.1.5 Gabriel M. De La Rosa (2008), This study used a survey of responses from the employees working in the United States of America and Other Foreign Companies to understand the application of Job Demands Control Support (JDCS Model). The findings of this study supported Karasek’s (1989) understandings of JDCS Model. The model suggested a linear relationship between perception of demand, control and support to employee engagement. Employees need to understand Job Demand, Job Support and Control of Job which influences employee engagement. The study also indicates that cultural values influence work and job engagement.

3.1.6 Andrew J. Wefald and Ronald G. Downey (2009), he investigated “the factor structure of W. B. Schaufeli et al.’s measure of engagement and academic engagement’s relation to academic satisfaction and found the Employee Engagement and Job Satisfaction to be highly related constructs. The Previous researchers found a 3-factor structure of engagement that comprises vigor, dedication, and absorption. The authors administered to a sample of university students, a questionnaire on their level of engagement in academic work and various other measures. The results did not confirm the 3-factor structure”.

3.1.7 Susan L. Sweem (2009), the study titled as “Leveraging Employee Engagement through a Talent Management Strategy: Optimizing Human Capital through Human Resources and Organization Development Strategy in a Field Study”. The field study was done in an US unit of

Coating / Chemical company, and the study investigates to find out whether talent management strategies effect employee engagement. The study investigates to find out if human resources practices and Organizational development practices in an organization influence and support talent management. The study uses the mixed method of approach to understand the intervention and compare it with the US business units through a well drafted questionnaire, Structured interviews and concluded that the talent management was a result of good improved work environment, open-door policy and clear-cut top management communications. According the study the construct of employee engagement are supervisors who are mentors, trust in the organization, challenging work environment, commitment to the organization. Based on the study there is a positive relationship between talent management and employee engagement.

3.1.8 Alan M. Saks (December 2011), the study “Workplace spirituality and employee engagement” describe the importance of Workplace Spirituality for Employee Engagement Maintenance. A model of workplace spirituality and employee engagement is presented in which three dimensions of workplace spirituality (transcendence, community, and spiritual values) relate to employee engagement through four psychological conditions (meaningfulness in work, meaningfulness at work, safety, and availability).

3.1.9 Junghoon Lee (2012), this study empirically tested relationships among antecedents and consequences of employee engagement in the hotel industry. The study in particular, provided theory-based empirical evidence regarding whether employee evaluations of self (i.e., core self evaluations) and perceptions of organizational environment (i.e., psychological climate) affect employee engagement. This study also investigated how employee engagement directly and indirectly leads to intrinsic rewards, job satisfaction, personal attachment to an organization (i.e., organizational commitment), and the (LMX). Results of hypothesis testing showed that core self evaluations and three components of psychological climate (managerial support for service, interdepartmental service, and team communication) positively influence employee engagement. The results revealed that employee engagement is also positively associated with all the outcome variables. This study further demonstrated that LMX mediates the relationships of employee engagement with job satisfaction and organizational commitment; job satisfaction mediates the relationships between employee engagement and organizational commitment and also between LMX and organizational commitment.

3.1.10 Pati Surya Prakash & Pankaj Kumar (July 2010), “Employee Engagement: Role of Self- Efficacy, Organizational Support & Supervisory Support.” This study argues that differences between Self –Efficacy levels in employees are primarily responsible for differences in displayed Engagement. Based on the findings the study argues and defines engagement as expressed empowerment pertaining to a role thus enriching the management literature concerning engagement. They conclude that employee engagement necessitates a workforce that is attributed with self-efficacy as a dispositional trait. They also argue that empowered employee can be expected to be engaged. Also, it is pointed that this condition may not hold well in bureaucratic organizations. Further they say that the absence of anyone of the empowerment conditions shall result eventually in disengagement. More specially, the absence of self efficacy shall inhibit individuals from self expression thus forcing them to limit their activities to extremity scripted roles.

3.1.11 Rama J. Joshi & J.S. Sodhi (2011), “Drivers of Employee Engagement in Indian Organizations”. This study is one among the good studies to access the determinants of employee engagement in Indian based on series of studies. This study is conducted by Shri Ram Center to analyze organizational climate and its role in driving employee engagement. The perception of about 40,000 employees was sought to brought to light work life balance, Job Content, Monetary Benefits and Team Orientation as common drivers of employee engagement. Three key drivers of engage rewards and Welfare facilities. This study has found the drivers of engagement in Indian scenario.

3.1.12 Saradha H and Dr Harold Andrew Patrick (2011), “Employee Engagement in Relation to Organizational Citizenship Behavior in Information Technology Organizations” As per author several literatures on OCB have highlighted the relationship between OCB and productivity, in-role performance, and business unit performance. However there has been no research established to find out if there is any influence of OCB on employee engagement. The research deals with two constructs relevant to employees, organizational behavior namely employee engagement and organizational citizenship behavior which influences the organization’s performance. The aim of the research presented in this paper is to investigate which among the drivers of employee engagement has the highest influence on employee engagement. 235 employees were surveyed and a reliable and standardized instrument was adopted. The findings

indicated moderate level of engagement and OCB experienced by employees and significant relationship was found between engagement and OCB. Current career intention, job satisfaction, pay & benefits, management, equal opportunities, and organization citizenship behavior had a significant influence on employee engagement. The detail findings and implications are discussed in the paper.

3.1.13 Ravichandran K. et al (2011), “The Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Work Engagement Behavior: An Empirical Study” The objectives of this study were to understand the linear association between the Emotional Intelligence and Work Engagement behavior and to identify the dominant variables of Emotional Intelligence which influence the Work Engagement behavior. In the research it is found there is a significant linear association between the Overall Emotional Intelligence and Overall Work Engagement behavior. It is critically observed the pearsons correlation co-efficient value of 0.377 indicates positive weaker relationship between the above said variables which reflects Emotional Intelligence behavior alone will not influence Work Engagement behavior. It is suggested that the managers need to identify those variables which influence Work Engagement behavior apart from the existing Emotional Intelligence construct variables used for this study. The factor analysis for the study extracts eight dimensions out of 29 variables in the research after reviewing Emotional Intelligence construct. Suggestions were given to managers to focus on these eight Emotional Intelligence dimensions when they explore Emotional Intelligence study.

3.1.14 Priyanka Anand (2011), the study focuses on the two important HR practices of performance appraisal and employee engagement in the hotel industry. The research was conducted in ITC Maurya evaluates their practices relating to HR processes. The basic methods and systems are described keeping in mind the general trend in the Industry. ITC Maurya conducts the Q12 gallup survey on its employees, this method is used to access the existing levels of satisfaction amongst employees. The study found that the employees were involved and highly satisfied with the work environment. The performance appraisal standards are updated and different methods of appraisal are used across the organization. The employees were aware of the criteria for appraisals and also related a sense of importance to them. The incentives and initiatives taken by the Hotel for various levels in the organization were communicated to all the employees.

3.1.15 Vaijayanthi P. et al (2011), the main purpose of this study is to ascertain the status of employee engagement and the factors that impede better employee engagement. The study found that the factors are confirm infrastructure, cross functional discussions, communication and interaction with the corporate office employees, reflection on the feedbacks and proper support and orientation the locations/offices, lack of accountable response from the corporate office for issues including dearth of personnel, employee facilities, deficient communication regarding seminars, workshops, and other training sessions from the corporate office, and inadequate visits by the business team to be the tumbling blocks for better employee engagement.

3.1.16 Rabiya Sange and R.K. Srivastava (2012) “Employee Engagement and Mentoring: An Empirical Study of Sales Professionals.” This research attempts to find whether being a part of the mentoring relationship enables employee engagement. The researchers took survey sample of 170 sales / marketing professionals at different levels in the organizational hierarchy of Mumbai region. They came to a conclusion that, there was a significant difference in the employee engagement scores of respondents who were a part of mentoring relationship. This indicates that the organizations that plan to invest their resources in establishing a mentoring program will see a significant effect on the employee engagement levels of their work force.

3.1.17 Neelam Lal et al (2013), worked on “Employee Engagement via Talent Management”. She studied innovative practices of TATA Motors Pune for adopting Employees Engagement through Talent Management. They correlated Employees Engagement and Job Satisfaction with Talent Management Practices.

3.1.18 Vishal Gupta and Sushil Kumar (2013), “Impact of performance appraisal justice on employee engagement: a study of Indian professionals”. Performance appraisal is the most important human resource management practices as it yields critical decisions integral to various human resource actions and outcomes. The purpose of this study is to explore the relationship between perceptions of performance appraisal fairness and employee engagement in the Indian business context. The study was conducted in two parts. The first part explored the relationship between justice perceptions and a one-dimensional conceptualization of engagement. The second part explored the relationship between justice perceptions and a three-dimensional conceptualization of engagement. The relationships between justice perceptions and engagement

were analyzed using zero-order correlations and hierarchical regression analysis. The results of the study show that distributive justice and informational justice take precedence over procedural justice. Employees who feel that they have been given fair ratings also tend to believe that the procedures followed are fair and just. When an employee feels that the outcomes (salary hike, rewards, etc.) commensurate with the effort put in, he/she reciprocates it with greater vigor, dedication and is more engaged (physically, cognitively and emotionally) in his / her job. The study findings suggest a significant positive association between distributive and informational justice dimensions and employee engagement. Distributive justice and informational justice dimensions were found to have a stronger impact on employee engagement conceptualized as antipode of burnout.

3.1.19 Hale, Richard T (2016), in his research study focused on individual personality, the perceived quality of employees working relationships with their supervisors, and their work roles contribute to employee engagement. They worked based on the Big five model of personality and perceived quality of relationship with one's supervisors based on LMX [Leader-Member-Exchange] theory.

3.1.20 Richards, Wayne K, Jr DBA (2013), The potential for increasing productivity through increased employee engagement was examined in this sliding. The analysis indicated that (a) the lived experiences of employees influenced employee engagement, (b) employee engagement affects organizational commitment & performance (c) trust & respect & leadership are essential components to keep employee engage.

3.1.21 Suehs Derrick (2014) quantitative study to explore the relationship between the emotional intelligence of frontline Managers & Supervisors and the degree of employee engagement of their direct reports in a tertiary care health care setting.

The health care industry is moving from volume- based fee-for- service financial reimbursement system to a value-based purchasing model. This study found that there was a favorable relationship between emotional intelligence and employee engagement.

3.1.22 Ricklefs, Kevin MS (2016), The findings of the study demonstrated that for employees over one year of experience, 4 engagement drivers made the most meaning full impact on

individual and team productivity. The engagement drivers most impacting employee productivity were having access to work-life balance, having positive relationship with their team & leader, having work that is meaning full & having authority and autonomy of making decisions affecting their work. The study demonstrated that first year employee's value employment factors such as building necessary job skills and establishing effective relationship contribute to the team & company.

3.1.23 Dyer, Sheldon D.B.A(2013), Results of this study indicated that there were significant differences in reporting engagement by employment type and by gender.

3.1.24 Thiagarajan B & Renugadevi V (2011), conducted research on “An empirical investigation on Employee Engagement Practices in Indian BPO Industries”, and the purpose of this research article is to introduce employee engagement and key research on engagement related factors in BPO Industries in India. The authors conducted a literature search on employee engagement and interviews with 126 executives. Career development, performance appraisal and motivation factors are connected to employee engagement. The implications are that leaders should be educated on engagement, career development opportunities are particularly important and that performance improvement should champion work life balance, these practices are useful to increase engagement.

3.1.25 Sakari Taipale, Kirsikka Selander, Timo Anttila, Jouko (2011), conducted research on “Work engagement in eight European countries: The role of job demands, autonomy, and social support” aim of this paper was to build upon established theories about job demands and autonomy, it uses a newer work engagement approach, produces cross-national knowledge about work engagement.

3.1.26 Rehman Muhammad Safdar & Waheed Ajmal (2011), conducted research on “An Empirical Study of Impact of Job Satisfaction on job Performance in the Public Sector Organizations”. The purpose of this descriptive-correlational study was to test link between job satisfaction, job retention and job performance. Sample of 568 employees from public sector regulatory authorities was selected for this study. Employing a descriptive correlative survey method data was collected through questionnaire. The employees were generally satisfied with

their jobs. This study has explored a relationship showing large effect size correlations ($r = 0.52$) between job performance and job satisfaction.

3.1.27 Mamta, Sharma R. Baldev (2011), conducted research on “Study of Employee Engagement and its Predictors in an Indian Public Sector Undertaking”. This article presents an assessment of the level of employee engagement among managers of a public sector undertaking in India. Besides highlighting the level of engagement, the study has identified the predictors of organizational commitment, which was used as an important manifestation of employee engagement. The study is based on primary data collected from 84 managerial employees on a number of parameters relating to employee engagement and its potential predictors. The study has revealed that the level of employee engagement in this organization is quite modest. Three factors, namely, pay, job content and objectivity are found to be the predictors of employee engagement.

3.1.28 Sharma Baldev R et al (2010), conducted research on “Determinants of Employee Engagement in a Private Sector Organization: An Exploratory Study” aimed to ascertain the level of employee engagement and the determinants thereof among the sales executives of a private sector organization. Sample for the study consists of 51 sales executives of a manufacturing organization located in the National Capital Region. Data were collected with the help of an 80-item "structured" questionnaire and analyzed using the SPSS package. The findings show an across-the-board low rating on all 14 parameters of the study. Multiple regression analysis revealed that four out of the 12 potential predictors, all of which belong to the situation within which the employees are working, are the critical determinants of employee engagement.

3.1.29 Krishnan Sandeep K & Singh Manjari (2010), conducted research on “Outcomes of intention to quit of Indian IT professionals”. This study explores performance orientation, organizational deviance, and organizational citizenship behavior as outcomes of intention to quit of Indian IT professionals. These factors become critical in the context of human resource management because employees who want to quit may become less productive or even dysfunctional for the organization. Further, exploration using structural equation modeling shows

that performance orientation mediates the relationships between intention to quit and organizational citizenship behavior as well as between intention to quit and organizational deviance. This study's findings imply that organizations need to understand that employees with a high intention to quit can prove costly from multiple dimensions.

3.1.30 Childs Julian H & Stoeber Joachim (2010), conducted research on “Self-Oriented, Other-Oriented, and Socially Prescribed Perfectionism in Employees: Relationships with Burnout and Engagement”. This study examines how individual differences in self-oriented, other-oriented, and socially prescribed perfectionism were associated with burnout and engagement in a sample of 106 employees. Results of correlation and regression analyses showed that perfectionism explained variance in all facets of burnout (exhaustion, cynicism, reduced efficacy) and engagement (vigor, dedication, absorption). Whereas socially prescribed perfectionism was associated with higher levels of burnout and lower levels of engagement, self-oriented and other-oriented perfectionism were associated with lower levels of burnout and higher levels of engagement.

3.1.31 Greenwood Michelle (2007), conducted research on “Stakeholder Engagement: Beyond the Myth of Corporate Responsibility”. The objectives of this article are to transcend the assumption that stakeholder engagement is necessarily a responsible practice. Stakeholder engagement is traditionally seen as corporate responsibility in action. Indeed, in some literatures there exists an assumption that the more an organization engages with its stakeholders, the more it is responsible. This simple 'more is better' view of stakeholder engagement belies the true complexity of the relationship between engagement and corporate responsibility. Stakeholder engagement may be understood in different ways and from a variety of different theoretical perspectives.

3.1.32 Jyotsna (2007), conducted research on “Talent management strategy of employee engagement in Indian ITES employees: Key to Retention”. The study indicated that a good level of engagement may lead to high retention, but only for a limited time in the ITES sector. The need for a more rigorous employee engagement construct is indicated by the study. Practical implications for retention in the BPO/ITES sector are referred to employee engagement.

3.1.33 Alexandra Michel March (2015) Smart phone use and work -home interference. The moderating role of social norms and employee work engagement, *Journal of occupational and organizational psychology*, volume 88 March 2015. Work in modern world society is facilitated by communication Technology involves connectivity, immediacy and a blurring of boundaries between work and non-work domains. Two potential moderators of work -home interference (WHI) are examined (1) social norms represented by the influence of colleagues and supervisors regarding availability after work hours and (2) work engagement. The findings suggest that engaged workers can prevent from interfering too much with their private lives even when they use their smart phone during evening hours.

3.1.34 Tom McMullen (2013), This paper suggests right recommendation to improve employee engagement building a business case, measure engagement, making managers accountable, connect people with future going beyond compensation, and include employees and managers in reward design use engagement metrics communicate the value of what you have.

3.1.35 V Kumar, Anita Pansari (2015), In the research papers measuring the benefits of employee's engagement the findings suggest that measuring employee engagement can reveal the areas of employee's development that need attention employees personify the company's service philosophy and having highly engaged employees is associated with higher profit growth.

3.1.36 Liat Eldor, Itzak Harpaz (2016), Employee engagement is used to a key mechanism for explaining the relation between perception of organizations learning climate and employee's proactivity, knowledge sharing creativity and adaptivity. It was revealed that employee engagement mediates the relationship between the perceived learning climate and extra role behavior.

3.1.37 Fatma Jaupi, Shyqyri Leaci (2015), The focus of this paper is to establish the relationship between employee engagements with organizational communication. The study suggests organizational communication and demographic variables have a strong impact on employee engagement.

3.1.38 Aakamshakataria, Remu Raslogi & Pooja Garg (2013), Organizational study suggest that engagement is significantly associated with perceived organizational effectiveness. It also

entails positive impact upon the organizational effectiveness. It indicates the role of HR managers in delineating the psychological fabric of organization and condition for high engagement. It also highlights that engagement is an expedient phenomenon that drifts organizational effectiveness.

3.1.39 Daniel A Cernasortiz (2013), The Study found a positive association with normative commitment while engagement has had a non-significant positive association with continuance commitment. Negative association was not found between engagement and continuance commitment.

3.1.40 Dania Manciangli (2015), The researchers suggest three winning strategies using technology to increase employee engagement, connect more closely with customers, celebrate major milestones in style and recognize and reward employee and make it meaningful. These can build customer and employee engagement.

3.1.41 Ivan T Robertson, Cary L Cooper (2009), The view in the paper focuses on full engagement which includes employee well being is a better basis for building sustainable benefits for individuals and organization. This study provides a novel concept by the integration of well being and commitment based engagement into a single construct.

3.1.42 Rosalie Catalana (2016), An acronym for Meaning, Autonomy, Growth, Impact and Connections, MAGIC, Represents the elements identified as contributing to engagement is suggested in this paper.

3.1.43 J Arrowsmith & J Parker (2013), The Paper suggests that effective engagement initiatives require political astuteness and commitment on the part of HR. A purposive approach of employee engagement involves HR interrogating the employment relationship to address the fundamental issues of employee wise work design and management agencies.

3.1.44 Vijaya Mani (2011), Four factors namely employee welfare, empowerment, employee growth and inter personal relationship were found as predictors of employee engagement at executive level of reputed banking, insurance and software companies in Tamilnadu.

3.1.45 Danan Carter, Timothy Baghurst (2014), The Theme in the paper reveals that servant leadership positively influences employee engagement while contributing to employee loyalty to the workplace. Based on the servant leadership experiences participants are more committed, build healthy work relationship and actively participate in achieving organizational goals.

3.1.46 Yadava BapuraoJeve, Christina Oppenheimier, Justin Konje (2015), The study uses UTRECHT work engagement scale (UWES) and identifies work engagement level below average. Vigor and dedication are significantly lower, these are characterised by energy, mental resilience and the will to invest in one's efforts. The NHS employees are immersed in their daily work.

3.1.47 Jain D Parent, Kathi J Lovelace (2015), The model suggests that a positive work culture enhances employee engagement and in specific cases leads to increased employee adaptability. The paper incorporates three critical elements of employee engagement, positive psychology and adaptation to organizational change.

3.1.48 John David Vizzuro (2015), The study led to the discovery of 4 themes of leader-employee engagement to include psychological commitment, expectation, realization, trust actualization and reduction in the leadership power distance. By applying employee engagement strategies aligned with these themes, leaders may influence patient care which contributes to social change by increasing health care quality for a positive influence on medical care and societal health.

3.1.49 Moran & Brooke Paul Tame (2013), During the process of engaging employees and advancing sustainability- as well as after initial goals are achieved - it is important to remember that people like to feel appreciated. Engaged and happy employees are central to an organization integrated approach to sustainability and ultimate viability.

3.1.50 Simon L Albrecht, Arnold Bakker Jammie A Gruman, William HM Alan M Saks 2015, The study is to argue in Support of a model that shows how four key HRM practices focused on engagement influence organizational climate, job demands and job resources, the psychological experiences of safety, meaningful and availability at work which leads to individuals, groups and organizational performance.

3.1.51 Stephanie N Downey, Lisa Van Det Werff Kecia M Thomas, Victoria C Plaut (2014),

This paper investigates the association of diversity practices with an important aspect of work place, well-being, and engagement. It is hypothesized that this association would be mediated by trust climate and that is mediation relationship would be stronger when employees experienced feelings of inclusion in the workplace. The results of the study indicate that diversity, practices are associated with a trusting climate that in turn is positively related to employee engagement.

3.1.52 CrowfordEcan R Le Pine, Jeffery A, Rich Bruce Louis (2010),

This Study uses Meta analytic structural Modeling. It has been seen that demands and burnout are positively associated whereas resources and burnout are negatively associated. Relation between engagement and resources were consistently positive, relation among demands and engagement were highly dependent on the nature of demand and demand that employees tend to appraise as challenges were positively associated with engagement.

3.1.53 Xiaomeng Zhang and Kathryn M Bartol (2010),

Anticipated, empowering leadership, positively affected psychological empowerment which in turn influenced both intrinsic motivation and creative process engagement.

3.1.54 Abhijit Siddhanta and DeDebalina Roy (2010),

The Journal publication throws light on how employee engagement can be enhanced. This study tries to identify the key drivers of employee engagement, its different attributes together with the ways to measure it and how to handle disengaged employee in the organization. Employee engagement is powerfully linked to a range of business success factors such as employee performance, productivity, safety, attendance & retention, customer service & satisfaction, customer loyalty & retention and profitability.

3.1.55 Josh Bersin (2015),

The issue of retention and engagement is raised to second position in the minds of business leaders, second only to the challenge of building global leadership. The article suggests that the concept of employee engagement needs a relook. It is important for an organization to make it simply irresistible place to work. Five elements that drive engagement include meaningful work, hands-on Management, positive work environment, Growth & opportunity and trust in leadership. It is also noted that highly engaged companies work very hard to make work simple.

3.1.56 Ms J Josephine Verginia Sharmita (2013), This study identifies the elements of employee engagement, examine factors that influence employee engagement, discuss the outcomes of employee engagement & cost of disengaged workforce. The factors that influence employee engagement according to this study are recruitment, job designing, career development opportunities, leadership empowerment, equal opportunity, training & development, performance management, compensation. Disengagement effects work, customers, productivity and overall company performance.

3.1.57 Andrew J Wefald and Ronald G Downey (2008), This study broadly defines engagement as involvement satisfaction and enthusiasm which is used by the Organization for the purpose of retention. Engagement fails to meet many positive criteria. With attentions to this criteria engagement may be useful to the organization.

3.1.58 Thang, Ziaomeng, Bartol, Katheryn M (2010), This study found an inverted U-shaped relationship between creative process engagement and overall job performance among professionals in highly complex jobs in the area of information technology. It found out that low experienced employees generally exhibit higher levels of overall job performance; creative performance partially mediated the relationship between creative process engagement & job performance.

3.1.59 Michelle R Sumpson (2009), The study has made a systematic review of the business organizational psychology and health sciences and health engagement administration literature about engagement at work. Many of the articles referred report on examination of antecedents and / or consequences of engagement at work among varying employee types and work settings. The findings suggest organizational factors versus individual contributors significantly impact engagement at work.

3.1.60 Simon L Albracht Arnold B Bakku Jamie A Gruman William H Macey Alan M Saks (2015), This study is to argue in support of a model that shows how four key HRM practices focused on engagement influence organizational climate, job demands and job resources, the psychological experiences of safety, meaningfulness & availability at work. The authors conclude that HRM practitioners need to go beyond the routine administration of annual engagement surveys and need to embed engagement in HRM policies and practices such as

selection, socialization, performance management, learning to facilitate & improve engagement and result in positive outcomes that will help organization achieve a competitive advantage.

3.1.61 Sean Graber (2015), This work suggests that individuals can be categorized into 9 Archetypes based on how people perceive their job and how they behave at work. Then the answers can be mapped as;

Perception	Positive	Brat	Under Achiever	All Star
	Indifferent	Delinquent	Drifter	Work horse
	Negative	Saboteur	Cynic	Martyr
		Destructive	Neutral	Constructive
		Behavior		

This approach enables organizations without people analytics capabilities to start seeing relationship between employee perception and actions. Then over time organizations can track how it relates to key performance indicators (KPI's) such as sales, customers satisfaction and attrition.

3.1.62 Swathi S (2013): The research paper deals with the factors that influence employee engagement. The Critical factors that have led to employee engagement are recruitment, Job designing, Family friendliness, Job satisfaction, Health & safety, employee perception of job importance, Employee clarity of job expectation, Career advancement & improvement opportunities.

3.1.63 Ali Abbas Albdour and IklasI Altarawneh (2014): The paper investigates the relationship between two measures of employee engagement (Job engagement and organisational engagement). The organisational commitment is measured by three key measurements which are affective (emotional) Commitment, continuance (maintenance) commitment and normative commitment. It is found that frontline employees who have high job engagement have high level of affective and normative commitment.

3.1.64 Anita j GRG (2014), the purpose of the present research work was to identify the key determinants of employee engagement and their predictability. Causal study was done to study

the relationship. The major factors that had an impact were environment of working, team and co-workers, relationship. It was found that employee engagement had significant impact on employee performance.

3.1.65 UNC Kenan, this white paper identified the drivers of employee engagement. “They are believing in one’s organisation, understand business context, respect and helpful to colleagues, willing to go to the extra mile. It also found out that low employee engagement not only affects performance, it increases employee turnout, lowers customer service satisfaction and increases absenteeism”.

3.1.66 M.G. Rao, “Management of Human Assets” This study highlighted the complications associated with Human Resource Management in the organizations of the present days. The study featured small scale industries in Industrial estates and also dealt with the concepts of HRD. A close examination of the concepts of training and development, organizational development, performance management has been undertaken by the researcher.

3.1.67 Pramod Verma, “Emerging Issues in Human Resources Management by a volume, attempted to present state-of-the-art explanations and experiences on the emerging issues in managing human resources in various organizations”.

3.1.68 Jayanthi Lal Jain, “An Empirical Model on Micro-Level Manpower Planning in Banks”, this study provided a model for manpower planning in the banks. They also presented a framework of various norms in the Indian Banking sector. The model and norms formulated by this research paper have been very useful and in planning and allocating banking staff to different branches of the banks.

3.1.69 O.P. Misra and S.K. Srivastava; “Leadership styles among Bank Managers” They conducted a research survey among 45 sample respondents from both nationalized and private banks. They contributed towards the various leadership styles and its effect on HRD. Bank managers have different leadership styles. Leadership styles will vary according to the position they hold in the hierarchy.

3.1.70 Uma Sekaran, “The perceived quality of working life in banks in major cities in India”, is a study carried out by this author. He tried to examine the concept of quality of work life (QWL) in the banking sector. The findings suggest that QWL differs from position to position at different levels in the organization. QWL is a perception of employees and can include many factors. Recognition, benefits, involvement are some of the facets considered in QWL.

3.1.71 K. Rajendra Prasad, Innovative practices followed by State Bank of India for educating and developing their employees” a business case and an detailed study, “dwelled upon few of creative and innovative efforts in SBI, Viz., Performance Appraisal, Quality Circles, Job Rotation, Training and Assessment, HRD Quiz, Self – Learning Centre actions, Messenger to Manager Programmes, Organization Development Intervention exercises, etc., all are aimed at training and developing the bank’s workforce.

3.1.72 Kundu and Malhan (2007) analyzed the HRM practices among insurance companies in India based on the information collected from 218 respondents. The respondents were drawn from four insurance firms (two multinational firms and two Indian firms) to examine the HRM practices followed in the sample firms. Data analysis was done using factor analysis and ANOVA. Training & benefits, performance appraisal policies, selection process, HR planning & recruitment approaches were found to be the significant HRM practices followed by insurance firms in India. Additionally, workforce diversity and competitive compensation policies were also found to be among the important HRM practices followed by the insurance firms.

3.1.73 Jyothsna& Kumar (2015) provided empirical evidence regarding the factors of performance appraisal that influence organizational attachment and job commitment among private sector bank employees in India. In this research, job satisfaction was considered as dependent variable while elements of rater, elements of rate, environmental aspects, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior were included as independent variables. Results of regression analysis highlighted that performance appraisal factors, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior have a significant impact and positive impact on job satisfaction of employees in private banks in India.

3.1.74 Lakkoju (2014), Research study was conducted in Andhra Pradesh of India. The study focused to explore the HRM Practices of two banks namely State Bank of India (SBI) and Karur

Vysya Bank (KVB). Analysis was undertaken to assess the perceptions regarding HRM practices by managerial and non-managerial personnel in the banks. Managerial respondents from SBI were 132 in number and that of KVB were 84. Similarly, the number of clerical respondents from SBI was 108 and KVB was 76 resulting in a final sample of 400 respondents. Analysis of data was done using ANOVA. The results of the research concluded that significant differences in perception of the two different classes of workers prevailed in SBI. However, in KVB, it was found that strong and good HRM practices prevailed as per the perception of managerial and non-managerial employees.

3.1.75 Roy (2015), investigated the various variables impacting employee retention among bank employees in Assam state, India. 252 respondents were included in the research through a structured questionnaire. Respondents were selected from four private banks (ICICI, HDFC, Axis Bank and YES Bank) and four public sector banks (SBI, UCO, UBI and PNB Bank) in Assam. The results of the research concluded that nearly 80 % of employees from public sector and 60 % of employees from private sector were satisfied with the HRM practices of various banks in Assam. The study indicated that there is a strong association with respect to the HRM practices and the employee retention strategies the banks adopt.

3.1.76 Mittal, Gupta and Mottiani (2016), examined the link between HRM practices and customer satisfaction levels among Indian banks which are private. Data was drawn from 203 employees of the bank. The results of the research concluded that various HRM practices have a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction.

3.1.77 Dale Carnegie, May 2018 conducted an online survey and 450 responses were elicited. Only 26% of the organisations consider employee engagement as top priority. Those organisations which considered employee engagement saw lesser rate of absenteeism and leaders were capable to handle their work more effectively.

3.1.78 Shailshri VT and Dr. Sureka Shenoy (2016) The study is meant to describe the employee retention in Uralungal Labour Contract Cooperative Society (ULCCS LTD). Retention of key employees is critical to the long-term health & success of any organization. It is a known fact that retaining the best employees ensures customer satisfaction, satisfied colleagues & deeply imbedded organization knowledge & learning. The Objective of this study is to find the

factors that influence employee retention and to establish a relationship between employee engagement and retention strategy and to identify factors to reduce the employees turn over in the organization. The study uses primary Data and statistical analysis for interpretation. By identifying the factors causing employee turnover, the organization can develop & maintain the strategies that help them to retain their employees. By providing job satisfaction to the employees, employee loyalty or employee engagement increases, which in turn helps the organization to retain their employees.

3.2 CONSULTANTS

There are plenty of professional consultants who have worked and working on employee engagement. The findings of their research work have a tremendous influence on how organisation looks at the human capital. Below mentioned are the contributions of some of them.

3.2.1 The Gallup Institute, Gallup Institute has been a significant producer of research on work connectedness constructs (commitment and job satisfaction) from the 1980's, in 1999 the construct was re-termed as engagement (Buckingham and Coffman 1999). Gallup has been instrumental in the supply of timely and relevant research on critical issues on human nature and behaviour for over seventy years (Gallup 2008). Gallup incorporates research areas that encompass: management, psychology, sociology and economics. Gallup's major contributions come from the Gallup Poll (relevant and timely research, Gallup College (provider of management degrees and courses), Gallup Consulting (providing consulting services to organisations on human nature and behaviour issues) and Gallup Press (publication of key research and findings) (Gallup 2008). Gallup has made a significant contribution to many human and behavioural areas, engagement has seen significant support.

To measure engagement the Gallup Institute developed the 'Gallup Workplace Audit' (GWA) (Buckingham and Coffman 1999). The scale has 12 engagement items, reflecting a tested unidimensional construct according to the study by Harter et al. (2002).

3.2.2 Towers Perrin, This, is a professional HR Consultant team who provide business assistance in improving the efficiency of employees, decrease financial risks and achieving the business goals. (Towers Perrin 2008). They are pioneers in the field of employee engagement

and developed a questionnaire which had nine items to measure engagement levels. They grouped employees into engaged and disengaged and defined engagement as the discretionary effort the employees put at work. It also means to say that employees go beyond the call of their work and work with no expectation of any reward or recognition.

3.2.3 The International Survey Research (ISR) This research group mainly focussed on surveys which included employees, customers and managers to identify the worth of people in an organisation. They conducted a number of surveys to identify if human resources are one of the key assets of the organisation. Most of the surveys conducted by this team of executives ended up with developing the human assets in the organisation. They provided methods of motivating the human capital in the organisation and also linked employee engagement to it. This was further taken over by Towers Perrin

3.2.4 The Corporate Leadership Council (CLC), this corporate council had a group of diverse executives who continuously worked on the issues of employee engagement. They provided the information gathered to HR executives who implemented the employee engagement strategies in the companies they worked for. In 2008 this group provided the assistance required to align HR strategy with organisational strategy. During the years of 2004-5 the team of experts defined employee engagement and developed a model of the same. The definition highlights that engagement is a commitment to someone or something where the employees' work. The model developed by them shows both emotional and rational aspects of commitment and describes engagement as the extra effort put by the employees and a sense of belongingness to the organisation.

3.2.5 Drefs Consulting, founded in the year 2005 believes in people engagement. They have unique programs and have very prestigious client base. The team sizes can vary and they have learning programmes which have a measurable outcome and impact. According to this study the factors of employee engagement are organisational values and culture, orientation of employees, methods of communication in the organisation, styles of leadership, health aspects and benefits and a balance between work and personal life.

3.2.6 Towers Watson, The study reported that leadership in the organisation plays a vital role in engaging the employees, but at the same time it is necessary for the individual employees to

align themselves with the values and ethos of the organisation. The study was conducted in December 2015.

3.2.7 The Times Job, August 2017 survey reported that disengagement causes 50% absenteeism, more accidents and a greater number of faults in everyday tasks. The survey highlights the importance of organisational culture as a major factor to enhance employee engagement.

3.2.8 Mercers, July 2018 employee engagement report states that 80% of Indian employees are engaged and 9 out of ten employees feel proud to be associated with their organisation, but one out of four employees may leave the organisation for better career.

3.3 RESEARCH GAP FOR THE STUDY

The review of literature has several insights to the concept of employee engagement. The inference drawn from all studies is that employee engagement is a very important aspect, particularly in the service sector. It has been observed in many researcher's that there exists an association between employee engagement and organisational outcomes in terms of profitability, customer satisfaction and overall growth and sustainability of an organisation. This research is an attempt to combine the three sectors namely education, banking and insurance to study employee engagement. A study of this nature was not identified in the review of literature. This study would further provide sufficient information on determine if nature of work influences strongly on employee engagement. It is an attempt to identify if same factors influence employee engagement in the different sectors in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada. Mangalore is a hub of the above mentioned services, and the people of this region have their own characteristics. The study thus is an attempt to determine the engagement levels (%) particular to the three sectors and group factors as similar and dissimilar in the sectors studied. The research further has attempted to determine the strength of association of the different factors of engagement and proceed towards a regression model. Since a study of this nature has not been conducted in Mangalore city of DK with respect to the three sectors, this would definitely add value to the knowledge of employee engagement theoretically and would be useful in driving engagement in the organisations.

3.4 CONCLUSION

The above chapter reviews the literature available on the concepts and issues relating to employee engagement. The review of literature is based on individual contributions by authors, organizational contribution to the topic and the consultant's viewpoint on the topic of employee engagement. The review highlights the work of both Indian and foreign authors on the specified topic. The review of literature helped the researcher to have a basis for the present study, identify the research gap and has laid a strong foundation for the present study.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESEARCH DESIGN

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CHAPTER FOUR

RESEARCH DESIGN

4.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design is a blue print of the entire research work carried out by the researcher. It gives an overview of the work that is carried in this particular study. Appropriate methods and application of a scientific framework is required for systematic study. The previous chapters have tried to understand the concept of employee engagement and an in-depth analysis of the various reviews in this area are dealt with. The main focus of this chapter is to provide a theoretical frame work for this study, explain the existing research gap, define the research objectives in specific, identify the hypothesis to be tested, elaborate on the sampling design, methods and tools used for data collection, statistical methods used for data analysis and interpretation and also the limitations and problems faced by the researcher during the course of study.

The research design is **exploratory cum descriptive in nature**. Usually exploratory studies do not start with a problem or hypothesis. It starts with identifying the problem. Therefore, this study has first reviewed a lot of literature in the area of employee engagement and identified areas which have not been touched upon. For this reason, it can be considered as an exploratory research (Rudison,2015). The review of literature includes concepts of employee engagement, differentiation with closely associated terminologies like employee satisfaction, Work engagement, and drivers of employee engagement and many more. While the research problem under consideration in this study has not been considered in the earlier studies, thus study can be said to be an exploration. The major emphasis of this study then, is on identification of engagement levels in the various service sectors to develop a predictive model for employee engagement which is descriptive in nature.

4.2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

The theoretical framework of the study attempts to identify various factors which influence employee engagement. Excessive review of literature and identifying the research gap has led to the development of a conceptual model for the study undertaken. The factors or constructs that influence engagement can be categorized under three heads namely individual, group (team) and

organizational (Simon L Albrecht, Arnold Bakker Jammie A Gruman, William HM Alan M Saks 2015). Sub factors within each of the constructs have been developed namely;

- ❖ Organizational leadership and planning.
- ❖ Organizational culture and communication.
- ❖ Organizational pay and benefits.
- ❖ Organizational training and development.
- ❖ Individuals work environment.
- ❖ Individual's role in the organization.
- ❖ Relationship with Immediate supervisors.

Fig 4.1 Model for drivers of employee engagement.

Employee Engagement is defined as the level of commitment, involvement and passion as a 'Positive, fulfilling work related state of mind of an individual, interrelationships in the organization, and overall practices of the organization that is characterized by vigor, dedication and absorption' (Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzalez-Roma and Bakker (2002)). The scale of these researchers and Best Companies Group (BCG) Employee engagement and satisfaction survey has been adapted in the Indian context in the current study.

4.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada in India, is a hub of service sector. Therefore, the proposed research study has the following objectives.

- To identify the employee engagement levels in the service sector namely Banking, Insurance and Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.
- To build a decision rule to enable the classification of employees into one of the two groups, that is engaged or disengaged in each of these sectors.
- To explore the drivers [Factors]of employee engagement in the service sector, namely Banking, Insurance and Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.
- To compare the three service sectors in term of employee engagement.
- To develop a relationship model for employee engagement and its causal factors for each of the three sectors.

4.4 HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

Based on the research objectives the following research hypothesis are being formulated.

4.4.1 Research objective 1

To identify the employee engagement levels in the service sector namely Banking, Insurance and Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.

- ❖ H₁: There is a significant difference in the level of engagement in the various service sectors namely Banking, Insurance, Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.

4.4.2 Research objective 2

To develop a relationship model for employee engagement and its causal factors for each of these three sectors.

- ❖ H₂: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and gender in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₃: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and gender in the Insurance sector.

- ❖ H₄: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and gender in the Education sector.
- ❖ H₅: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and length of service in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₆: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and length of service in the Insurance sector.
- ❖ H₇: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and length of service in the Education sector.
- ❖ H₈: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and age in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₉: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and age in the Insurance sector.
- ❖ H₁₀: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and age in the Education sector.
- ❖ H₁₁: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and salary in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₁₂: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and salary in the Insurance sector.
- ❖ H₁₃: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and salary in the Education sector.

Researchers have considered many demographic factors as the moderating variables which influence employee engagement (Qiao et al., 2009). Demographic variables (i.e. age and gender) are included as control variables that can be expected to confound relationships between job characteristics and outcome variables (E.G. Karasek and Theorell, 1990; Kasl, 1989; Schaufeli and Van Dierendonck, 1994). Rosseel (1979) found work values and ethics differed to factors such as age, sex, job tenure and degree of family responsibility. Research has suggested that the level of employee engagement generally is affected by demographic characteristics, the work place, and job demand (Kahn, 1990; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). There is also significant relationship between demographic factors like gender, race and job satisfaction (Hunjra, 2010, Scott et al, 2005), Huberman (1992, 1993).

4.5 SAMPLE DESIGN

The purpose of the real research is to identify characteristics or parameters of the population. The population is the aggregate of all elements that share certain set of common characteristics for the purpose of the research study. The sample is the subgroup of the population under study.

4.5.1 Population

Population for this study would be employees working in the service sector [Private sectors only] namely banking, insurance, and educational sector in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.

While almost all service sectors have participated in the boom, growth is fastest in banking, insurance, and educational sector. Never the less these sectors have also seen a tremendous growth in Mangalore too. Therefore, these sectors are identified.

4.5.2 Sample frame

Research studies are based on the sample because of two major reasons, time and resource. This study is also based on the sample study. A representative sample has been drawn from the population. The Sampling frame has been developed with the help of primary sources. Branch heads, Sales managers and Departmental heads have been contacted to get authentic information about the number of employees working at the middle level management [Private sectors only] in the banking, insurance and Education sector. The sampling frame is the representation of the total population.

4.5.2.1 Sampling Frame: Education sector

Table 4.1 Sampling Frame: Education sector	
College Name	Number of Faculty
St. Agnes College	72
Canara College	57
Besant College	55
St. Aloysius College	198
Govindadas College	47
Srinivas First grade college	30
Total	459

Source: Primary

The above table represents the colleges offering basic under graduation courses in the city of Mangalore. They are the traditional and well known colleges offering basic courses in Science, Arts and Commerce. The heads of the departments were consulted personally for the number of faculty and also the information was verified with the mandatory disclosures made by each of these colleges.

4.5.2.2 Sampling Frame: Private Banking Sector

Bank Name	Number of Employees
Karnataka Bank	195
HDFC	62
ICICI	81
Yes Bank	15
Axis Bank	43
Kotak Mahindra	9
Federal Bank	8
Total	413

Source: Primary

The above table represents the number of middle level employees working in the private banking sector. These banks are the major players in the city of Mangalore and are the ones which have more number of branches and employees. The branch Managers were contacted and the number of employees working is arrived at. Further, employee records were verified for the authentication of these numbers.

4.5.2.3 Sampling Frame: Insurance Sector

Name Of the company	Number of Employees
Reliance Nippon life insurance	60
Bajaj Allianz life insurance company Ltd	55
Max Life Insurance	28
Kotak Life Insurance	38
Exide Life Insurance	56
ICICI Prudential Life insurance	45
HDFC Life	63
Royal Sundaram General Insurance	20
Bajaj Alliance General Insurance	35
ICICI Lombard	22

HDFC ERGO	18
Total	440

Source: Primary

The above table represents the number of employees in the Insurance sector. These are the private life insurance and private general insurance providers in the city of Mangalore. Sales heads were contacted and the number of advisors and insurance agents is arrived at after the discussion with the sales managers of each of these companies.

4.5.3 Sample Size

A very small sample size will yield scanty information and constrains like time, economic viability, ethics prevent us from taking a very large sample size too. A sample size of 30 is considered to be a large sample in statistics as it follows normal approximation, (Cohen, Jacob 1977). For this study, 1312 members constitute the sampling units for the study, with a spilt of 459 employees in the education sector, 413 in the Banking sector and 440 employees in the Insurance sector. Since equal importance is given to each of these sectors 25% employees of the sampling frame is chosen as the sampling size. Therefore, the total sample size and sample sizes for each of the sectors is shown in the table below.

Sector	Total of sampling frame	Sample size [25% of sampling frame]	Actual number of questionnaires administered
Education	459	115	145
Banking	413	104	145
Insurance	440	110	145
Total	1312	329	435

Considering the non-response rate and invalid responses, a total of 435 questionnaires were administered among the middle level employees of the private sectors of insurance, banking and education sector.

Sample Inclusion

Banking: Middle level employees. Scale 1 and 2 and office staff.

Insurance: General and health Insurance [Sales head and Agents].

Education: Faculty of Basic Under graduation courses.

4.5.4 Sampling Method

Sampling is a procedure to obtain a representative sample member from the Population, (Kish, L. (1995)). A quota sampling technique is used in this study. For this study 25% was the specified quota for each of the population subgroup. Thus, this study assumes variability across the subgroups rather than within the groups.

Since the response rate was 84%, 364 completed questionnaires were collected and analyzed for the research study. Sector wise distribution of the completed questionnaire is as follows;

Table 4.5 Completed respondents in each sector			
Sector	Insurance	Banking	Education
Completed responses	112	133	119

4.6 DATA COLLECTION METHOD

Data Collection involves both primary sources and secondary sources.

4.6.1 Secondary Data

Secondary source of data includes data collected from journal, newspaper, magazines, articles, reports and internet websites.

4.6.2 Primary Data

Employee engagement levels were measured through the administration of a structured questionnaire and interview method. The questions in the questionnaire have been divided into two parts. Part-1 would consist statements related to organizations corporate culture, individual's role in the organization, work environment, pay and benefits, training and developmental activities in the organization, career development, formal and informal relationships in the organization which has been rated on a rating scale of five (1-strongly disagree.....5-strongly

agree). Part-2 elicited information from respondents regarding their demographic details and socio-cultural background with specific and open-ended questions. Refer Annexure-2

Questionnaire scoring pattern and classification.

The questions were rated on a likert scale (1-strongly disagree.....5-strongly agree).

4.7 CONTENT VALIDITY

The questionnaire has been developed using previous studies and its content validity is tested with the help of subject experts. The opinions from the industry experts were solicited and this helped in developing the questionnaire.

Further a pilot study was conducted with 32 respondents covering all the sectors. The insight of the pilot study was considered, necessary changes were incorporated and again a pretest was done. Thus, the validity of the questionnaire was thoroughly checked before actually administering it to the respondents.

4.7.1 Reliability analysis

A pilot survey was conducted to determine the reliability of the questionnaire. The sample of 32 completed data set was used to check the reliability of the study.

Table 4.6 Reliability Analysis					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Banking	13	40.6	40.6	40.6
	Insurance	9	28.1	28.1	68.8
	Education	10	31.3	31.3	100.0
	Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the spilt of the data considered for the pilot study. 40 questionnaires were distributed among the sample respondents. The response rate was 80%. Therefore 32 completed genuine responses are considered and insights of these are considered in drafting the final questionnaire.

Table 4.7 Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.934	0.973	61

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the reliability value for the given scales in the questionnaire. Cronbach's Alpha has shown a value of 0.934 and standardized value is 0.973 which is usually considered as a good scale. If the alpha value for the scale is 0.7 or more, it is usually considered a good scale. The final questionnaire was drafted after consideration of the alpha value. A few questions were dropped. Questions which had less correlation towards the total and did not make much of a difference were deleted to enhance the worth of the questionnaire. Reliability test values are given in Annexure-1

4.8 STATISTICAL TOOLS FOR DATA ANALYSIS

The response obtained by the employees has been coded and entered into the software as per the requirements of the objectives. The data is analyzed using SPSS Version 21. Descriptive statistics like mean, median, mode, range, standard deviation, percentage, cumulative percentage have been used. Also, inferential statistics like Chi-Square, ANOVA, correlation coefficient, factor analysis, curve estimation and Discriminant analysis is used in the study.

4.8.1 Chi-Square Test

Chi-square test is used to test if two variables are statistically associated with each other significantly. Statistical Significance is inferred with the probability value {p} reported on the computer output. This value tells us if there is an association or not but the strength of association is understood with the following measures of indexes of agreement (David M Lane, R B Burns 1981).

1. Contingency co-efficient C: The contingency co-efficient lies between 0 and 1 and can be used for any cross tabulation with any number of rows and columns, provided both are equal.

2 Cramers V: This is a variation of the Phi Correlation coefficient, and maximum value is 1.

3 The Phi Correlation Coefficient: Is used for a 2x2 contingency table.

4 Goodman and Kruskals Lambda Coefficient: This Coefficient measures the error reduction in predicting the value of one variable if we know the category of the other variable.

Generally one or two indexes are sufficient to find out if the association is strong or weak.

4.8.2 Correlation and regression Analysis

Correlation and regression analysis are best when applied together to test whether metric variables are associated with each other and whether the dependent variable can be explained by some independent variables or predicted from them (Bruce Ratner 2009). The correlation coefficient of all the variables provide a good indicator of which independent variable are highly correlated with the dependent variable. The regression equation is judged for its usefulness based on the overall F-test for the model. This shows up as p-value of less than 0.05 on the ANOVA table in the regression output. Also, the R^2 Value of the model tells us the percentage of the variation in the dependent variable as explained by all the independent variables in the model.

4.8.3 Factor Analysis for Data reduction

Factor analysis is a very useful tool in statistics and is a method by which data complexity is reduced by reducing the number of variables being studied. In this research study the researcher has attempted to find out exactly what makes employees to be engaged in the work place. Factor analysis is a good way of resolving and identifying latent factors from the array of seemingly important variables. It is a set of techniques which, by analyzing the correlations between the variables reduces their number into lesser number of factors which explain the original data in a more economical way (M.C.Howard 2009).

There are two levels of factor analysis. Level-1 or stage-1 is the factor extraction process which identifies the number of factors that will be extracted from the given set of data. The method used is the Principal Component analysis and the rule of thumb is based on the computation of an Eigenvalue, to decide how many factors are to be extracted.

The higher the Eigen value of a given factor, the higher is the amount of variability. The given study is an attempt to extract the least number of factors as possible, which will however

maximize the explained variance. Since the objective is to reduce the number of variables to few factors those with Eigen value one and more are only retained.

The second level is called the Rotation of the Principal Components. This stage is highly recommended after the extraction to determine which factors are to be considered. The factor matrix is used for this purpose. The factor matrix gives the loading to each variable on each extracted factor. The objective is to identify variables with high loading and name them as new variables or retain as it is.

4.8.4 Discriminant Analysis for Classification and Prediction

Discriminant analysis is used in the similar manner of multiple regression. Discriminant analysis will be used to group respondents into two groups namely engaged and disengaged and also to derive a discriminant function in the form of;

$$Y = a + K_1X_1 + K_2X_2 + K_3X_3 + K_4X_4$$

Where Y is the dependent variable (employee engagement), $X_1, X_2, X_3,$ and X_4 are the independent variables which have to be determined from the study. a is a constant and K_1, K_2, K_3 and K_4 are co-efficient of the independent variable which will be determined from the study. The dependent variable Employee engagement is a categorical variable and the independent variables are continuous {metric} in nature. A model is built with a linear equation, and use the coefficients of the equation to calculate Y discriminant score. For any new data value the discriminant value is calculated and the classification can be made a decision rule formed for this process is to determine the cutoff score, which is generally the midpoint of the mean discriminant scores of the two groups (Ronald Fisher 1936).

The classification of the existing data is done using the derived equation and the accuracy of the model is determined. This output matrix is called the classification matrix or confusion matrix which indicates the percentage of the existing data values that are correctly classified in the model.

4.9 BENEFITS OF THE STUDY

- ❖ A methodology to measure employee engagement in the three sectors namely banking, insurance and education sector.
- ❖ To identify factors of engagement and classify them as similar and dissimilar factors.
- ❖ To classify employees as engaged and disengaged in each of these sectors.
- ❖ To predict the engagement levels in each of these sectors and also have a draft questionnaire of employee engagement in the three sectors.

4.10 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The respondents were very busy in their regular schedule of work. Therefore, filling in the questionnaire or responding to the questions was the least interesting thing for them. In spite of this serious limitation, the researcher spent a lot of time with the respondents to elicit the right information for them. Observation technique was used to a great extent.
- Some of the respondents tried to relate it to employee satisfaction and the researcher had to spend a lot of time in explaining the difference between the two.
- The study is limited to the private sector organizations only. The researcher excluded the government and public sector as the comparison would lead to misleading outcome.
- The sample respondents for this study belong to the middle level management. Middle level management is considered in all three sectors to bring about certain commonality.
- The study is limited to the city of Mangalore of Dakshina Kannada. But since at most care was taken to fill in the responses, the study can be definitely generalized.

4.11 STRUCTURE OF THE THESIS

This thesis is structured to provide a review of relevant information regarding the theories and models of employee engagement as proposed by prominent practitioners and academicians. Further the research design, theoretical framework, research objectives and hypotheses are provided and discussed. Data gathered is analyzed to provide evidence for support of these research objective and research hypotheses. Factor analysis, discriminant research model is being generated and the research findings are then used to suggest implications that are important

for the understanding of employee engagement in the service sector. The research consists of chapters, and its framework is presented as follows.

Chapter 1: Introduction

It begins with the introduction of the subject of employee engagement, followed by the conceptualization of employee engagement. Multidimensional aspect of employee engagement; various models proposed in employee engagement are elaborated in detail.

Chapter 2: Service Sector Analysis

This chapter provides an understanding of the service sector in India. The contribution of the service sector towards economic growth of the country is elaborated. Further the Insurance sector, banking sector and Education sector are analyzed from the point of growth and contribution towards economic development to the country. Also, the HR implications in each of these sectors is reviewed.

Chapter 3: Review of Literature

The previous research work on the topic of employee engagement has been quoted in this chapter which is relevant for the study. The review of literature consists of journal articles of individual authors and the studies conducted by various organizations. Research gap is identified after an in-depth study is done on the available literature.

Chapter 4: Research Design

This Chapter deals with the research design analysis, theoretical frame work, sample design which includes sample size and sampling method, questionnaire design of the present study validity and reliability of the questionnaire. It also discusses the data collection methods and techniques used in interpretation of the data. Finally, the problems faced during survey have been discussed; chapters of the thesis and the benefits of this study at large are included in this chapter.

Chapter 5: Analysis and Interpretations

It deals with the application of Statistical techniques to the primary data collected. It is divided into three parts of analysis based on the sectors namely Insurance, Banking and Educational sector. It discusses the various statistical techniques with their results and interpretations.

Chapter 6: Findings and Recommendations

This Chapter discusses the major findings in all the three sectors. It provides with the discriminant scores, factors that are extracted and also the regression model for prediction in all the three sectors.

Chapter 7: Research Implication, Limitation of the study and scope of further research

This chapter discusses the research implications of the study, limitations of the study, scope of further research and conclusion.

Bibliography

It includes the references of secondary data which helps in identifying, formulating and solving a research problem.

Annexure

It includes questionnaire framed for the study, variables name, reliability statistics, the discriminant scores of the given data, newly drafted questionnaire for each of the sector and regression values for the given set of data.

CHAPTER FIVE

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

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CHAPTER FIVE

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

5.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE CHAPTER

This chapter deals with the data analysis and interpretation of the primary data which was collected from the private insurance, banking and education sectors. The analysis and interpretation are based on the objectives and hypothesis formulated in the study. This chapter is divided into four different sections namely A, B, C and D.

Section A Deals with the analysis of data collected from the Private Insurance sector. Demographic details of respondents are discussed. The hypothesis with respect to the causal factors is tested using the Chi-Square test. The various factors affecting employee engagement in the insurance sector is extracted using the Factor Analysis and a questionnaire is drafted to measure and identify engagement levels in this sector. Further the discriminant analysis is used to classify the collected data into two classes namely engaged and disengaged and a decision rule is drafted to predict employee engagement in this sector. Curve estimation is used to fit a linear regression model for each the causal variables independently with respect to employee engagement.

Section B Deals with the analysis of data collected from the Private Banking sector. Demographic details of respondents are discussed. The hypothesis with respect to the causal factors is tested using the Chi-Square test. The various factors affecting employee engagement in the banking sector is extracted using the Factor Analysis and a questionnaire is drafted to measure and identify engagement levels in this sector. Further the discriminant analysis is used to classify the collected data into two classes namely engaged and disengaged and a decision rule is drafted to predict employee engagement in this sector. Curve estimation is used to fit a linear regression model for each the causal variables independently with respect to employee engagement.

Section C Deals with the analysis of data collected from the Private Education sector. Demographic details of respondents are discussed. The hypothesis with respect to the causal factors is tested using the Chi-Square test. The various factors affecting employee engagement in the education sector is extracted using the Factor Analysis and a questionnaire is drafted to measure and identify engagement levels in this sector. Further the discriminant analysis is used

to classify the collected data into two classes namely engaged and disengaged and a decision rule is drafted to predict employee engagement in this sector. Curve estimation is used to fit a linear regression model for each the causal variables independently with respect to employee engagement.

Section A: Analysis for the Insurance Sector

Insurance sector in the city of Mangalore provides plenty of job opportunities. It is one of the booming sectors which generate revenue to the country. The government is further promoting the policy of insuring the uninsured and this has pushed the insurance penetration rate in the country. The future in this sector is promising with several changes that are occurring in the regulatory framework and the way industry conducts its business and engages with its customer.

The total number of respondents in the insurance sector is 112. These are the respondents who have given complete response to all the questions in the questionnaire. Therefore, care has been taken to eliminate missing values and get the most accurate responses.

5.2 CAUSAL FACTORS AFFECTING EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN THE INSURANCE SECTOR

5.2.1 Based on Gender

Table 5 .1 Profile on the basis of Gender in the insurance sector					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	91	81.3	81.3	81.3
	Female	21	18.8	18.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

The number of female responses is 18.8% which is comparatively less. This is a general indication that the number of female workers in the insurance sector is less in Mangalore. The insurance sector seems to be dominated by male work force.

Source: Primary

The above Fig 5.1 clearly shows that the insurance industry is still facing a gender divide. The insurance sector should still go a long way and bring in new initiatives which will increase the representation of women in the insurance sector. Overall this sector is male dominated and is still in the culture of face-time driven environment. Employers need to bring in the concept flexible work possibilities with the advent of the information technology and increase the participation of women in this sector.

Table 5.2 Table of Cross tabulation Gender * Engaged employees

		Engaged		Total
		Engaged	Disengaged	
Gender	Male	14	77	91
	Female	21	0	21
Total		35	77	112

Source: Primary Data

The attribute Gender affects the engagement levels in the insurance sector. Predominately it is seen that all the female workers in this sector are engaged. The numbers of women respondents are less. Female employees are happy with the facilities provided and are also happy with the compensation to some extent. The above table 5.2 shows that all the 21 female employees are engaged in the insurance sector. The number of women agents is growing, as many of them have accounted it as another source of income.

For most of the women the career opportunity the insurance sector has opened for them, is more important than the income they earn. It gives them a sense of pride by being independent and at the same time being able to balance both personal and professional life.

5.2.2 Based on Age

Age		
N	Valid	112
	Missing	0
Mean		28.4375
Median		26.0000
Mode		24.00
Std. Deviation		6.09945
Minimum		24.00
Maximum		47.00

Source: Primary Data

The above table 5.3 shows the mean age of workforce in the insurance sector is 28.4375 years. The modal age is 24 years. The minimum age is 24 years and maximum age is 47 years. The sector is dominated with youth of a younger age. This shows workforce in the insurance sector is fresh out from their higher education. This trend of the workforce is good for the Indian insurance sector since a business-like insurance is affected by a number of Mega trends. The primary trend is going digital, which has affected the traditional insurance model which was more product-centric to customer centric. Customer engagement will be the aim of any insurance service provider. Thus, younger generation can embrace technology and move this sector ahead.

		Engaged		Total
		Engaged	Disengaged	
Age	24.00	14	14	28
	25.00	0	21	21
	26.00	7	7	14
	28.00	7	0	7

	29.00	0	21	21
	31.00	0	7	7
	39.00	7	0	7
	47.00	0	7	7
Total		35	77	112

Source: Primary Data

The above table 5.4 is a cross tabulation of age with engagement score. It gives a clear understanding of respondent's engagement levels with the age factor considered. Age is considered as age completed in the previous year. A chi-square test is performed to understand the significant association between the two variables namely engagement and age factor.

Table 5.5 Chi-Square Tests Age * Engaged employees in insurance sector			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	47.289^a	7	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	63.232	7	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.020	1	0.889
N of Valid Cases	112		

Source: Primary Data

Table 5.5 reveals a significant association between the two variables that is Engagement level and age. From the test output it is seen that the significant level for Pearson chi-square is 0.000. This means that Chi-square test is showing a significant association of 100% between the two variables age and engagement.

Table 5.6 Chi square Symmetric Measures Age * Engaged employees			
		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	0.545	0.000
N of Valid Cases		112	

Source: Primary Data

The contingency coefficient of 0.545 from the above table 5.6 infers that the association between the dependent and independent variable is significant as it is closer to 1 than to 0. This coefficient gives the measure of strength of the output. If the value is close to 0, then there does

not exist any strong correlation between the two variables. However, if the value lies in between 0.5 to 1, there exists a strong relationship.

Table 5.7 Chi-Square Directional Measures Age * Engaged employees in insurance sector						
			Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Appro x. T^b	Approx . Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	0.167	0.080	1.958	0.050
		Age Dependent	0.083	0.067	1.191	0.234
		Engaged Dependent	0.333	0.145	1.901	0.057
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Age Dependent	0.053	0.012		0.000
		Engaged Dependent	0.422	0.024		0.000

Source: Primary Data

Lambda is the measure of reduction in error in measuring the association between the two variables. From the table 5.7 the value of Lambda is 0.167 which means 16.7% error reduction. This is a moderate low value leading to 16.7% reduction in error in estimating or predicting one variable from the other. Therefore, age may not be considered for prediction in the insurance sector.

5.2.3 Based on length of service

Table 5.8 Length of service of employees in the insurance sector		
How long have you worked for this organization?		
N	Valid	112
	Missing	0
Mean		1.8750
Std. Deviation		1.45890
Sum		210.00

Source: Primary Data

The average length of service of employees in the insurance sector is 1.875 year. This is an indication that the employees do not stay for a long time in this sector. The insurance sector needs to take measures to see that employees are retained in the organization. The standard deviation also indicates that there is not much deviation. Overall the insurance sector does not

have workforce who have long years of service. It is also observed that 50% of the respondents have one year of experience in the insurance sector and 87% of workforce quit the insurance sector within three years of their service.

Table 5.9 Chi-Square Tests Length of service* Engaged employees in the Insurance sector			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	40.889^a	6	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	54.532	6	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.488	1	0.019
N of Valid Cases	112		

Source: Primary Data

The chi-square test shows that there is a significant association between length of service and the engagement levels. The result shows that there is 100% association between the dependent and independent variable.

Table 5.10 Chi-Square Tests Symmetric Measures Length of service* Engaged employees in the Insurance Sector			
		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	0.517	0.000
N of Valid Cases		112	

Source: Primary Data

The contingency coefficient value of 51.7% supports that there is a strong association between the two variables. The value can lie between 0 and 1. As the value is closer to 1 rather than 0 it can be concluded that the association is strong between the two variables. This industry needs to create and find ways to promote its careers in social, national, radio, online and television media.

Table 5.11 Chi-Square Tests Directional Measures Length of service* Engaged employees in the Insurance Sector						
			Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Approx. T	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	0.133	0.029	4.000	0.000
		How long have you worked for this	0.000	0.000		

		organization? Dependent				
		Engaged Dependent	0.333	0.073	4.000	0.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	How long have you worked for this organization? Dependent	0.040	0.010		0.000
		Engaged Dependent	0.365	0.015		0.000

Source: Primary Data

Lambda is the measure of reduction in error in measuring the association between the two variables. From the table the value of Lambda is 0.133 which means 13.3% error reduction. This is a moderate low value leading to 13.3% reduction in error in estimating or predicting one variable from the other. This industry does not have a very interesting career path nor is the salary very competitive to attract the best talent. The HR department faces the main problem of cash crunch and therefore unable to put a strong recruitment strategy.

5.2.4 Based on Salary

Table 5.12 Chi-Square Tests Salary * Engaged employees in the Insurance sector			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	82.133	9	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	109.374	9	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	24.108	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	112		

Source: Primary Data

Salary and engagement are two factors which are associated. The Chi –Square test is applied and it is identified that there is a significant association between the two factors. Salary is a prime determinant to any individual’s commitment to his/her job. The compensation package should be well defined and it should motivate individuals to achieve the best returns in terms of monetary benefits.

Table 5.13 Chi-Square Tests Directional Measures Salary * Engaged employees in the insurance sector				
			Value	Asymp. Std. Error
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	0.278	0.072
		Salary Dependent	0.083	0.067

	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Engaged Dependent	0.733	0.007
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Source: Primary Data

Lambda is the measure of reduction in error in measuring the association between the two variables. From the table the value of Lambda is 0.278 which means 27.8% error reduction. This is a moderate low value leading to 27.8% reduction in error in estimating or predicting one variable from the other.

Table 5.14 Chi-Square Tests Symmetric Measures salary * Engaged employees in the insurance sector			
		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	0.650	0.000
N of Valid Cases		112	

Source: Primary Data

The contingency coefficient value of 65.0% supports that there is a strong association between the two variables. The value can lie between 0 and 1. As the value is closer to 1 rather than 0 it can be concluded that the association is strong between the two variables.

Table 5.15 Salary levels of the Respondents in the insurance sector		
Salary		
N	Valid	112
	Missing	0
Mean		30500.00
Median		29000.00
Mode		25000.00
Std. Deviation		7234.80078
Range		25000.00
Minimum		20000.00
Maximum		45000.00
Sum		3416000.00

Source: Primary Data

The mean salary in the insurance sector is found to be Rs 30500. Median salary is Rs 29000 and the mode of the salary is Rs 25000. Many jobs are created in this sector. But there is a wrong

perception that the agents or marketing executives need to beg and sell their insurance products to their customers. The employees of the organization are paid a salary whereas the agents would receive salary plus the commission or only commission. Agents include both captive agents who work for only one company and brokers who are associated with a number of companies. Bonus and commission are paid, but the salary is highly linked with the performance of the individuals.

5.3 ENGAGED WORKFORCE IN THE INSURANCE SECTOR

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Engaged	35	31.3	31.3	31.3
	Disengaged	77	68.8	68.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

The insurance sector has 68.8% of workforce who are disengaged. This is an indication of workforce not being highly motivated to work in the sector. Only 31.3 % of human resources in the sector are engaged. Therefore, the companies need to identify measures to engage employees.

Source: Primary Data

The above fig 5.2 clearly shows that the employee engagement levels are as low as 31%. The insurance sector is a growing one and has plenty of job opportunities. But the millennial doesn't consider this as their career destination or path. The insurance industry needs to have a makeover by introducing this sector to the universities, have a tie up with academics and make the job more

exiting. Also, there should be additional motivational factors such as incentives, perks etc., so as to make youngsters join this industry.

5.4 EMPLOYEES PLANNING TO STAY IN THE SAME COMPANY FOR MORE THAN TWO YEARS IN INSURANCE SECTOR

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree strongly	7	6.3	6.3	6.3
	Disagree somewhat	28	25.0	25.0	31.3
	Neutral	70	62.5	62.5	93.8
	Agree Somewhat	7	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

Majority of respondents are neutral about the question of continuing their career in the same company. This is also an indication of employee disengagement. Therefore, the industry must consider measures to make the place of work more interesting and attract the best talent to the industry.

Source: Primary

The insurance industry is known for its mobility. Fig 5.3 clearly gives a picture that the employees are neutral about the careers in the company they are working for. It is common for

people to have multiple career paths and try to find out which fits them best and move accordingly, in the career path. Around 31% of the employees firmly believe that they will be quitting the organization. This shows that they have alternative career plans and working out something for their benefit.

5.4.1 Employees recommend company's product

Table 5.18 Employees Recommend company's product in Insurance Sector					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree strongly	35	31.3	31.3	31.3
	Disagree somewhat	21	18.8	18.8	50.0
	Agree Somewhat	56	50.0	50.0	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

The employees seem not to be very comfortable with the insurance product. Almost 50% of employees do not recommend their company products. It could be seen that the employees themselves are not aware of some products. When customers questioned them in depth the employees could not give justifying answers. The nature of insurance products depends on the nature of risk to be covered. This is varied from one individual to another. The primary function of insurance is to provide protection, collective risk, and evaluation of risks. The insurance products also cater to the secondary functions like avoidance of losses, investment and savings, small capital to cover large risk, source for foreign exchange. Since all this depends on an individual's needs the insurance advisor should be smart and knowledgeable enough to propose the right policy to the right person. Fig 5.4 shows the same.

Source :Primary

5.4.2 Employees would recommend employment opportunity in their company to a friend

Table 5.19 Employees would recommend employment opportunity in their company to a friend in Insurance Sector

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree somewhat	7	6.3	6.3	6.3
	Neutral	21	18.8	18.8	25.0
	Agree strongly	84	75.0	75.0	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary

Many of the employees in the insurance sector recommended employment of a friend to their company. This shows that in spite of not being engaged, employee refer to their friends for an initial job opening or as a stop gap arrangement to their friends. From the table 5.19 it is seen that 75 % of the employees are confident enough to recommend job opportunities of their companies to their friends and relatives. The insurance sector has plenty of job opportunities and at the same time government is trying to boost this sector. Therefore, for the fresher's, house wives and elderly people this is an additional source of income. The below graph also depicts this.

Source: Primary

5.5 OVERALL SATISFACTION OF RESPONDENTS ON THE ORGANIZATIONAL ASPECTS IN INSURANCE SECTOR

Table 5.20 Overall satisfaction of respondents on the organizational aspects in Insurance Sector

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Overall satisfaction with this organization as an employee.	112	3.00	1.00	4.00	343.00	3.0625	1.0335
Overall, I am happy with the leadership and Planning in the organization.	112	4.00	1.00	5.00	364.00	3.2500	1.1507
Overall, I am happy with the organizational culture and communication.	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	350.00	3.1250	0.99662
Overall, I understand the importance of my role to the success of the organization.	112	3.00	2.00	5.00	476.00	4.2500	1.3048
Overall the work environment is good	112	3.00	1.00	4.00	336.00	3.0000	1.17787

Overall the superior subordinate relationship is good	112	3.00	2.00	5.00	364.00	3.2500	0.66441
Overall Training and development are good in the organization	112	1.00	3.00	4.00	392.00	3.5000	0.50225
Overall, I'm satisfied with this organization's benefits package	112	1.00	2.00	3.00	308.00	2.7500	0.43496
Valid N (list wise)	112						

Source: Primary

The above table displays the overall satisfaction of employees on organizational, group and individual factors. Overall satisfaction has a value of 3.0625 which is less and shows that employees are in a category of neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. In particular it can be seen that each individual understands their role in the organization and has a value of 4.25. The least satisfaction is regarding the organizational benefit package which has a value of 2.75 and the dispersion value that is standard deviation is also the least with 0.43496. This is an indicator that majority of respondents are not happy with the pay benefits they receive from their company.

Source: Primary

The fig 5.6 shows that employees in the insurance sector are clear about their individual role. They are also aware that their individual contribution matters a lot to the organization's success. The second important factor that the employees are happy about is the training and development activities in the insurance sector. The benefit package is not very attractive. The insurance sector should have a lucrative package to motivate employees to enter this sector.

5.5.1 Analysis on organizations leadership and planning in the insurance sector

Table 5.21 Descriptive Statistics Analysis on organizations leadership and planning in Insurance Sector							
	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I understand the long-term strategy of this organization	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	322.00	2.8750	0.93119
There is adequate planning of corporate objectives	112	4.00	1.00	5.00	357.00	3.1875	1.24141
There is adequate planning of departmental objectives	112	1.00	3.00	4.00	420.00	3.7500	0.43496
There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives	112	3.00	1.00	4.00	322.00	2.8750	1.05800
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	392.00	3.5000	0.86992
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization	112	4.00	1.00	5.00	301.00	2.6875	1.10715
The leaders of this organization care about their employees' well being	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	399.00	3.5625	0.61191

The leaders of this organization are open to input from employees	112	3.00	2.00	5.00	336.00	3.0000	0.86992
Valid N (listwise)	112						

Source: Primary

The above table 5.21 makes an analysis of respondents under the heading of organizational leadership and planning. Majority of respondents are happy with the departmental planning whereas they lack confidence in the leadership of the organization. It is very clear from this that individual targets are well known by the employees, and also the departments are aware of their contribution towards achieving the business goals. Employees are not very confident about their immediate seniors and also the sales managers. Trust in the leaders is missing in this sector.

5.5.1.1 Interpretation of the factor Analysis on organizational leadership and planning

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.776	47.202	47.202	3.776	47.202	47.202
2	1.503	18.784	65.986	1.503	18.784	65.986
3	1.340	16.745	82.731	1.340	16.745	82.731
4	0.691	8.633	91.364			
5	0.393	4.917	96.281			
6	0.170	2.119	98.400			
7	0.128	1.600	100.000			
8	1.001E-013	1.015E-013	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Source: Primary

The output of factor analysis is obtained by requesting Principal Component Analysis and specifying a rotation. The first step in interpreting the result deals with factors extracted their Eigen values and the cumulative percentage of variance. From the above table 5.22 it is very clear that 82.731% of variance is obtained if three factors are obtained. This is fairly good because we can have three questions considered for the factor organizational leadership and

planning instead of eight questions [82.731% of information content is retained by three factors extracted out of eight].

5.5.1.2 Interpretation of the Communalities of factor analysis on organizational leadership and planning

	Initial	Extraction
I understand the long-term strategy of this organization	1.000	0.815
There is adequate planning of corporate objectives	1.000	0.888
There is adequate planning of departmental objectives	1.000	0.907
There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives	1.000	0.764
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.	1.000	0.907
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization	1.000	0.907
The leaders of this organization care about their employees' well being	1.000	0.697
The leaders of this organization are open to input from employees	1.000	0.733
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

Communality is the proportion of variance in the original variable which is captured by the extracted factor. The table above shows that after three factors are extracted and retained the communality is 0.815, 0.888, and 0.907 so on. This means that 81.5% of the variance [information content] of question 1 is captured by the extracted factors and the least being 69.7%.

5.5.1.3 Interpretation of Rotated Component Matrix of factor analysis on organizational leadership and planning

	Component		
	1	2	3
1 I understand the long-term strategy of this organization	0.636	0.527	0.365

2 There is adequate planning of corporate objectives	-0.140	-0.044	0.931
3 There is adequate planning of departmental objectives	0.931	0.110	-0.171
4 There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives	0.380	0.776	0.133
5 There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.	0.931	0.110	-0.171
6 I have confidence in the leadership of this organization	-0.145	0.916	-0.216
7 The leaders of this organization care about their employees' well being	0.760	0.049	0.341
8 The leaders of this organization are open to input from employees	0.745	0.056	-0.418
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.			

Source: Primary

The analysis of the factor matrix is based on the loading each factor has column wise. The first factor has two statements which has high loading value of 0.931. The second component has one statement which has a high loading of 0.916 and the third component has one statement which has a loading of 0.931. Therefore, it can be concluded that the eight questions under the heading of this organizations leadership and planning can be reduced to four statements

5.5.2 Analysis on organizations corporate culture and communications

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough	112	4.00	1.00	5.00	315.00	2.8125	0.95419
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough	112	3.00	1.00	4.00	273.00	2.4375	1.17620

I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially	112	3.00	2.00	5.00	343.00	3.0625	1.03350
I can trust what this organization tells	112	4.00	1.00	5.00	329.00	2.9375	1.09282
This organization treats me like a person, not a number	112	3.00	1.00	4.00	294.00	2.6250	0.99662
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done	112	4.00	1.00	5.00	329.00	2.9375	1.44123
Staffing levels are adequate to provide quality products/ services	112	2.00	1.00	3.00	259.00	2.3125	0.92055
Quality is a top priority with this organization	112	3.00	1.00	4.00	336.00	3.0000	1.17787
Safety is a top priority with this organization	112	1.00	2.00	3.00	308.00	2.7500	0.43496
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	392.00	3.5000	0.86992
Employees are treated fairly here regardless of race, gender, age, religion or sexual orientation	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	378.00	3.3750	0.93119
I like the people I work with at this organization	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	364.00	3.2500	0.90544
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation	112	1.00	2.00	3.00	308.00	2.7500	0.43496
Valid N (listwise)	112						

Source: Primary

Cooperation between the workers scores a high value. It has a ranking of 3.5 which is a high score amongst all factors considered under the heading the organizations corporate culture and communications. The insurance sector has a culture of team work to a certain extent and employees seem to be cooperating with one another.

5.5.2.1 Communalities on organizations corporate culture and communications

Table 5.26 Communalities on organizations corporate culture and communications		
	Initial	Extraction
This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough	1.000	0.782
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough	1.000	0.864
I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially	1.000	0.827
I can trust what this organization tells	1.000	0.719
This organization treats me like a person, not a number	1.000	0.760
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done	1.000	0.752
Staffing levels are adequate to provide quality products/services	1.000	0.751
Quality is a top priority with this organization	1.000	0.469
Safety is a top priority with this organization	1.000	0.930
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization	1.000	0.930
Employees are treated fairly here regardless of race, gender, age, religion or sexual orientation	1.000	0.835
I like the people I work with at this organization	1.000	0.910
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation	1.000	0.930
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The table above shows that after four factors extracted and retained the communality are 0.782, 0.864 and so on. This means that 78.2% of the variance [information content] of question 1 is captured by the extracted factors and the least being 46.9% for the eighth question under the factors for corporate culture and communication.

5.5.2.2 Interpretation of the factor Analysis on corporate culture and communications

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.101	46.930	46.930	6.101	46.930	46.930
2	1.827	14.052	60.982	1.827	14.052	60.982
3	1.494	11.491	72.473	1.494	11.491	72.473
4	1.036	7.972	80.445	1.036	7.972	80.445
5	0.898	6.904	87.350			
6	0.662	5.095	92.445			
7	0.399	3.072	95.517			
8	0.274	2.107	97.623			
9	0.238	1.829	99.452			
10	0.050	0.383	99.835			
11	0.021	0.165	100.000			
12	1.001E-013	1.010E-013	100.000			
13	-1.002E-013	-1.015E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

The output of factor analysis is obtained by requesting Principal Component Analysis and specifying a rotation. The first step in interpreting the result deals with factors extracted, their Eigen values and the cumulative percentage of variance. From the above table it is very clear that 80.445% of variance is obtained if four factors are obtained. This is fairly good because we can have four questions considered for the factor organizational culture and communications instead of thirteen questions [80.445% of information content is retained by four factors extracted out of thirteen].

5.5.2.3 Rotated Component Matrix on organizations corporate culture and communications

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough	0.357	-0.311	-0.622	0.414
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough	0.149	-0.139	0.906	0.023

I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially	-0.146	0.874	0.016	0.204
I can trust what this organization tells	0.520	-0.229	0.177	-0.603
This organization treats me like a person, not a number	0.406	0.766	-0.088	-0.027
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done	0.344	0.105	0.000	0.789
Staffing levels are adequate to provide quality products/services	0.824	0.112	-0.226	-0.093
Quality is a top priority with this organization	0.621	0.238	0.113	0.121
Safety is a top priority with this organization	0.950	-0.006	0.089	0.140
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization	0.950	-0.006	0.089	0.140
Employees are treated fairly here regardless of race, gender, age, religion or sexual orientation	0.877	0.175	-0.145	-0.121
I like the people I work with at this organization	0.885	-0.318	-0.080	0.139
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation	0.950	-0.006	0.089	0.140
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.				

Source: Primary

The analysis of the factor matrix is based on the loading each factor has column wise. The first factor has three statements which has high loading value of 0.950. The second component has one statement which has a high loading of 0.874, the third component has one statement which has a loading of 0.90 and the fourth factor has a loading of 0.789. Therefore, it can be concluded that the thirteen questions under the heading of this organizations corporate culture and communication can be reduced to six statements.

5.5.3 Analysis on individual's role in the organization

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I like the type of work that I do	112	2.00	3.00	5.00	490.00	4.3750	0.93119
I am given enough authority to make decisions I need to make	112	3.00	2.00	5.00	413.00	3.6875	1.49492

I believe my job is secure Deadlines at this organization are realistic	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	392.00	3.5000	0.86992
I feel I am valued in this organization	112	1.00	3.00	4.00	420.00	3.7500	0.43496
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal	112	3.00	2.00	5.00	476.00	4.2500	1.30488
I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life	112	3.00	1.00	4.00	350.00	3.1250	1.22383
I have a clear understanding of my job role	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	392.00	3.5000	0.86992
Valid N (listwise)	112						

Source: Primary

Majority of the insurance employees enjoy the type of work they are doing. The rank obtained for this statement is as high as 4.375. The least ranking is obtained for the statement related to balance between work and personal life which is 3.125. This is true by the nature of the job. The employees need to meet the customers at their convenience and to finish with a sales deal requires a lot of patience and motivation.

5.5.3.1 Analysis on communalities Individual's role in the organization

Table 5.30 Communalities Individual's role in the organization in Insurance Sector		
	Initial	Extraction
I like the type of work that I do	1.000	0.851
I am given enough authority to make decisions I need to make	1.000	0.726
I believe my job is secure deadlines at this organization are realistic	1.000	0.981
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal	1.000	0.981
I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life	1.000	0.927
My job makes good use of my skills and abilities	1.000	0.981
I have a clear understanding of my job role	1.000	0.981
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The communalities values range from 0.981 which is the highest to a value 0.726 which is the least. This tells that after two factors are extracted and retained from the heading Your role in this organization the information content captured by these variables is 98.1% to 72.6% which is quite high.

5.5.3.2 Analysis on Individual's role in the organization

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.322	76.034	76.034	5.322	76.034	76.034
2	1.105	15.784	91.818	1.105	15.784	91.818
3	0.419	5.985	97.802			
4	0.154	2.198	100.000			
5	-1.000E-013	-1.005E-013	100.000			
6	-1.001E-013	-1.018E-013	100.000			
7	-1.006E-013	-1.087E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

This factor matrix gives an indication that 91.818% of the total variance is contained in the two factors extracted from the seven questions which are considered for the concept of your role in the organization.

5.5.3.3 Rotated Component Matrix on Individual's role in the organization

	Component	
	1	2
I like the type of work that I do	0.899	-0.206
I am given enough authority to make decisions I need to make	0.704	-0.480
I believe my job is secure Deadlines at this organization are realistic	0.990	-0.029
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal	0.990	-0.029
I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life	0.003	0.963
My job makes good use of my skills and abilities	0.990	-0.029
I have a clear understanding of my job role	0.990	-0.029

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Source: Primary

The factor matrix indicates four variables having a high loading of 0.990 for the first factor. These variables can be grouped together into a single variable but the researcher intends to use all the four statements as factor 1. The statement relating to maintaining a balance between work and personal life scores a high loading of 0.963 which is considered as the second factor.

5.5.4 Analysis on Work Environment

Table 5.33 Descriptive Statistics Analysis on Work Environment in Insurance Sector

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My physical working conditions are good	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	364.00	3.2500	0.56153
My general work area is adequately lit	112	1.00	3.00	4.00	420.00	3.7500	0.43496
My general work area is adequately heated/ cooled	112	3.00	1.00	4.00	329.00	2.9375	1.25405
My general work area is adequately clean	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	378.00	3.3750	0.86081
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	357.00	3.1875	0.95419
I feel physically safe in my work environment	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	378.00	3.3750	0.93119
Valid N (listwise)	112						

Source: Primary

The statement relating to lighting of the work area scores the highest ranking with a value of 3.75 and the least value is scored by the statement relating to the work area being adequately heated and cooled. The insurance job requires a lot of travelling and the employees need to meet customers. There it is seen that employees are not having a favorite opinion towards temperature.

5.5.4.1 Analysis on communalities on work environment

	Initial	Extraction
My physical working conditions are good	1.000	0.784
My general work area is adequately lit	1.000	0.932
My general work area is adequately heated/cooled	1.000	0.638
My general work area is adequately clean	1.000	0.866
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work	1.000	0.835
I feel physically safe in my work environment	1.000	0.831
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

Communalities values from 0.932 to 0.638. The two variables extracted on the factor ‘your work environment’ gives a cumulative percentage of 81.447 and individual commonalties as shown in the above table.

5.5.4.2 Analysis on Total variance on work environment

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.645	60.753	60.753	3.645	60.753	60.753
2	1.242	20.694	81.447	1.242	20.694	81.447
3	0.659	10.983	92.429			
4	0.355	5.913	98.342			
5	0.069	1.149	99.491			
6	0.031	0.509	100.000			

Source: Primary

The six questions related to working condition can be reduced to two. These two questions can capture 81.447% of information content of all questions put together. It is necessary to consider those questions whose Eigen values are one and more than one.

5.5.4.3 Analysis of Rotated Component Matrix on work environment

	Component	
	1	2
My physical working conditions are good	0.222	0.857
My general work area is adequately lit	0.958	0.115
My general work area is adequately heated/cooled	0.532	-0.596
My general work area is adequately clean	0.896	0.253
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work	0.872	-0.273
I feel physically safe in my work environment	0.911	-0.031
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.		
a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.		

Source: Primary

The two questions for the factor working conditions are related to the illumination and the overall working condition of the organization. The question that can be included is Physical conditions of work are good and the second one is related to the lighting facilities provided in the organization.

5.5.5 Analysis on Relationships with supervisor

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My supervisor treats me fairly	112	3.00	1.00	4.00	287.00	2.5625	0.70750
My supervisor treats me with respect	112	1.00	2.00	3.00	294.00	2.6250	0.48630
My supervisor handles my work-related issues satisfactorily	112	3.00	2.00	5.00	329.00	2.9375	1.14908
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily	112	3.00	1.00	4.00	322.00	2.8750	1.17116
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	336.00	3.0000	0.71028

My supervisor tells me when my work needs	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	336.00	3.0000	0.71028
My supervisor is open to hearing my opinion or feedback	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	294.00	2.6250	0.93119
My supervisor helps me develop to my fullest potential	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	315.00	2.8125	0.52900
I can trust what my supervisor tells me	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	315.00	2.8125	0.52900
Valid N (list wise)	112						

Source: Primary

Based on the ranking on superiors it is seen that the question related to whether the supervisors treat subordinates fairly gets the least ranking while two questions relating to acknowledgement of subordinates gets average ranking of 3.00. Usually the insurance sector employees work as a team. Therefore, when individuals perform well they are acknowledged by their supervisors.

5.5.5.1 Analysis on Communalities of Factor Analysis for Relationships with supervisor

Table No 5.38 Relationships with supervisor: Communalities of factor Analysis		
	Initial	Extraction
My supervisor treats me fairly	1.000	0.474
My supervisor treats me with respect	1.000	0.806
My supervisor handles my work-related issues satisfactorily	1.000	0.476
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily	1.000	0.697
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well	1.000	0.933
My supervisor tells me when my work needs	1.000	0.933
My supervisor is open to hearing my opinion or feedback	1.000	0.761
My supervisor helps me develop to my fullest potential	1.000	0.865
I can trust what my supervisor tells me	1.000	0.865
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

Communalities result for the superior and subordinate relationship shows that there are two questions which have a less value of 0.476 and 0.474 and the remaining have a moderately high

value. The two questions which are extracted for the factor on superiors contain about 75.697% of information for the factor.

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.820	53.553	53.553	4.820	53.553	53.553
2	1.993	22.144	75.697	1.993	22.144	75.697
3	0.840	9.335	85.032			
4	0.701	7.792	92.824			
5	0.392	4.357	97.181			
6	0.183	2.028	99.209			
7	0.071	0.791	100.000			
8	-1.000E-013	-1.005E-013	100.000			
9	-1.001E-013	-1.015E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

The Eigen value for two questions is greater than one which signifies that two questions can be considered for the above factor. The questions can capture 75.697% of the information content for the given factor relationship with the superiors.

5.5.5.2 Analysis on Rotated Component Matrix of Factor Analysis for Relationships with supervisor

	Component	
	1	2
My supervisor treats me fairly	0.298	0.621
My supervisor treats me with respect	0.755	0.487
My supervisor handles my work-related issues satisfactorily	-0.347	0.596
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily	-0.008	0.835
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well	0.966	-0.026
My supervisor tells me when my work needs	0.966	-0.026
My supervisor is open to hearing my opinion or feedback	0.836	-0.250
My supervisor helps me develop to my fullest potential	0.761	0.535
I can trust what my supervisor tells me	0.761	0.535

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Source: Primary

The questions which can be considered, are regarding acknowledgement of supervisors for work well done, and supervisor's consideration in telling what work should be done. The other question is regarding how supervisors handles personal issues. Therefore, three questions can be considered instead of nine components for the factor Relationship with superiors.

5.5.6 Analysis on organizational training and development

Table 5.41 Analysis on organizational training and development: Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	392.00	3.5000	0.86992
This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	343.00	3.0625	0.75075
provides enough information, equipment and resources	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	343.00	3.0625	0.75075
This organization provides training or experiences to help me explore other possible opportunities within the company	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	364.00	3.2500	0.56153
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement	112	1.00	3.00	4.00	364.00	3.2500	0.43496
I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career	112	1.00	3.00	4.00	420.00	3.7500	0.43496
There is room for me to advance at this organization	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	364.00	3.2500	0.83288
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay	112	3.00	1.00	4.00	308.00	2.7500	0.75337

I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion	112	4.00	1.00	5.00	336.00	3.0000	0.86992
Valid N (list wise)	112						

Source: Primary

The least ranking is related to a question regarding linking of pay and good work. In most of the organizations the pay is directly not linked to performance. Also, it is seen that there is no immediate acknowledgement for the ones, who do good work. At the same time, it is observed that organizations do consider the career of individuals in this sector. Training on specific issues is provided for employees whereas knowledge enhancement and overall development is not considered much in the industry.

5.5.6.1 Analysis on Communalities of factor analysis for the factor organizational training and development

Table 5.42 Communalities of factor analysis for the factor organizational training and development in Insurance Sector		
	Initial	Extraction
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed	1.000	0.937
This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need	1.000	0.964
provides enough information, equipment and recourses	1.000	0.964
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement	1.000	0.934
I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career	1.000	0.934
This organization provides training or experiences to help me explore other possible opportunities within the company	1.000	0.820
There is room for me to advance at this organization	1.000	0.727
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay	1.000	0.650
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion	1.000	0.803
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The communalities values range from 0.964 to 0.650. These values are quite good. Most of the information is captured by the Principal component analysis. The extraction leads to three

questions which can get all the information needed for the factor related to training and development.

5.5.6.2 Analysis on total variance of factor analysis for the factor organizational training and development

Table 5.43 Organizational training and development : Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.119	45.768	45.768	4.119	45.768	45.768
2	2.382	26.464	72.232	2.382	26.464	72.232
3	1.231	13.682	85.914	1.231	13.682	85.914
4	0.687	7.638	93.552			
5	0.432	4.797	98.349			
6	0.115	1.282	99.631			
7	0.033	0.369	100.000			
8	1.000E-013	1.005E-013	100.000			
9	1.000E-013	1.002E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

Three questions have an Eigen value of more than one which is an indication that these can be questions which can be considered for the factor training and development. It is also seen that these three questions can capture 85.914% of information needed for the factor training and development.

5.5.6.3 Analysis on Rotated Component Matrix of factor analysis for the factor organizational training and development

Table 5.44 Organizational training and development: Rotated Component Matrix			
	Component		
	1	2	3
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed	0.101	0.960	-0.070
This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need	0.569	0.793	0.110
provides enough information, equipment and resources	0.569	0.793	0.110

My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement	0.920	0.293	0.037
I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career	-0.920	-0.293	-0.037
This organization provides training or experiences to help me explore other possible opportunities within the company	0.553	-0.447	-0.560
There is room for me to advance at this organization	0.241	0.077	-0.814
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay	0.127	-0.086	0.792
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion	0.238	0.254	0.826
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.			
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.			

Source: Primary

The three questions which can be distinctively asked are the one related to the company clearly identifying what is expected from individuals in terms of advancement, providing adequate initial training for employees in the company and consideration of promotion if good work is done by the employees. These three questions can be asked to elicit the same response in terms of organizational training and development

5.5.7 Analysis on the factor Pay and benefits

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	399.00	3.5625	0.70750
Sick leave policy	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	336.00	3.0000	0.71028
Retirement plan benefits	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	301.00	2.6875	0.58558
Life insurance benefits	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	308.00	2.7500	0.56153
Tuition reimbursement benefits	112	1.00	2.00	3.00	294.00	2.6250	0.48630
My pay is fair for the work I perform	112	2.00	2.00	4.00	308.00	2.7500	0.56153
Valid N (list wise)	112						

Source: Primary

Respondents in the insurance sector do not have any complaint towards the amount of vacation given to them but they are not happy with the tuition reimbursement and retirement plans the organization is offering to them.

5.5.7.1 Analysis on communalities of factor analysis for the factor Pay and benefits

	Initial	Extraction
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)	1.000	0.827
Sick leave policy	1.000	0.805
Retirement plan benefits	1.000	0.449
Life insurance benefits	1.000	0.970
Tuition reimbursement benefits	1.000	0.913
My pay is fair for the work I perform	1.000	0.970
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The communalities are quite high except for one value relating to retirement benefits. Therefore, it can be agreed that two questions are enough to draw conclusions regarding pay and benefits in the organization in the insurance sector.

5.5.7.2 Analysis on Total variance of factor analysis for the factor Pay and benefits

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.614	60.232	60.232	3.614	60.232	60.232
2	1.319	21.979	82.211	1.319	21.979	82.211
3	0.844	14.061	96.272			
4	0.146	2.440	98.712			
5	0.077	1.288	100.000			
6	1.001E-013	1.017E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

The Eigen values of two variables are greater than one and these two questions can capture around 82.211% of information regarding the factor of pay and benefits. The method of elimination suffices with two questions for pay and benefits. The two questions can generate nearly 82% of the information contained in the six questions which are there in the questionnaire.

5.5.7.3 Analysis on Rotated compound Matrix of factor analysis for the factor Pay and benefits

	Component	
	1	2
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off	-0.086	-0.905
Sick leave policy	0.736	0.513
Retirement plan benefits	0.108	0.661
Life insurance benefits	0.949	0.264
Tuition reimbursement benefits	0.936	-0.190
My pay is fair for the work I perform	0.949	0.264
a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.		

Source: Primary

The two questions that can be extracted include the one which relates to Life insurance benefits and the other which includes a question on retirement benefit. Apart from this a question on fairness of pay can be used to get insights into the factors concerning pay and benefits.

5.6 FACTOR ANALYSIS FOR INSURANCE SECTOR

A very useful tool is used to reduce data complexity by reducing the number of variables being used in the study. In this study factor analysis is used to extract the various factors which will make decision makers identify what exactly makes employees engaged in the organization where they are working. The table below summaries the number of questions before and after factor analysis for the relevant parameters considered

Parameter	Number of Questions Before Factor Analysis	Number of Questions After Factor Analysis
Organizations Leadership and Planning	8	4
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	13	6
Individual role at the organization	8	5

Work Environment	6	2
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	9	3
Training and Development	9	3
Pay and Benefits	7	3
Total	49	26

Source: Primary

The above table represents the number of factors that needs to be considered in each of the parameters after factor analysis. Work environment has the least factors whereas organizational culture and communication has the highest number of questions.

The questionnaire drafted after factor analysis is annexed (Annexure 2(a))

Parameters	Questions After factor reduction
Organizations Leadership and Planning	1 There is adequate planning of departmental objectives
	2 There is adequate planning of corporate objectives
	3 I have confidence in the leadership of this organization
	4 There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	1 I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization
	2 I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially
	3 This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough
	4 This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done
	5 Safety is a top priority with this organization
	6 Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation
Individual role at the organization	1 I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life
	2 I believe my job is secure
	3 Deadlines at this organization are realistic
	4 I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal

	5 My job makes good use of my skills and abilities
	6 I have a clear understanding of my job role
Work Environment	1 My physical working conditions are good
	2 My general work area is adequately lit
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	3 My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily
	4 My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well
	5 My supervisor tells me when my work needs
Training and Development	1 This organization provided as much initial training as I needed
	2 My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement
	3 I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion
Pay and Benefits	1 Retirement plan benefits
	2 Life insurance benefits
	3 My pay is fair for the work I perform

Source: Primary

The above table is the factor reduction table with a particular parameter and the likely questions that can be asked to elicit the same kind of response. The detailed questionnaire need not be used for further study on employee engagement in the service sector in particular to the insurance sector.

Fig 5.7 Factors of Engagement for the Insurance Sector - Saks model

The above diagrammatic representation shows employee engagement is an outcome of organizational elements, group elements and individual elements. These elements are considered

in the factor analysis and the study identifies the most important factor and the least important factor. Apart from the individual elements certain personal factors also contribute to employee engagement. This can be represented in a diagrammatic representation as below.

Fig 5.8 Individual factors of employee engagement in the Insurance Sector - Saks model

The above factors, contribution towards employee engagement are estimated using the discriminant analysis and also the methods of correlation and regression.

5.7 DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS FOR CLASSIFICATION AND PREDICTION IN THE INSURANCE SECTOR

Discriminant Analysis is used to classify objects into two or more groups based on the knowledge of some variable {Characteristics} related to the Study. Typically, these groupings would be user/nonuser, engaged /disengaged, high risk/low risk etc. The form of equation in a three variable discriminant analysis is

$$Y=a+K_1X_1+K_2X_2+K_3X_3$$

Where Y is the dependent variable and X₁, X₂ and X₃ are independent variables and K₁K₂ and K₃ are constant coefficients.

Y is a classification into two or more groupings and therefore known as a grouping variable. Groups are formed on the basis of the existing data and coded as 1 and 2. The independent

variables are continuous scale variables and used as predictors of group to which the objects belong.

Then a model is built which is linear in nature and use the coefficients of the equation to calculate the Y discriminant score --- for any new data points that we want to classify into one of the groups. A decision rule is formulated for this purpose --- to determine the cutoff score, which is usually the midpoint of the mean discriminant scores of the two groups.

Table 5.51 Wilks' Lambda value for strength of the Discriminant function for the Insurance Sector				
Test of Function(s)	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	0.531	68.391	4	0.000

Source: Primary

The statistical significance of the discriminant function is answered by looking at the Wilks Lambda value and the probability value of the test is given in the above table 5.49. The value of Wilks Lambda is 0.531. This value is in between 0 to 1 and a low value indicates better discriminating power. Thus, a value 0.531 is an indicator that the model is a good fit. Also, the probability value of F-test indicates that discriminating between the two groups is highly significant. This is because the significant value is 0.00 which means that F test is significant to a confidence level of up to 100%.

Table 5.52 Best Predictor in Insurance Sector: Structure Matrix	
	Function-1
Gender	0.841
Salary	0.560
How long have you worked for this organization?	-0.243
Age	-0.014
Pooled within-groups correlations between discriminating variables and standardized canonical discriminant functions.	

Source: Primary

Better predictor: There are four independent variables namely Age, Salary, Length of service and gender. From the output table that is structure table Matrix, it is observed that gender is the best predictor followed by salary then followed by length of service and the last factor is age. The

absolute value in the structure matrix for each independent variable indicates its relative importance in prediction.

Table 5.53 Canonical Discriminant Function Coefficients in Insurance Sector	
	Function-1
Age	-0.124
Salary	0.000128
How long have you worked for this organization?	0.200
Gender	2.844
(Constant)	-2.940
Unstandardized coefficients	

Source: Primary

In order to compute the discriminant score for engagement the following discriminant function has to be used.

$$Y = a + K_1X_1 + K_2X_2 + K_3X_3 + K_4X_4$$

$$Y = -2.940 - 0.124X_1 + 0.000128X_2 + 0.200X_3 + 2.844X_4 \text{ [Calculated values Annexed]}$$

Where Y is the dependent variable [Engagement], -2.940 is the constant and the respective co-efficient are -0.124, 0.000128, 0.200, 2.844 for age, salary, length of service and gender

Table 5.54 Functions at Group Centroids: Cut off values for Engagement	
	Function-1
Engaged	1.203
Disengaged	-0.722
Unstandardized canonical discriminant functions evaluated at group means	

Source: Primary

The means of canonical variables, gives us the new means for the transformed group centroids. Thus, the new mean for engaged is 1.203 and the new mean for group disengaged is -0.722. This means that the midpoint of these two is 0.2405. This is clear with the diagram below.

This also helps in the decision rule for classifying any new case. If the discriminant score of an applicant falls to the right of the midpoint we classify as engaged and if it falls to the left it is classified as disengaged.

Table 5.55 Classification Results in Insurance Sector					
		Engaged	Predicted Group Membership		Total
			Engaged	Disengaged	
Original	Count	Engaged	28	14	42
		Disengaged	0	70	70
	%	Engaged	66.7	33.3	100.0
		Disengaged	0.0	100.0	100.0
a. 87.5% of original grouped cases correctly classified.					

Source: Primary

The above output table is called the classification matrix or also known as the confusion matrix. It indicates that the discriminant function that is obtained is able to classify 87.5% of the original data to be grouped and classified correctly. Since this value is above 80% the discriminant model is a good fit.

5.7.1 Correlation and Regression analysis taking individual independent variables

The regression analysis is judged for its usefulness based on

- 1 Overall F-Test for the model. If this is significant say at 95% then the model is a good fit. This shows up as a significant value in the model summary [which should be less than 0.05].
- 2 The R square value of the model tells the percentage of variation in the dependent variable explained by the independent variable.

Table 5.56 Model Summary and Parameter Estimates for Salary in Insurance Sector							
Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.463	94.824	1	110	0.000	-3.919	0.000128
The independent variable is Salary.							

The linear model is a good fit between employee engagement and salary. The F test shows that the model is significant. The R square value is 46.3% which denotes the variation in employee engagement explained by the independent factor salary. The Regression equation can be written in the form

$$Y=a+bX_1$$

$$Y=-3.919+.000128 X_1$$

Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.105	12.959	1	110	0.000	0.588	-0.307

The independent variable is How long have you worked for this organization?

The linear model is a good fit between employee engagement and years of working in the organization. The F test shows that the model is significant. The R square value is 10.5% which denotes the variation in employee engagement explained by the independent factor length of stay in the organization. The Regression equation can be written in the form

$$Y=a+bX_1$$

$$Y=0.5888-0.307 X_1$$

Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.820	500.560	1	110	0.000	-3.747	3.155

The independent variable is Gender.

The linear model is a good fit between employee engagement and gender. The F test shows that the model is significant. The R square value is 82% which denotes the variation in employee engagement explained by the independent factor length of stay in the organization. The Regression equation can be written in the form

$$Y=a+bX_1$$

$$Y=-3.747+3.155X_1$$

Table 5.59 Model Summary and Parameter Estimates for Age in Insurance Sector							
Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.000	0.041	1	110	0.839	0.124	-0.004
The independent variable is Age.							

The linear model is not a good fit between employee engagement and age. The F test shows that the model is insignificant. The R square value is also zero which denotes the variation in employee engagement explained by the independent factor age. Diagrammatic representation for the various individual factors affecting employee Engagement is shown in graphs below;

Fig 5.9 Diagrammatic representation for the various individual factors affecting employee Engagement

SECTION B: Analysis for the Banking Sector

The Banking sector provides plenty of job opportunities in the city of Mangalore. The Banking industry has a career path which is attractive and also plenty of job roles. This is a very dynamic industry which is highly regulated. Being a service oriented organization banks need to have talented skillful and resourceful employees who can effectively deal with customers. Also, this industry is becoming a tech savvy one, which demands computer literate employees. The total number of respondents in the Banking sector is 119. These are the respondents who have given complete response to all the questions in the questionnaire. Therefore, care has been taken to eliminate missing values and get the most accurate responses.

5.8 CAUSAL FACTORS AFFECTING EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN THE BANKING SECTOR

5.8.1 Based on Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	84	70.6	70.6	70.6
	Female	35	29.4	29.4	100.0
	Total	119	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary

The number of female responses is 29.4% which is comparatively less. This is a general indication that the number of female workers in the banking sector is less in Mangalore. More number of male employees are associated in the banking sector. In the middle level management, it is seen that women contribute to 30% of the workforce. In the top level it is even lesser in number. For the women employees who have been employed in the banks, they say family support is one of the most important criteria for progressing in their career.

The attribute Gender affects the engagement levels in the banking sector. Predominately it is seen that most of the female workers in the sector are engaged. The number of women respondents is less. Female employees are happy with the facilities provided and are also happy with the compensation to some extent. Engagement levels with the male gender are exactly fifty percent only. This can be seen in table 5.61.

Count		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Engaged	Engaged	57	29	86
	Disengaged	27	6	33
Total		84	35	119

Source: Primary

5.8.2 Based on Age

Age		
N	Valid	119
	Missing	0
Mean		31.7899
Median		28.0000
Mode		24.00
Std. Deviation		9.37258
Minimum		24.00
Maximum		53.00

Source: Primary

The mean age of workforce in the banking sector is 31.789 years. The modal age is 24 years. The minimum age is 24 years and maximum age is 53 years. The sector is dominated with youth of a younger age. The banking sector has recruited a large number of youngster's presently as many of the older employees have retired in the recent times. The mean age in the private sector bank is much lesser when compared to that of the public sector.

Count		Engaged		Total
		Engaged	Disengaged	
Age	24.00	21	5	26
	25.00	0	21	21

	26.00	1	6	7
	28.00	7	0	7
	29.00	20	1	21
	35.00	1	0	1
	37.00	1	0	1
	39.00	7	0	7
	41.00	14	0	14
	51.00	7	0	7
	53.00	7	0	7
Total		86	33	119

Source: Primary

The above is a cross tabulation of age with engagement score. It gives a clear understanding of respondent's engagement levels with the age factor considered. It is observed from the table that employees are disengaged in the initial days of service and with time an experienced employee are engaged to their work and organization. A chi-square test is performed to understand the significant association between the two Variables engagement and age factor.

Table 5.64 Chi-Square Tests Age * Engaged employees in Banking sector			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	89.820^a	10	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	101.275	10	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	22.907	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	119		

Source: Primary

The chi-square test reveals a significant association between the two variables that is Engagement level and Age. From the test output it is seen that the significant level is 0.000. This means that Chi-square test is showing a significant association of 100% between the two variables. The chi-square test proves the fact that as an employee gets experience in the banking sector he is more engaged in general.

		Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	0.656			0.000
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	-0.441	0.042	-5.309	0.000 ^c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	-0.419	0.070	-4.991	0.000 ^c
N of Valid Cases		119			

Source: Primary

The contingency coefficient of 0.656 infers that the association between the dependent and independent variable is significant as it is closer to 1 than to 0. This coefficient gives the measure of strength of the output. If the value is close to 0, then there does not exist any strong association between the two variables. However, if the value lies in between 0.5 to 1, there exists a strong relationship. Here since the value is 0.656 there is a strong relationship between age of employees in the bank and employee engagement levels.

			Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	0.333	0.060	4.662
		Age Dependent	0.172	0.050	3.276
		Engaged Dependent	0.788	0.074	5.503
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Age Dependent	0.125	0.025	
		Engaged Dependent	0.755	0.062	

Source: Primary

Lambda is the measure of reduction in error in measuring the association between the two variables. From the table the value of Lambda is 0.333 which means 33.3% error reduction. This is a moderate low value leading to 33.3% reduction in error in estimating or predicting one variable from the other.

5.8.3 Based on length of service

Table 5.67 Length of service of employees in the Banking sector		
Statistics		
N	Valid	119
	Missing	0
Mean		6.3361
Median		2.0000
Mode		1.00
Std. Deviation		7.99817
Minimum		1.00
Maximum		25.00
Sum		754.00

Source: Primary

The average length of service of employees in the banking sector is 6.338 years. This is an indication that the employees stay for a long time in this sector. The median is 2 years and the mode are one year. This shows that there are many employees quitting in the initial stages. Therefore, on boarding activities need to be taken care of in the banking sector. Once the orientation is done properly to the new employees and they are taken care by the organization in the initial days the employees will remain in the organization.

Table 5.68 Length of service of employees in the Banking sector					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1.00	46	38.7	38.7	38.7
	2.00	21	17.6	17.6	56.3
	3.00	7	5.9	5.9	62.2
	4.00	7	5.9	5.9	68.1
	5.00	8	6.7	6.7	74.8
	8.00	1	0.8	0.8	75.6
	9.00	1	0.8	0.8	76.5
	15.00	7	5.9	5.9	82.4
	17.00	7	5.9	5.9	88.2
	23.00	7	5.9	5.9	94.1
	25.00	7	5.9	5.9	100.0
	Total		119	100.0	100.0

Source: Primary

The above table shows that there nearly 56.3% of the respondents have two years of experience in the banking sector. About 5.9% of the employees have more than 15 years of experience in the organization. The banking industry has employees with long experience and their experience can be used for the strategic development of the banks.

Table 5.69 Chi-Square Tests Length of service* Engaged employees in Banking Sector			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	48.656^a	10	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	57.282	10	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	16.590	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	119		

Source: Primary

The chi-square test shows that there is a significant association between length of service and the engagement levels. The result shows that there is 100% association between the dependent and independent variable. The longer they serve the organization better is the engagement levels. The likelihood ratio and linear by linear model also supports the test.

Table 5.70 Chi-Square Tests Symmetric Measures Length of service* Engaged employees in Banking sector				
			Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	0.085	0.065
		How long have you worked for this organization? Dependent	0.000	0.000
		Engaged Dependent	0.273	0.188
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	How long have you worked for this organization? Dependent	0.093	0.022
		Engaged Dependent	0.409	0.070

Source: Primary

Lambda is the measure of reduction in error in measuring the association between the two variables. From the table the value of Lambda is 0.085 which means 8.5% error reduction. This

is a moderate low value leading to 8.5% reduction in error in estimating or predicting one variable from the other.

Table 5.71 Chi-Square Tests Directional Measures Length of service* Engaged employees in the Banking sector					
		Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Approx. T	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	0.539			0.000
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	-0.375	0.040	-4.375	0.000 ^c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	-0.466	0.065	-5.691	0.000 ^c

Source: Primary

The contingency coefficient value of 53.9% supports that there is a strong association between the two variables. The value can lie between 0 and 1. As the value is closer to 1 rather than 0 it can be concluded that the association is strong between the two variables. Length of service has a strong impact on engagement levels in the Banking sector.

5.8.4 Based on Salary

Table 5.72 Salary levels of the Respondents in the Banking sector: Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Salary	119	20000.00	85000.00	38957.9832	18154.42000
Valid N (listwise)	119				

Source: Primary

Salary is an integral component which influences employee engagement. The above table represents the mean salary of employees in the middle level management is Rs 38958 in the banking sector. This is the highest amongst the three sectors which are compared in the study. The minimum salary is Rs 20000 and the maximum salary is Rs 85000. Salary is not a matter of concern in the banking sector. Employees are paid well and also provided with several benefits.

Table 5.73 Chi-Square Tests Salary * Engaged employees in the Banking Sector			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	89.820^a	10	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	101.275	10	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	19.016	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	119		

Source: Primary

The Chi-square test reveals that there is an association with the salary and engagement levels. The Pearson Chi-Square value is 85.820 as both the values of likelihood ratio and linear by linear association values support the chi-square test of association. Banking is the back bone for any country and also the banking job is an aspiration for many individuals. Banks provide a high salary for an entry level job. Career path in the banks are well-defined and it depends on an individual's performance and potential.

			Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	0.333	0.060	0.000
		Salary Dependent	0.172	0.050	0.001
		Engaged Dependent	0.788	0.074	0.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Salary Dependent	0.125	0.025	0.000
		Engaged Dependent	0.755	0.062	0.000

Source: Primary

Lambda is the measure of reduction in error in measuring the association between the two variables. From the table the value of Lambda is 0.333 which means 33.3 % error reduction. This is a moderate value leading to 33.3% reduction in error in estimating or predicting one variable from the other that is salary and employee engagement levels.

		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0.869	0.000
	Cramer's V	0.869	0.000
	Contingency Coefficient	0.656	0.000
N of Valid Cases		119	

Source: Primary

The contingency coefficient value of 65.6 % supports that there is a strong association between the two variables. The value can lie between 0 and 1. As the value is closer to 1 rather than 0 it

can be concluded that the association is strong between the two variables. Salary has a strong impact on engagement levels in the Banking sector. Phi and Cramer's V value also support the association between the two variables.

5.9 ENGAGED WORKFORCE IN THE BANKING SECTOR

Table 5.76 Number of Engaged workforces in Banking Sector					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Engaged	86	72.3	72.3	72.3
	Disengaged	33	27.7	27.7	100.0
	Total	119	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary

The banking sector has 72.3% of workforce who are engaged. This is an indication of workforce being highly motivated to work in the sector. Only 27.74% of human resources in the sector are disengaged. The nature of job has played an important role for employees to be engaged in this sector. Banking sector is one of the exciting sectors which provide ample employment opportunities in the present generation. With the advent of technology, the nature of Banking jobs has changed and employees have a lot of new things to learn. The government has come up with a number of schemes which involves the banks. Thus, employees should be quick learners.

Source: Primary

5.10 EMPLOYEES PLANNING TO STAY IN THE SAME COMPANY FOR MORE THAN TWO YEARS IN BANKING SECTOR

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	77	64.7	64.7	64.7
	Agree Somewhat	8	6.7	6.7	71.4
	Agree strongly	34	28.6	28.6	100.0
	Total	119	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary

Majority of respondents are neutral about the question of continuing their career in the same company. But 28.6% of the employees strongly agree to be staying back in the organization for more than two years and above. The people who have more than five years of experience in this sector show that they will stay back in the same organization. The banking sector requires employees with good organizing skills, mathematical ability, honesty and integrity. Employees need to re-skill themselves to remain in the dynamic work environment.

Source: Primary

5.10.1 Employees recommend company's product

Table 5.78 Employees Recommend company's product [Banking sector]					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree somewhat	7	5.9	5.9	5.9
	Agree Somewhat	112	94.1	94.1	100.0
	Total	119	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary

The employees seem to be very comfortable with the banking product. Almost 94.1% of employees do recommend their company products. The employees are confident with the company products and are also happy to talk about their products to the customers. The nature of job is changed. Automation has made customers go digital.

Source: Primary

5.10.2 Employees would recommend employment opportunity at their company to a friend

Table 5.79 Employees would recommend employment opportunity at their company to a friend

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree somewhat	7	5.9	5.9	5.9
	Neutral	21	17.6	17.6	23.5
	Agree Somewhat	7	5.9	5.9	29.4
	Agree strongly	84	70.6	70.6	100.0
	Total	119	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary

Many of the employees in the banking sector recommended employment of a friend to their company. This shows that in spite of being engaged employee refer to their friends for an initial job opening and encourage people to join the banking sector. Today the nature of banking job has changed. Many employees have retired and plenty of job opportunities are available in this sector. Also, the salary structure for the initial probationary officers is reasonably high when compared to other sectors.

Source: Primary

5.11 OVERALL SATISFACTION OF RESPONDENTS ON THE ORGANIZATIONAL ASPECTS

Table 5.80 Overall satisfaction of respondents on the organizational aspects in Banking Sector						
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Overall satisfaction with this organization as an employee	119	2.00	4.00	413.00	3.4706	0.85195
Overall, I am happy with the leadership and Planning in the organization	119	2.00	4.00	406.00	3.4118	0.91514
Overall, I am happy with the organizational culture and communication	119	2.00	4.00	420.00	3.5294	0.85195
Overall, I understand the importance of my role to the success of the organization	119	2.00	5.00	504.00	4.2353	1.26696
Overall the work environment is good	119	3.00	4.00	448.00	3.7647	0.42598
Overall the superior subordinate relationship is good	119	3.00	5.00	385.00	3.2353	0.64710
Overall Training and development are good in the organization	119	1.00	4.00	399.00	3.3529	0.76566
Overall, I'm satisfied with this organization's benefits package	119	2.00	4.00	336.00	2.8235	0.51498
Valid N (listwise)	119					

Source: Primary

Overall satisfaction has a value of 3.47 which shows that employees are in a category of satisfaction. In particular it can be seen that each individual understands their role in the organization and has a value of 4.23. The least satisfaction is regarding the organizational benefit package which has a value of 2.8235 and the dispersion value that is standard deviation is also

the least with 0.51498. This is an indicator that majority of respondents are not happy with the pay benefits they receive from their company even if the industry standards are quite high.

Source: Primary

The work environment is appreciated by the employees. They are provided with ergonomically designed environment. Apart from this, they are coached continuously and the concept of flexi time is encouraged. The training which many employees have undergone has been rigorous and they can now adjust with any time pressure and work pressure in the organization.

5.11.1 Analysis on organizations leadership and planning

Table 5.81 Descriptive Statistics Analysis on organizations leadership and planning						
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I understand the long-term strategy of this organization	119	2.00	4.00	406.00	3.4118	0.91514

There is adequate planning of corporate objectives	119	1.00	5.00	378.00	3.1765	1.04676
There is adequate planning of departmental objectives	119	3.00	4.00	448.00	3.7647	0.42598
There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives	119	2.00	4.00	399.00	3.3529	0.90749
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.	119	2.00	4.00	420.00	3.5294	0.85195
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization	119	1.00	5.00	329.00	2.7647	1.00596
The leaders of this organization care about their employees' well being	119	3.00	4.00	448.00	3.7647	0.42598
The leaders of this organization are open to input from employees	119	2.00	5.00	364.00	3.0588	0.87618
Valid N (listwise)	119					

Source: Primary

The above table under the heading of organizational leadership and planning reveals that majority of respondents are happy with the departmental planning whereas they lack confidence in the leadership of the organization. Departmental objectives and goals are communicated and employees are aware of these. The top management of private sector banks are very aggressive and want immediate results from employees.

5.11.1.1 Interpretation of the factor Analysis on organizational leadership and planning

Table 5.82 Interpretation of the factor Analysis on organizational leadership and planning in Banking Sector: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.170	64.628	64.628	5.170	64.628	64.628
2	1.233	15.407	80.036	1.233	15.407	80.036

3	0.833	10.409	90.445		
4	0.487	6.086	96.531		
5	0.253	3.160	99.691		
6	0.025	0.309	100.000		
7	-1.000E-013	-1.001E-013	100.000		
8	-1.002E-013	-1.019E-013	100.000		

Source: Primary

The output of factor analysis is obtained by requesting Principal Component Analysis and specifying a rotation. The first step in interpreting the result deals with factors extracted their Eigen values and the cumulative percentage of variance. From the above table it is very clear that 80.036% of variance is obtained if two factors are obtained. This is fairly good because we can have two questions considered for the factor organizational leadership and planning instead of eight questions. 80.036% of information content is retained by two factors extracted out of eight.

5.11.1.2 Interpretation of the Communalities of factor analysis on organizational leadership and planning

	Initial	Extraction
I understand the long-term strategy of this organization	1.000	0.887
There is adequate planning of corporate objectives	1.000	0.543
There is adequate planning of departmental objectives	1.000	0.958
There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives	1.000	0.829
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.	1.000	0.958
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization	1.000	0.688
The leaders of this organization care about their employees' well being	1.000	0.958
The leaders of this organization are open to input from employees	1.000	0.582
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

Communality is the proportion of variance in the original variable which is captured by the extracted factor. The above table reveals that after two factors extracted and retained the communality is 0.958, 0.887 and so on. This means that 95.8% of the variance [information content] of question 1 is captured by the extracted factors and the least being 54.3%.

5.11.1.3 Interpretation of Rotated Component Matrix of factor analysis on organizational leadership and planning

	Component	
	1	2
I understand the long-term strategy of this organization	0.925	0.177
There is adequate planning of corporate objectives	-0.112	-0.728
There is adequate planning of departmental objectives	0.979	0.013
There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives	0.907	0.079
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.	0.979	0.013
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization	0.019	0.829
The leaders of this organization care about their employees' well being	0.979	0.013
The leaders of this organization are open to input from employees	0.729	0.224

Source: Primary

The analysis of the factor matrix is based on the loading each factor has column wise. The first factor has three statements which has high loading value of 0.979. The second component has one statement which has a high loading of 0.829. Therefore, it can be concluded that the eight questions under the heading of organizations leadership and planning can be reduced to two statements for further analysis.

5.11.2 Analysis on organizations corporate culture and communications

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives	119	2.00	4.00	399.00	3.3529	0.90749
This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough	119	1.00	5.00	350.00	2.9412	0.87618
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough	119	1.00	4.00	399.00	3.3529	1.02996

I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially	119	2.00	5.00	329.00	2.7647	0.94516
I can trust what this organization tells	119	1.00	5.00	364.00	3.0588	1.11457
This organization treats me like a person, not a number	119	2.00	4.00	420.00	3.5294	0.85195
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done	119	2.00	5.00	504.00	4.2353	1.26696
Staffing levels are adequate to provide quality products/ services	119	1.00	3.00	308.00	2.5882	0.77473
Quality is a top priority with this organization	119	2.00	4.00	406.00	3.4118	0.91514
Safety is a top priority with this organization	119	2.00	5.00	343.00	2.8824	0.67869
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization	119	2.00	4.00	420.00	3.5294	0.85195
Employees are treated fairly here regardless of race, gender, age, religion or sexual orientation	119	2.00	4.00	420.00	3.5294	0.85195
I like the people I work with at this organization	119	2.00	4.00	406.00	3.4118	.91514
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation	119	2.00	4.00	336.00	2.8235	.51498
Valid N (listwise)	119					

Source: Primary

The banking sector gives enough recognition to the employee. It scores a high value. It has a ranking of 4.2 which is a high score amongst all factors considered under the heading the organizations corporate culture and communications. The private banks measure the performance of employees on a regular basis. Career advancement can be achieved by individuals if they are motivated and perform very well in their job. It is again seen that the number of employees in the organization is less. There seems to be a staff crunch and this is

highlighted by the employees in the banking sector. Though massive recruitment drives have taken place in this sector organizations are finding it difficult to identify the right talent.

5.11.2.1 Communalities on organizations corporate culture and communications

Table 5.86 Communalities on organizations corporate culture and communications		
	Initial	Extraction
This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough	1.000	0.588
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough	1.000	0.970
I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially	1.000	0.651
I can trust what this organization tells	1.000	0.557
This organization treats me like a person, not a number	1.000	0.999
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done	1.000	0.996
Staffing levels are adequate to provide quality products/services	1.000	0.943
Quality is a top priority with this organization	1.000	0.982
Safety is a top priority with this organization	1.000	0.972
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization	1.000	0.999
Employees are treated fairly here regardless of race, gender, age, religion or sexual orientation	1.000	0.999
I like the people I work with at this organization	1.000	0.982
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation	1.000	0.987
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The table above shows that after three factors extracted and retained the communality are 0.999, 0.982 and 0.987 and so on. This means that 99.9% of the variance [information content] is captured by the extracted factors for some questions while the least being 55.7%.

5.11.2.2 Interpretation of the factor Analysis on organizations corporate culture and communications

Table 5.87 Interpretation of the factor Analysis on organizations corporate culture and communications in Banking Sector: Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	8.621	66.312	66.312	8.621	66.312	66.312
2	1.876	14.428	80.740	1.876	14.428	80.740
3	1.130	8.689	89.429	1.130	8.689	89.429

4	.765	5.886	95.315			
5	.566	4.357	99.672			
6	.043	.328	100.000			
7	1.008E-013	1.062E-013	100.000			
8	1.001E-013	1.008E-013	100.000			
9	1.000E-013	1.003E-013	100.000			
10	-1.000E-013	-1.001E-013	100.000			
11	-1.001E-013	-1.007E-013	100.000			
12	-1.001E-013	-1.010E-013	100.000			
13	-1.003E-013	-1.026E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

The output of factor analysis is obtained by requesting Principal Component Analysis and specifying a rotation. The first step in interpreting the result deals with factors extracted their Eigen values and the cumulative percentage of variance. From the above table it is very clear that 89.429% of variance is obtained if three factors are obtained. This is fairly good because we can have three questions considered for the factor organizational culture and communications instead of thirteen questions [89.429% of information content is retained by four factors extracted out of thirteen].

5.11.2.3 Rotated Component Matrix on organizations corporate culture and communications

Table 5.88 Rotated Component Matrix on organizations corporate culture and communications in Banking Sector			
	Component		
	1	2	3
This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough	-0.021	0.322	0.696
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough	0.187	0.930	0.264
I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially	-0.098	0.069	-0.798
I can trust what this organization tells	0.056	0.701	-0.251
This organization treats me like a person, not a number	0.798	0.583	0.144
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done	0.677	0.710	0.184
Staffing levels are adequate to provide quality products/services	0.792	0.557	0.074
Quality is a top priority with this organization	0.388	0.879	0.243

Safety is a top priority with this organization	0.980	-0.087	-0.056
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization	0.798	0.583	0.144
Employees are treated fairly here regardless of race, gender, age, religion or sexual orientation	0.798	0.583	0.144
I like the people I work with at this organization	0.388	0.879	0.243
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation	0.976	0.184	0.023
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.			
a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.			

Source: Primary

The analysis of the factor matrix is based on the loading each factor has column wise. The first factor has statements which has high loading value of 0.980. The second component has one statement which has a high loading of 0.930; the third component has one statement which has a loading of 0.696. Therefore, it can be concluded that the thirteen questions under the heading of organizations corporate culture and communication can be reduced to three statements. The questions included will be in relation to safety, frequency of corporate communication and adequacy of formal communication.

5.11.3 Analysis on individual's role in the organization

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I like the type of work that I do	119	3.00	5.00	532.00	4.4706	0.85195
I am given enough authority to make decisions I need to make	119	2.00	5.00	504.00	4.2353	1.26696
I believe my job is secure Deadlines at this organization are realistic	119	2.00	4.00	406.00	3.4118	0.91514
I feel I am valued in this organization	119	3.00	4.00	448.00	3.7647	0.42598
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal	119	2.00	5.00	490.00	4.1176	1.37272

I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life	119	1.00	5.00	427.00	3.5882	1.14545
My job makes good use of my skills and abilities	119	2.00	5.00	504.00	4.2353	1.26696
I have a clear understanding of my job role	119	2.00	4.00	413.00	3.4706	0.85195
Valid N (listwise)	119					

Source: Primary

Majority of the banking employees enjoy the type of work they are doing. The rank obtained for this statement is as high as 4.4706. Today the nature of bank jobs is changing. The regular mundane work is taken over by the machines and employees need to use their creativity to deal with situations in the banks. The least ranking is obtained for the statement related to deadlines being realistic for which the rank is 3.4118. Targets are given in the banking job and employees work in pressure.

5.11.3.1 Analysis on communalities Individual's role in the organization

Table 5.90 Communalities Individual's role in the organization Communalities in Banking Sector		
	Initial	Extraction
I like the type of work that I do	1.000	1.000
I am given enough authority to make decisions I need to make	1.000	0.990
I believe my job is secure. Deadlines at this organization are realistic	1.000	0.938
I feel I am valued in this organization	1.000	0.920
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal	1.000	0.938
I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life	1.000	0.015
My job makes good use of my skills and abilities	1.000	0.990
I have a clear understanding of my job role	1.000	1.000
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The communalities values range from 1.000 which is the highest to a value 0.015 which is the least. This tells that after one factor is extracted and retained from the heading 'Your role in this organization' the information content captured by these variables is almost equal to 1.00, 0.990so on till 0.015 which is the least.

5.11.3.2 Analysis on Individual's role in the organization

Table 5.91 Individual's role in the organization in Banking Sector: Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.790	84.872	84.872	6.790	84.872	84.872
2	0.989	12.362	97.234			
3	0.221	2.766	100.000			
4	1.002E-013	1.026E-013	100.000			
5	1.001E-013	1.008E-013	100.000			
6	1.000E-013	1.005E-013	100.000			
7	-1.002E-013	-1.021E-013	100.000			
8	-1.004E-013	-1.044E-013	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Source: Primary

This factor matrix gives an indication that 84.872% of the total variance is contained in the one factor extracted from the seven questions which are considered for the concept of your role in the organization.

5.11.3.3 Rotated Component Matrix on Individual's role in the organization

Table 5.92 Rotated Component Matrix on Individual's role in the organization	
	Component-1
I like the type of work that I do	1.000
I am given enough authority to make decisions I need to make	0.995
I believe my job is secure Deadlines at this organization are realistic	0.969
I feel I am valued in this organization	0.959
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal	0.969
I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life	-0.122
My job makes good use of my skills and abilities	0.995
I have a clear understanding of my job role	1.000

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

a. 1 components extracted.

Source: Primary

The factor matrix indicates all variables having a high loading of 1.000 for the first factor. These variables can be grouped together into a single variable ‘I like the work I do’ as factor 1. Therefore, one question can be asked in the place of eight questions.

5.11.4 Analysis on Work Environment

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My physical working conditions are good	119	1.00	4.00	329.00	2.7647	0.64710
My general work area is adequately lit	119	2.00	4.00	434.00	3.6471	0.59072
My general work area is adequately heated/cooled	119	1.00	4.00	399.00	3.3529	1.02996
My general work area is adequately clean	119	2.00	5.00	427.00	3.5882	0.91514
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work	119	2.00	4.00	420.00	3.5294	0.85195
I feel physically safe in my work environment	119	2.00	4.00	413.00	3.4706	0.85195
Valid N (listwise)	119					

Source: Primary

The statement relating to lighting of the work area scores the highest ranking with a value of 3.64 and the least value is scored by the statement relating to the physical work area being good. In general, private sector banks are known to have a good ambience of their work environment. In Mangalore the employees are not satisfied with the work environment when compared with other branches in the metro cities.

5.11.4.1 Analysis on communalities on work environment

	Initial	Extraction
My physical working conditions are good	1.000	0.794
My general work area is adequately lit	1.000	0.916
My general work area is adequately heated/cooled	1.000	0.956
My general work area is adequately clean	1.000	0.905
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work	1.000	0.966
I feel physically safe in my work environment	1.000	0.999
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

Communalities values from 0.999 to 0.794. The two variables extracted on the factor ‘Your work environment’ gives a cumulative percentage of 92.246% and individual commonalties is as shown in the above table 5.94.

5.11.4.2 Analysis on communalities on work environment

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.120	68.659	68.659	4.120	68.659	68.659
2	1.415	23.588	92.246	1.415	23.588	92.246
3	0.465	7.754	100.000			
4	1.002E-013	1.042E-013	100.000			
5	1.000E-013	1.001E-013	100.000			
6	-1.001E-013	-1.022E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

The six questions related to working condition can be reduced to two. These two questions can capture 92.246% of information content of all questions put together. It is necessary to consider those questions whose Eigen values are one and more than one.

5.11.4.3 Analysis of Rotated Component Matrix on work environment

	Component	
	1	2
My physical working conditions are good	-0.088	0.887
My general work area is adequately lit	0.907	-0.306
My general work area is adequately heated/cooled	0.962	-0.172
My general work area is adequately clean	0.731	0.609
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work	0.880	0.438
I feel physically safe in my work environment	0.974	0.223

Source: Primary

The two questions for the factor working conditions are related to the general temperature of the working area and the overall working condition of the organization.

5.11.5 Analysis on Relationships with supervisor

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My supervisor treats me fairly	119	1.00	3.00	315.00	2.6471	0.59072
My supervisor treats me with respect	119	2.00	3.00	329.00	2.7647	0.42598
My supervisor handles my work-related issues satisfactorily	119	2.00	4.00	252.00	2.1176	0.47258
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily	119	1.00	4.00	399.00	3.3529	1.02996
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well	119	2.00	4.00	350.00	2.9412	0.72829
My supervisor tells me when my work needs	119	2.00	4.00	350.00	2.9412	0.72829
My supervisor is open to hearing my opinion or feedback	119	2.00	4.00	308.00	2.5882	0.91514
My supervisor helps me develop to my fullest potential	119	2.00	4.00	343.00	2.8824	0.58479

I can trust what my supervisor tells me	119	2.00	5.00	350.00	2.9412	0.72829
Valid N (list wise)	119					

Source: Primary

Based on the ranking on superiors it is seen that the question related to whether the supervisor's handles work related issues satisfactorily gets the least ranking, while the question relating to supervisors handling personal issues gets a high score. This shows that employees are usually friendly with one another. Superiors do not respond to the subordinate's problems immediately in the private sector. They usually want the juniors to find their own means of solving problems.

5.11.5.1 Analysis on Communalities of Factor Analysis for Relationships with supervisor

Table No 5.98 Relationships with supervisor in Banking Sector: Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
My supervisor treats me fairly	1.000	0.907
My supervisor treats me with respect	1.000	0.908
My supervisor handles my work-related issues satisfactorily	1.000	0.941
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily	1.000	0.902
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well	1.000	0.916
My supervisor tells me when my work needs	1.000	0.916
My supervisor is open to hearing my opinion or feedback	1.000	0.463
My supervisor helps me develop to my fullest potential	1.000	0.941
I can trust what my supervisor tells me	1.000	0.987
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

Communalities result for the superior and subordinate relationship shows that there are questions which have a less value of 0.463 and high value of 0.987 and the remaining have a moderately high value. The two questions which are extracted for the factor on superiors contain about 87.574 % of information for the further analysis in this sector.

5.11.5.2 Analysis on Communalities of Factor Analysis for Relationships with supervisor

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.114	56.818	56.818	5.114	56.818	56.818
2	2.768	30.756	87.574	2.768	30.756	87.574
3	.887	9.859	97.433			
4	.231	2.567	100.000			
5	1.002E-013	1.018E-013	100.000			
6	1.001E-013	1.007E-013	100.000			
7	1.000E-013	1.003E-013	100.000			
8	-1.001E-013	-1.007E-013	100.000			
9	-1.001E-013	-1.016E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

The Eigen value for two questions is greater than one which signifies that two questions can be considered for the above factor. The questions can capture 87.574% of the information content for the given factor.

5.11.5.3 Analysis on Rotated Component Matrix of Factor Analysis for Relationships with supervisor

	Component	
	1	2
My supervisor treats me fairly	0.940	-0.154
My supervisor treats me with respect	0.682	0.666
My supervisor handles my work-related issues satisfactorily	-0.560	0.792
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily	0.950	0.006
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well	0.942	0.173
My supervisor tells me when my work needs	0.942	0.173
My supervisor is open to hearing my opinion or feedback	0.650	0.202
My supervisor helps me develop to my fullest potential	0.329	0.913
I can trust what my supervisor tells me	0.083	0.990

Source: Primary

The questions which can be considered for the variable ‘relationship with superiors’ are regarding acknowledgement of supervisors for work well done and supervisors consideration in telling what work should be done and handling of personal issues. The other question is regarding the trust worthiness of the superior. Therefore, two questions can be considered instead of nine components.

5.11.6 Analysis on organizational training and development

Table 5.101 Analysis on organizational training and development: Descriptive Statistics						
	N	Mini mum	Maxi mum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed	119	2.00	5.00	427.00	3.5882	0.91514
This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need	119	2.00	5.00	378.00	3.1765	0.86011
Provides enough information, equipment and resources	119	2.00	4.00	357.00	3.0000	0.77021
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement	119	3.00	4.00	392.00	3.2941	0.45757
I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career	119	2.00	4.00	434.00	3.6471	0.59072
This organization provides training or experiences to help me explore other possible opportunities within the company	119	2.00	4.00	371.00	3.1176	0.47258
There is room for me to advance at this organization	119	2.00	4.00	434.00	3.6471	0.68381
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay	119	1.00	4.00	350.00	2.9412	0.64169
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion	119	1.00	4.00	350.00	2.9412	0.64169
Valid N (listwise)	119					

Source: Primary

The least ranking is related to a question regarding linking of pay and good work and also the question related to promotion. In most of the organizations the pay is directly not linked to performance. Also, it is seen that there is no immediate acknowledgement for the ones who do good work. At the same time, it is observed that organizations do consider the career of individuals in the banking sector and also gives people the scope to develop their potential for career advancement.

5.11.6.1 Analysis on Communalities of factor analysis for the factor organizational training and development

Table 5.102 Communalities of factor analysis for the factor organizational training and development in Banking Sector		
	Initial	Extraction
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed	1.000	0.734
This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need	1.000	0.950
Provides enough information, equipment and resources	1.000	0.738
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement	1.000	0.931
I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career	1.000	0.885
This organization provides training or experiences to help me explore other possible opportunities within the company	1.000	0.400
There is room for me to advance at this organization	1.000	0.684
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay	1.000	0.909
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion	1.000	0.909
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The communalities values range from 0.950 to 0.440. These values are quite good. Most of the information is captured by the Principal component analysis. The extraction leads to three questions which can get all the information needed for the factor related to training and development.

5.11.6.2 Analysis on total variance of factor analysis for the factor organizational training and development

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.345	48.281	48.281	4.345	48.281	48.281
2	1.743	19.369	67.650	1.743	19.369	67.650
3	1.052	11.689	79.339	1.052	11.689	79.339
4	0.826	9.176	88.515			
5	0.659	7.320	95.834			
6	0.371	4.126	99.960			
7	0.004	0.040	100.000			
8	1.001E-013	1.006E-013	100.000			
9	-1.000E-013	-1.004E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

Three questions have an Eigen value of more than one which is an indication that these can be questions which can be considered for the factor ‘training and development’. It is also seen that these three questions can capture 79.339% of information needed for the above-mentioned factor.

5.11.6.3 Analysis on Rotated Component Matrix of factor analysis for the factor organizational training and development

	Component		
	1	2	3
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed	0.509	0.313	0.614
This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need	0.489	0.611	0.582
This Organization provides enough information, equipment and resources	0.131	0.315	0.788
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement	0.191	0.927	0.186
I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career	-0.328	-0.878	-0.084

This organization provides training or experiences to help me explore other possible opportunities within the company	-0.190	0.584	0.153
There is room for me to advance at this organization	0.570	0.182	-0.571
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay	0.940	0.065	0.146
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion	0.940	0.065	0.146
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.			
a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.			

Source: Primary

The three questions which can be distinctively asked for the factor ‘Training and Development’ are the one related good work and pay and promotion; identifying what is expected from individuals in terms of advancement, providing adequate initial training for employees in the company and consideration and providing enough information on equipment and other recourses.

5.11.7 Analysis on the factor Pay and benefits

	N	Mini mum	Maxi mum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)	119	2.00	5.00	434.00	3.6471	0.76566
Sick leave policy	119	2.00	4.00	364.00	3.0588	0.72829
Retirement plan benefits	119	1.00	4.00	343.00	2.8824	0.67869
Life insurance benefits	119	2.00	5.00	343.00	2.8824	0.76109
Tuition reimbursement benefits	119	2.00	5.00	329.00	2.7647	0.73307
My pay is fair for the work I perform	119	2.00	5.00	343.00	2.8824	0.76109
Valid N (listwise)	119					

Source: Primary

Respondents in the banking sector do not have any complaint towards the amount of vacation given to them but they are not happy with the tuition reimbursement and retirement plans the organization is offering them. The private sector banks pay the employee quite well, but most of them compare themselves to the public sector banks when payments are considered. Most of the

private sector banks don't pay separate tuition fee and they don't plan for the retirement of their employees.

5.11.7.1 Analysis on communalities of factor analysis for the factor Pay and benefits

	Initial	Extraction
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)	1.000	0.932
Sick leave policy	1.000	0.924
Retirement plan benefits	1.000	0.466
Life insurance benefits	1.000	0.947
Tuition reimbursement benefits	1.000	0.940
My pay is fair for the work I perform	1.000	0.947
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The communalities are quite high except for one value relating to retirement benefits. Therefore, it can be agreed that two questions are enough to draw conclusions regarding pay and benefits in the organization.

5.11.7.2 Analysis on Total variance of factor analysis for the factor Pay and benefits

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.740	62.334	62.334	3.740	62.334	62.334
2	1.417	23.621	85.955	1.417	23.621	85.955
3	0.699	11.655	97.610			
4	0.090	1.501	99.111			
5	0.053	0.889	100.000			
6	-1.001E-013	-1.014E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

The Eigen values of two variables are greater than one and these two questions can capture around 85.955% of information regarding the factor of pay and benefits. The method of elimination suffices with two questions for pay and benefits. The two questions can generate

nearly 85.955% of the information contained in the six questions which are there in the questionnaire.

5.11.7.3 Analysis on Rotated compound Matrix of factor analysis for the factor Pay and benefits

	Component	
	1	2
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)	-0.056	0.964
Sick leave policy	0.896	-0.349
Retirement plan benefits	-0.457	-0.507
Life insurance benefits	0.961	0.153
Tuition reimbursement benefits	0.862	0.443
My pay is fair for the work I perform	0.961	0.153
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.		
a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.		

Source: Primary

The two questions that can be extracted include the one which relates to Life insurance benefits and the other which includes a question on vacations. Apart from this, a question on fairness of pay can be used to get insights into the factors concerning pay and benefits.

5.12 FACTOR ANALYSIS a very useful tool is used to reduce data complexity by reducing the number of variables being used. In this study factor analysis is used to identify decision makers identify what exactly makes employees engaged in the organization where they are working. The table below summaries the number of questions before and after factor analysis for the relevant parameters considered

Parameter	Number Of questions Before Factor Analysis	Number of Questions After Factor Analysis
Organizations Leadership and Planning	8	2
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	13	3
Individual role at the organization	8	1
Work Environment	6	2

Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	9	2
Training and Development	9	3
Pay and Benefits	6	2
Total	49	15

Source: Primary

The questionnaire drafted after factor analysis is annexed for Banking sector (Annexure 2(b)).

Table 5.110 Questions to be considered after factor analysis in Banking Sector	
Parameters	1. Questions After factor reduction.
Organizations Leadership and Planning	2. There is adequate planning and follow up of departmental objectives.
	3. I have confidence in the leadership of this organization.
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	1 Safety is a top priority with this organization.
	2 This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough.
	3 This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough.
Individual role at the organization	1 I like the work I do.
Work Environment	1 My physical working conditions are good.
	2 My general work area is adequately heated /cooled.
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	1 I can trust what my supervisor tells me.
	2 My supervisor tells me when my work needs to be done.
Training and Development	1 This Organization provides enough information, equipment and recourses
	2 My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement
	3 I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion and pay
Pay and Benefits	1 Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)
	2 My pay is fair for the work I perform

Source: Primary

The above table is the factor reduction table with the parameter and the likely questions that can be asked to elicit the same kind of response. The detailed questionnaire need not be used for further study on employee engagement in the service sector in particular to the banking sector.

Fig 5.15 Factors of Engagement for Banking Sector - Saks model

The above diagrammatic representation shows employee engagement is an outcome of organizational elements, group elements and individual elements. These elements are considered in the factor analysis and the study identifies the most important factor and the least important factor. Apart from the individual elements certain personal factors also contribute to employee engagement. This can be represented in a diagrammatic representation as below.

Fig 5.16 Individual factors of employee engagement in Banking Sector - Saks model

The above factors contribution towards employee engagement is estimated using the discriminant analysis and also the methods of correlation and regression.

5.13 DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS FOR CLASSIFICATION AND PREDICTION

Discriminant Analysis is used to classify objects into two or more groups based on the knowledge of some variable {Characteristics} related to the. Typically, these groupings would be user/nonuser, engaged /disengaged high risk/low risk etc. The form of equation in a three variable discriminant analysis is

$$Y=a+K_1X_1+K_2X_2+K_3X_3$$

Where Y is the dependent variable and X₁, X₂ and X₃ are independent variables. K₁ K₂ and K₃ are constant and coefficients.

Y is a classification into two or more groupings and therefore known as a grouping variable. Groups are formed on the basis of the existing data and coded as 1 and 2. The independent variable are continuous scale variables and used as predictors of group to which the objects belong.

Then a model is built which is a linear form and uses the coefficients of the equation to calculate the Y discriminant score. For any new data points that we want to classify into one of the groups. A decision rule is formulated for this purpose to determine the cutoff score, which is usually the midpoint of the mean discriminant scores of the two groups.

Table 5.111 Wilks' Lambda value for strength of the Discriminant function.				
Test of Function(s)	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	0.763	31.078	4	0.000

Source: Primary

The statistical significance of the discriminant function is answered by looking at the Wilks Lambda and the probability value of the test given above. The value of Wilks Lambda is 0.763. This value is in between 0 to 1 and a low value indicates better discriminating power. Thus, a value 0.763 is an indicator that the model is a good fit. Also, the probability value of F-Test

indicates that discriminating between the two groups is highly significant. This is because the significant value is 00 which means that F test is significant to a confidence level of up to 100%.

Table 5.112 Best Predictor in Banking Sector: Structure Matrix	
	Function-1
Age	0.881
Salary	0.787
How long have you worked for this organization?	0.726
Gender	0.277
Pooled within-groups correlations between discriminating variables and standardized canonical discriminant functions Variables ordered by absolute size of correlation within function.	

Source: Primary

Better predictor: There are four independent variables namely Age, Salary, Length of service and Gender. From the output table of standardized canonical discriminant functions co-efficient and structure Matrix table it is observed that age is the best predictor followed by salary then followed by length of service and the last factor is gender. The absolute value of the standardized coefficient of each independent variable indicates its relative importance.

Table 5.113 Canonical Discriminant Function Coefficients in Banking Sector	
	Function-1
How long have you worked for this organization?	-0.135
Gender	1.406
Age	0.073
Salary	0.000077
(Constant)	-6.282
Unstandardized coefficients	

Source: Primary

In order to compute the discriminant score for engagement the following discriminant function has to be used.

$$Y = a + K_1X_1 + K_2X_2 + K_3X_3 + K_4X_4$$

$$Y = -6.282 - 0.135X_1 + 1.406X_2 + 0.073X_3 + 0.000077X_4 \text{ [Calculated values Annexed]}$$

Where Y is the dependent variable [Engagement], -6.282 is the constant and the respective coefficients are -0.135, 1.406, 0.073, 0.000077 for length of service, gender, age, salary respectively.

Table 5.114 Functions at Group Centroids: Cut off values for Engagement	
Engaged	Function-1
Engaged	0.342
Disengaged	-0.892
Unstandardized canonical discriminant functions evaluated at group means	

Source: Primary

The means of canonical variables, gives us the new means for the transformed group centroids. Thus, the new mean for engaged is 0.342 and the new mean for group disengaged is -0.892. This indicates that the midpoint of these two values is -0.275. This is clear with the diagram below.

This also helps in the decision rule for classifying any new case. If the discriminant score of an applicant falls to the right of the midpoint we classify as engaged and if it falls to the left it is classified as disengaged.

Table 5.115 Classification Results in Banking Sector					
		Engaged	Predicted Group Membership		Total
			Engaged	Disengaged	
Original	Count	Engaged	64	22	86
		Disengaged	1	32	33
	%	Engaged	74.4	25.6	100.0
		Disengaged	3.0	97.0	100.0
a. 80.7% of original grouped cases correctly classified.					

Source: Primary

The above output table is called the classification matrix or also known as the confusion matrix. It indicates that the discriminant function that is obtained is able to classify 80.7% of the original data to be grouped and classified correctly.

5.13.1 Correlation and Regression analysis taking individual independent variables

The regression analysis is judged for its usefulness based on the

1. Overall F-Test for the model. If this is significant say at 95% then the model is a good fit. This shows up as a significant value in the model summary [which should be less than 0.05].
2. The R square value of the model tells the percentage of variation in the dependent variable explained by the independent variable.

Table 5.116 Model Summary and Parameter Estimates for Length of service in Banking Sector							
Dependent Variable: Discriminant Scores from Function 1 for Analysis 1							
Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.594	170.972	1	117	0.000	-0.696	0.110
The independent variable is How long have you worked for this organization?							

Source: Primary

The linear model is a good fit between employee engagement and years of working in the organization. The F test shows that the model is significant. The R square value is 59.4% which denotes the variation in employee engagement explained by the independent factor length of service in the organization. The Regression equation can be written in the form

$$Y=a+bX_1$$

$$Y= -0.696 + 0.110 X_1$$

Table 5.117 Model Summary and Parameter Estimates for Gender in Banking Sector							
Dependent Variable: Discriminant Scores from Function 1 for Analysis 1							
Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.098	12.773	1	117	0.001	-1.011	0.782
The independent variable is Gender.							

Source: Primary

The linear model is a good fit between employee engagement and gender. The F test shows that the model is significant. The R square value is 9.8% which denotes the variation in employee

engagement explained by the independent factor length of stay in the organization. The Regression equation can be written in the form.

$$Y=a+bX_1$$

$$Y=- 1.011+ 0.782X_1$$

Table 5.118 Model Summary and Parameter Estimates for Age in Banking Sector							
Dependent Variable: Discriminant Scores from Function 1 for Analysis 1							
Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.820	532.184	1	117	0.000	-3.500	0.110
The independent variable is Age.							

Source: Primary

The linear model is not a good fit between employee engagement and age. The F test shows that the model is significant. The R square value is 82% which denotes the variation in employee engagement explained by the independent factor age. The Regression equation can be written in the form

$$Y=a+bX_1$$

$$Y=- 3.5+ 0.110X_1$$

Table 5.119 Model Summary and Parameter Estimates for Salary in Banking Sector							
Dependent Variable: Discriminant Scores from Function 1 for Analysis 1							
Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.681	249.231	1	117	0.000	-2.018	5.179E-005
The independent variable is Salary.							

Source: Primary

The linear model is a good fit between employee engagement and salary. The F test shows that the model is significant. The R square value is 68.1% which denotes the variation in employee engagement explained by the independent factor salary. The Regression equation can be written in the form

$$Y=a+bX_1$$

$$Y=-2.108+ 0.00005179 X_1$$

The graphical representation of the linear regression equation is shown in the fig 5.17.

Fig 5.17 Diagrammatic representation for the various individual factors affecting employee Engagement in Banking Sector

Section C: Analysis for the Education Sector

Mangalore is a hub of education. There are a number of education institutions which offer the undergraduate course. The analysis deals with private sector employees mostly teaching undergraduate courses. The courses include all streams of study in the undergraduate level namely commerce, arts and science. The study aims to find out the engagement levels in this sector and engaged faculty members can make a difference in the organization. In the education sector innovation, differentiation and high performance has become a universal requirement. Improved engagement levels can lead to high performance. The total number of respondents in the education sector is 133. These are the respondents who have given complete response to all the questions in the questionnaire. Therefore, care has been taken to eliminate missing values and get the most accurate responses.

5.14 CAUSAL FACTORS AFFECTING EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN THE EDUCATION SECTOR

5.14.1 Based on Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	69	51.9	51.9	51.9
	Female	64	48.1	48.1	100.0
	Total	133	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary

The number of female responses is 48.1% which is almost equal to the number of male employees. This is a general indication that the number of female workers in the education sector is almost the same as men in the city of Mangalore. The education sector seems to be having the same number of male and female work force in the category of lecturer, assistant professor and associate professor. But the number of women is lesser in the senior academic positions. Today this profession is gaining importance and most of them are there because they have a passion for teaching. Also, it is seen that many of them are pursuing higher education and keeping themselves updated.

Count		Engaged		Total
		Engaged	Disengaged	
Gender	Male	38	31	69
	Female	53	11	64
Total		91	42	133

Source: Primary

The attribute Gender affects the engagement levels in the education sector. The distinction in the engagement levels cannot be seen as clearly as in the insurance sector. Comparatively women seem to be more engaged in this sector also. Women usually do the routine work in the colleges and keep them updated with the students. But when it comes to research and publication the contribution is lesser with respect to women, whereas the male counterparts have more contribution towards research and publication.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.825^a	1	0.001		
Continuity Correction ^b	10.576	1	0.001		
Likelihood Ratio	12.217	1	0.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				0.001	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	11.736	1	0.001		
N of Valid Cases	133				

Source: Primary

The chi-square test reveals that there is an association between gender and employee engagement. The teaching job has been suitable to women predominantly. This is a profession which has a relatively lesser salary when compared to other professions. It is usually the love for the profession which has made faculty to remain in this profession.

		Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	0.286			0.001
N of Valid Cases		133			

Source: Primary

The above contingency coefficient infers the association between the two variables gender and engagement. The value of this is 0.286 which shows that there is a weak association between the two variables gender and engagement. A value close to 0 means there does not exist any association and a value close to one shows a strong association between the two variables.

Lambda is the measure of reduction in error in measuring the association between the two variables. The value of Lambda is 0.142 which means 14.2% error reduction. This is a moderate low value leading to 14.2% reduction in error in estimating or predicting one variable from the other.

5.14.2 Based on Age

Table 5.124 Profile on the basis age in education sector		
Age		
N	Valid	133
	Missing	0
Mean		32.2105
Median		28.0000
Mode		24.00
Std. Deviation		10.65083
Range		32.00
Minimum		24.00
Maximum		56.00

Source: Primary

The mean age of workforce in the education sector is 32.2 years. The modal age is 24 years. The minimum age is 24 years and maximum age is 56 years. The sector has shown that employees have a wider range of age and the spread of the age in terms of standard deviation is also high. Since the average age is around 32 years the faculty are keeping up with technological changes and continuing their education too. Young staff and faculty many face many challenges in academics but they will connect better with the student crowd.

Count		Engaged		Total
		Engaged	Disengaged	
Age	24.00	14	28	42
	26.00	14	7	21
	28.00	7	0	7
	29.00	21	0	21
	31.00	0	7	7
	39.00	7	0	7
	47.00	14	0	14
	55.00	7	0	7
	56.00	7	0	7
Total		91	42	133

Source: Primary

The above is a cross tabulation of age with engagement score. It gives a clear understanding of respondent's engagement levels with the age factor considered. A chi-square test is performed to understand the significant association between the two Variables namely engagement and age factor. Freshers in the education field usually face a lot of challenge in the profession. Knowledge enhancement and transfer of this knowledge to the students is very important. Youngsters in the beginning of the teaching profession are disengaged.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	68.205^a	8	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	85.691	8	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	24.367	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	133		

Source: Primary

The chi-square test reveals a significant association between the two variables that is Engagement level and age. From the test output it is seen that the significant level is 0.000. This means that Chi-square test is showing a significant association of 100% between the two variables. In the education sector it is clearly evident that as age progresses the engagement levels also increases. Usually individuals start with the teaching career and continue with the

same and very few people will change their profession from teaching to industry. Individuals from the industry shift to the teaching profession towards the latter part of their life. Therefore, engagement levels are high as the age increases.

			Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	0.211	0.072	2.718	0.007
		Age Dependent	0.077	0.062	1.189	0.234
		Engaged Dependent	0.500	0.118	3.107	0.002

Source: Primary

Lambda is the measure of reduction in error in measuring the association between the two variables. From the table the value of Lambda is 0.211 which means 21.1% error reduction. This is a moderate low value leading to 21.1% reduction in error in estimating or predicting one variable from the other.

		Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	0.582			0.000

Source: Primary

The contingency coefficient of 0.582 infers that the association between the dependent and independent variable is significant as it is closer to 1 than to 0. This coefficient gives the measure of strength of the output. If the value is close to 0, then there does not exist any strong correlation between the two variables. However, if the value lies in between 0.5 to 1, there exists a strong relationship. Here from the above table it is clearly seen that there is a strong association between age and engagement level. Engagement is less at a younger age.

5.14.3 Based on length of service

How long have you worked for this organization?		
N	Valid	133
	Missing	0

Mean	6.0316
Median	3.0000
Mode	1.00
Std. Deviation	7.13187
Range	25.00
Minimum	1.00
Maximum	26.00
Sum	802.20

Source: Primary

The above table shows that the average of length of service is 6.0316 years which is quite high when compared to any other sector. Employees stick on to their job for a longer period even though the modal value is one. The modal value one indicates that majority people have one year of experience in the sampled respondents. 73.7% of employees have five years of experience in the education sector. The five years of experience for most of them is in the same organization. The job satisfaction attribute makes employees to stay back in the same sector and organization. They enjoy their work and are happy with the facilities provided. It can also be understood that the teaching profession is less stressful when compared to the other sectors.

Table 5.130 Chi-Square Tests Length of service* Engaged employees in education sector			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	73.605 ^a	9	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	93.017	9	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	18.655	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	133		

Source: Primary

The chi-square test shows that there is a significant association between length of service and the engagement levels. The result shows that there is 100% association between the dependent and independent variable. As the length of service increases the engagement level also increases. Employees stick on to the teaching profession for a longer period of time. From the sample respondents it is also seen that many teaching professionals have also stuck on to the same organization.

Table 5.131 Chi-Square Tests Directional Measures Length of service* Engaged employees in education sector					
			Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	0.211	0.072	2.718
		How long have you worked for this organization? Dependent	0.077	0.062	1.189
		Engaged Dependent	0.500	0.118	3.107

Source: Primary

Lambda is the measure of reduction in error in measuring the association between the two variables. From the table the value of Lambda is 0.211 which means 21.1% error reduction. This is a moderate low value leading to 21.1% reduction in error in estimating or predicting one variable from the other. Length of service can be used to predict engagement levels.

Table 5.132 Chi-Square Tests Symmetric Measures Length of service* Engaged employees in education sector					
		Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	0.597			0.000
N of Valid Cases		133			

Source: Primary

The contingency coefficient value of 59.7% supports that there is a strong association between the two variables. The value can lie between 0 and 1. As the value is closer to 1 rather than 0 it can be concluded that the association is strong between the two variables. Length of service has a strong association with employee engagement levels in the teaching professionals.

5.14.4 Based on Salary

Table 5.133 Salary levels of the Respondents in education sector					
Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Salary	133	20000.00	60000.00	33578.9474	12212.89093
Valid N (list wise)	133				

Source: Primary

Salary ranges in the teaching profession is less compared to the banking sector. The minimum salary is Rs 20000 and the Maximum salary is around Rs 60000. The average salary is Rs 33579. The salary levels in the private sector are increasing but many of them do not follow norms and regulations of the regulatory authority. Teaching professionals do not get any additional benefits and perks as in the other professions. But colleges help in the additional skill and knowledge development of the professors.

Table 5.134 Chi-Square Tests Salary * Engaged employees in education sector			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	72.525^a	10	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	92.048	10	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	44.618	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	133		

Source: Primary

Salary and engagement are two factors which are associated. The Chi-Square test is applied and it is identified that there is a significant association between the two factors. Salary is a prime determinant to any individual's commitment to his/her job. The compensation package should be well defined and it should motivate individuals to achieve the best returns in terms of monetary benefits.

Table 5.135 Chi-Square Tests Directional Measures Salary * Engaged employees in education sector					
			Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	0.150	0.051	0.007
		Salary Dependent	0.000	0.000	
		Engaged Dependent	0.500	0.134	0.007
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Salary Dependent	0.074	0.011	0.000 ^d
		Engaged Dependent	0.545	0.053	0.000 ^d

Source: Primary

Lambda is the measure of reduction in error in measuring the association between the two variables. From the table the value of Lambda is 0.150 which means 15% error reduction. This is

a moderate low value leading to 15% reduction in error in estimating or predicting one variable from the other.

Table 5.136 Chi-Square Tests Symmetric Measures salary * Engaged employees in education sector			
		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0.738	0.000
	Cramer's V	0.738	0.000
	Contingency Coefficient	0.594	0.000
N of Valid Cases		133	

Source: Primary

The contingency coefficient value of 59.4% supports that there is a strong association between the two variables. The value can lie between 0 and 1. As the value is closer to 1 rather than 0 it can be concluded that the association is strong between the two variables.

5.15 ENGAGED WORKFORCE IN THE EDUCATION SECTOR

Table 5.137 Number of Engaged workforces in education sector					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Engaged	91	68.4	68.4	68.4
	Disengaged	42	31.6	31.6	100.0
	Total	133	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary

The education sector has 68.4% of workforce who are engaged. This is an indication of workforce being highly motivated to work in the sector. Only 31.6 % of human resources in the sector are disengaged. This is an indication that employees are happy with their work life and also seems to be enjoying the job. The teaching profession is an evergreen profession. Though it may not fetch huge financial benefits people come to this profession out of passion. Private educational organizations are increasing the work load of their staff and expecting much more than teaching. Many of them have become deemed, autonomous and private universities which, demand administrative, teaching and research work from the faculty working for them. Also, these universities follow the cost cutting strategy.

Fig 5.18 Engaged workforce in the Education Sector.

Source: Primary

5.16 EMPLOYEES PLANNING TO STAY IN THE SAME COMPANY FOR MORE THAN TWO YEARS IN EDUCATION SECTOR

Table 5.138 Employees planning to stay in the same company for more than two years

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree strongly	7	5.3	5.3	5.3
	Disagree somewhat	28	21.1	21.1	26.3
	Neutral	57	42.9	42.9	69.2
	Agree Somewhat	34	25.6	25.6	94.7
	Agree strongly	7	5.3	5.3	100.0
	Total	133	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary

42.9% of respondents are neutral about their future in the organizations while 5.3% are definite that they are going to stay back in the same organization. 25.6 % of employees agree that they will remain in the same organization. This shows that the respondents are not only committed to their job but also committed to their organization. Mangalore is an educational hub. More and more educational institutes are originating in this place and employees have lateral movement for better prospective. The private colleges too need to keep in pace with the technological advancements and progress with time.

Source: Primary

5.16.1 Employees recommend company's product

Table 5.139 Employees Recommend company's product in education sector

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree strongly	42	31.6	31.6	31.6
	Disagree somewhat	21	15.8	15.8	47.4
	Neutral	7	5.3	5.3	52.6
	Agree Somewhat	63	47.4	47.4	100.0
	Total	133	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary

About 47.4 % of employees recommend their college and course to their friends and relatives. This shows that they are convinced by the teaching methods and proud to be associated with the organizations they are working for. Today basic science and commerce subjects are gaining importance. Mangalore is known for its quality education. People from neighboring states and district prefer Mangalore for higher education. Most of the respondents interviewed are from prestigious colleges and hence recommend their courses and colleges to friends and relatives.

Fig 5.20 Recommend your college and university to friends and relatives

5.16.2 Employees would recommend employment opportunity in their company to a friend

Table 5.140 Employees would recommend employment opportunity in their company to a friend in education sector					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree somewhat	7	5.3	5.3	5.3
	Neutral	28	21.1	21.1	26.3
	Agree strongly	98	73.7	73.7	100.0
	Total	133	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary

73.7% of employees recommend their place of work for job opportunities to their friend's. This shows that employees are happy with the environment in the education sector. They are also satisfied with the job and recommend the same to others. Colleges are opening new courses and increasing their intake. To keep in pace with their growth strategy the number of employees required is also increasing. Thus, the present employees have a chance for referral recruitment.

Source: Primary

5.17 OVERALL SATISFACTION OF RESPONDENTS ON THE ORGANIZATIONAL ASPECTS IN EDUCATION SECTOR

Table 5.141 Overall satisfaction of respondents on the organizational aspects						
	N	Mini mum	Maxi mum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Overall satisfaction with this organization as an employee	133	1.00	4.00	442.00	3.3233	0.96569
Overall, I am happy with the organizational culture and communication	133	2.00	4.00	434.00	3.2632	0.96840
Overall, I am happy with the leadership and Planning in the organization	133	1.00	5.00	420.00	3.1579	1.27233
I understand the importance of my role to the success of the organization	133	2.00	5.00	553.00	4.1579	1.31335
Overall the work environment is good	133	1.00	4.00	406.00	3.0526	1.15020
Overall the superior subordinate relationship is good	133	2.00	5.00	427.00	3.2105	0.61610
Overall Training and	133	2.00	4.00	455.00	3.4211	0.59302

development is good in the organization						
Overall, I'm satisfied with this organization's benefits package	133	2.00	3.00	364.00	2.7368	0.44201
Valid N (list wise)	133					

Source: Primary

Overall satisfaction has a value of 3.3233 which is less and shows that employees are in a category of neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. In particular it can be seen that each individual understands their role in the organization and has a value of 4.1579. The least satisfaction is regarding the organizational benefit package which has a value of 2.7368 and the dispersion value that is standard deviation is also the least with 0.44201. This is an indicator that majority of respondents are not happy with the pay benefits they receive from their company. The teaching staff understands their role as a teacher, mentor and Role model to the students. For the success of any college or university the faculties are the pillars.

Source: Primary

5.17.1 Analysis on organizations leadership and planning in the Education sector

Table 5.142 Descriptive Statistics Analysis on organizations leadership and planning						
	N	Mini mum	Maxi mum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I understand the long-term strategy of this organization	133	2.00	4.00	420.00	3.1579	0.87769
There is adequate planning of corporate objectives	133	1.00	5.00	427.00	3.2105	1.10818
There is adequate planning of departmental objectives	133	2.00	4.00	497.00	3.7368	0.54903
There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives	133	1.00	4.00	413.00	3.1053	1.02442
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.	133	2.00	5.00	497.00	3.7368	0.78716
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization	133	1.00	5.00	364.00	2.7368	1.16707
The leaders of this organization care about their employees' well being	133	2.00	4.00	469.00	3.5263	0.68067
The leaders of this organization are open to input from employees	133	2.00	5.00	413.00	3.1053	0.79070
Valid N (list wise)	133					

Source: Primary

This above table under the heading of organizational leadership and planning reveals that majority of respondents are happy with the departmental planning and follow through whereas they lack confidence in the leadership of the organization.

5.17.1.1 Interpretation of the factor Analysis on organizational leadership and planning

Table 5.143 Interpretation of the factor Analysis on organizational leadership and planning in education sector: Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.503	31.285	31.285	2.503	31.285	31.285
2	1.615	20.188	51.473	1.615	20.188	51.473

3	1.335	16.684	68.158	1.335	16.684	68.158
4	0.821	10.268	78.426			
5	0.761	9.514	87.940			
6	0.433	5.407	93.347			
7	0.328	4.096	97.443			
8	0.205	2.557	100.000			

Source: Primary

The output of factor analysis is obtained by requesting Principal Component Analysis and specifying a rotation. The first step in interpreting the result deals with factors extracted their Eigen values and the cumulative percentage of variance. From the above table it is very clear that 68.158% of variance is obtained if three factors are extracted. This is fairly good because we can have three questions considered for the factor organizational leadership and planning instead of eight questions [68.158% of information content is retained by three factors extracted out of eight].

5.17.1.2 Interpretation of the Communalities of factor analysis on organizational leadership and planning

Table 5.144 Communalities of factor analysis on organizational leadership and planning		
	Initial	Extraction
I understand the long-term strategy of this organization	1.000	0.675
There is adequate planning of corporate objectives	1.000	0.740
There is adequate planning of departmental objectives	1.000	0.484
There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives	1.000	0.736
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.	1.000	0.800
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization	1.000	0.715
The leaders of this organization care about their employees' well being	1.000	0.579
The leaders of this organization are open to input from employees	1.000	0.723
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

Communality is the proportion of variance in the original variable which is captured by the extracted factor. The table above shows that after three factors extracted and retained the communality is 0.800, 0.736, 0.740 and so on. This means that 80.0% of the variance

[information content] of one of the questions is captured by the extracted factors and the least being 48.4%.

5.17.1.3 Interpretation of Rotated Component Matrix of factor analysis on organizational leadership and planning

Table 5.145 Rotated Component Matrix of factor analysis on organizational leadership and planning in education sector			
	Component		
	1	2	3
I understand the long-term strategy of this organization	0.251	0.591	0.512
There is adequate planning of corporate objectives	-0.319	0.137	0.787
There is adequate planning of departmental objectives	0.694	0.035	0.029
There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives	0.293	0.792	0.154
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.	0.854	0.205	0.172
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization	-0.085	0.811	-0.224
The leaders of this organization care about their employees' well being	0.397	-0.219	0.611
The leaders of this organization are open to input from employees	0.729	0.136	-0.415
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.			
a. Rotation converged in 11 iterations.			

Source: Primary

The analysis of the factor matrix is based on the loading each factor has column wise. The first factor has one statements which has high loading value of 0.854. The second component has one statement which has a high loading of 0.811 and the third component has one statement which has a loading of 0.78. Therefore, it can be concluded that the eight questions under the heading of organizations leadership and planning can be reduced to three statements.

5.17.2 Analysis on organizations corporate culture and communications

Table 5.146 Descriptive Statistics on organizations corporate culture and communications							
	N	Range	Mini mum	Maxi mum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
This organization's	133	3.00	2.00	5.00	385.00	2.8947	0.85514

corporate communicates are frequent enough							
This organization's corporate communicates are detailed enough	133	3.00	1.00	4.00	378.00	2.8421	1.14046
I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially	133	3.00	2.00	5.00	413.00	3.1053	1.02442
I can trust what this organization tells	133	4.00	1.00	5.00	413.00	3.1053	1.12319
This organization treats me like a person, not a number	133	3.00	1.00	4.00	378.00	2.8421	0.99119
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done	133	4.00	1.00	5.00	413.00	3.1053	1.48866
Staffing levels are adequate to provide quality products/services	133	3.00	1.00	4.00	315.00	2.3684	1.09041
Quality is a top priority with this organization	133	4.00	1.00	5.00	420.00	3.1579	1.27233
Safety is a top priority with this organization	133	3.00	2.00	5.00	399.00	3.0000	0.65134
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization	133	3.00	2.00	5.00	483.00	3.6316	0.87450
Employees are treated fairly here regardless of race, gender, age, religion or sexual orientation	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	455.00	3.4211	0.88086
I like the people I work with at this organization	133	3.00	2.00	5.00	448.00	3.3684	0.93317
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	371.00	2.7895	0.52300
Valid N (list wise)	133						

Source: Primary

Cooperation between the workers scores a high value. It has a ranking of 3.63 which is a high score amongst all other factors considered under the heading organizations corporate culture and communications. The education sector has a culture of team work to a certain extent and employees seem to be cooperating with one another.

5.17.2.1 Communalities on organizations corporate culture and communications

Table 5.147 Communalities on organizations corporate culture and communications		
	Initial	Extraction
This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough	1.000	0.771
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough	1.000	0.903
I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially	1.000	0.840
I can trust what this organization tells	1.000	0.763
This organization treats me like a person, not a number	1.000	0.806
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done	1.000	0.733
Staffing levels are adequate to provide quality products/services	1.000	0.866
Quality is a top priority with this organization	1.000	0.759
Safety is a top priority with this organization	1.000	0.764
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization	1.000	0.933
Employees are treated fairly here regardless of race, gender, age, religion or sexual orientation	1.000	0.915
I like the people I work with at this organization	1.000	0.951
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation	1.000	0.805
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The table above shows that after five factors are extracted and retained, the communality is 0.771, 0.903, 0.840, 0.763 and so on. This means that 77.1% of the variance [information content] of question 1 is captured by the extracted factor and the least variance being 73.3% for the eighth question.

5.17.2.2 Interpretation of the factor Analysis on corporate culture and communications

Table 5.148 Interpretation of the factor Analysis on corporate culture and communications in education sector: Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.732	36.400	36.400	4.732	36.400	36.400
2	1.994	15.340	51.741	1.994	15.340	51.741
3	1.673	12.873	64.613	1.673	12.873	64.613
4	1.360	10.459	75.072	1.360	10.459	75.072
5	1.052	8.089	83.162	1.052	8.089	83.162
6	0.734	5.647	88.808			
7	0.506	3.889	92.698			
8	0.398	3.060	95.758			
9	0.286	2.201	97.958			
10	0.151	1.162	99.120			
11	0.089	0.683	99.803			
12	0.014	0.107	99.910			
13	0.012	0.090	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Source: Primary

The output of factor analysis is obtained by requesting Principal Component Analysis and specifying a rotation. The first step in interpreting the result deals with factors extracted their Eigen values and the cumulative percentage of variance. From the above table it is very clear that 83.162% of variance is obtained if five factors are obtained. This is fairly good because we can have five questions considered for the factor organizational culture and communications instead of thirteen questions [83.162% of information content is retained by four factors extracted out of thirteen].

5.17.2.3 Rotated Component Matrix on organizations corporate culture and communications

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough	0.073	-0.645	0.513	0.241	-0.170
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough	0.335	0.066	-0.314	0.452	0.695
I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially	0.106	0.508	0.710	-0.172	0.194
I can trust what this organization tells	0.556	-0.071	-0.653	-0.089	-0.125
This organization treats me like a person, not a number	0.504	0.086	0.290	-0.635	0.240
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done	0.509	-0.141	0.476	0.416	-0.233
Staffing levels are adequate to provide quality products/services	0.712	-0.445	-0.044	-0.380	-0.122
Quality is a top priority with this organization	0.706	-0.371	0.115	-0.037	0.331
Safety is a top priority with this organization	0.803	0.031	0.157	0.176	0.250
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization	0.850	0.437	-0.040	0.108	-0.080
Employees are treated fairly here regardless of race, gender, age, religion or sexual orientation	0.703	0.514	-0.102	-0.271	-0.269
I like the people I work with at this organization	0.829	-0.469	-0.137	0.045	-0.150
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation	0.475	0.522	0.022	0.469	-0.294
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.					
a. 5 components extracted.					

Source: Primary

The analysis of the factor matrix is based on the loading each factor has column wise. The first factor has one statement which has high loading value of 0.850. The second component has one statement which has a high loading of 0.522, the third component has one statement which has a loading of 0.710 and the fourth factor has a loading of 0.469 and fifth 0.696. Therefore, it can be

concluded that the thirteen questions under the heading of this organizations corporate culture and communication can be reduced to five statements.

5.17.3 Analysis on individual's role in the organization

Table 5.150 Descriptive Statistics Analysis on individual's role in the organization in education sector							
	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I like the type of work that I do	133	2.00	3.00	5.00	595.00	4.4737	0.88402
I am given enough authority to make decisions I need to make	133	3.00	2.00	5.00	483.00	3.6316	1.46408
I believe my job is secure Deadlines at this organization are realistic	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	462.00	3.4737	0.88402
I feel I am valued in this organization	133	1.00	3.00	4.00	504.00	3.7895	0.40922
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal	133	3.00	2.00	5.00	581.00	4.3684	1.22767
I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life	133	3.00	1.00	4.00	413.00	3.1053	1.25688
My job makes good use of my skills and abilities	133	3.00	2.00	5.00	574.00	4.3158	1.22083
I have a clear understanding of my job role	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	483.00	3.6316	0.74339
Valid N (listwise)	133						

Source: Primary

Majority of the employees working in the education sector are enjoying the type of work they are doing. The rank obtained for this statement is as high as 4.473. The least ranking is obtained for the statement related to balance between work and personal life which is 3.1053.

5.17.3.1 Analysis on communalities Individual's role in the organization

Table 5.151 Communalities Individual's role in the organization in education sector		
	Initial	Extraction
I like the type of work that I do	1.000	0.934
I am given enough authority to make decisions I need to make	1.000	0.609
I believe my job is secure, deadlines at this organization are realistic	1.000	0.934
I feel I am valued in this organization	1.000	0.912
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal	1.000	0.912
I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life	1.000	0.924
My job makes good use of my skills and abilities	1.000	0.846
I have a clear understanding of my job role	1.000	0.906
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The communalities value ranges from 0.934 which is the highest to a value 0.609 which is the least. This tells that after two factors are extracted and retained from the heading 'your role in this organization' the information content captured by these variables is 93.4% to 60.9% which is quite high.

5.17.3.2 Analysis on Individual's role in the organization

Table 5.152 Individual's role in the organization in education sector: Total Variance Explained						
Compon ent	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.911	73.888	73.888	5.911	73.888	73.888
2	1.068	13.346	87.234	1.068	13.346	87.234
3	0.527	6.583	93.817			
4	0.380	4.753	98.570			
5	0.114	1.430	100.000			
6	1.002E-013	1.024E-013	100.000			
7	1.000E-013	1.004E-013	100.000			
8	-1.001E-013	-1.015E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

This factor matrix gives an indication that 87.23 of the total variances is contained in the two factors extracted from the seven questions which are considered for the concept of your role in the organization.

5.17.3.3 Rotated Component Matrix on Individual's role in the organization

	Component	
	1	2
I like the type of work that I do	0.954	-0.154
I am given enough authority to make decisions I need to make	0.671	-0.399
I believe my job is secure. Deadlines at this organization are realistic	0.954	-0.154
I feel I am valued in this organization	0.955	0.007
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal	0.955	0.007
I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life	-0.011	0.961
My job makes good use of my skills and abilities	0.913	-0.112
I have a clear understanding of my job role	0.950	0.053
a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.		

Source: Primary

The factor matrix indicates five variables having a high loading of 0.955, 0.954 for the first factor. These variables can be grouped together into a single variable but the researcher intends to use all the four statements as factor-1. The statement relating to maintaining a balance between work and personal life scores a high loading of 0.961 which is considered as the second factor.

5.17.4 Analysis on Work Environment

	N	Range	Mini mum	Maxi mum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My physical working conditions are good	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	441.00	3.3158	0.56900
My general work area is adequately lit	133	2.00	3.00	5.00	511.00	3.8421	0.48993

My general work area is adequately heated/cooled	133	3.00	1.00	4.00	371.00	2.7895	1.32604
My general work area is adequately clean	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	448.00	3.3684	0.87450
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	427.00	3.2105	0.95388
I feel physically safe in my work environment	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	462.00	3.4737	0.88402
Valid N (list wise)	133						

Source: Primary

The statement relating to lighting of the work area scores the highest ranking with a value of 3.84 and the least value is scored by the statement relating to the work area being adequately heated and cooled. Mangalore has a humid climate. During the summers it is very hot. Also, it is seen that staff rooms are shared by many faculty and adequate AC facilities are not provided.

5.17.4.1 Analysis on communalities on work environment

Table 5.155 Analysis on communalities on work environment Communalities in education sector		
	Initial	Extraction
My physical working conditions are good	1.000	0.841
My general work area is adequately lit	1.000	0.324
My general work area is adequately heated/cooled	1.000	0.570
My general work area is adequately clean	1.000	0.753
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work	1.000	0.829
I feel physically safe in my work environment	1.000	0.703
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

Communalities values from 0.841 to 0.324. The two variables extracted on the factor ‘your work environment’ gives a cumulative percentage of 66.99% and individual commonalties is as shown in the above table 5.155.

5.17.4.2 Analysis on Total variance on work environment

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.769	46.146	46.146	2.769	46.146	46.146
2	1.251	20.844	66.991	1.251	20.844	66.991
3	0.933	15.557	82.548			
4	0.660	11.000	93.548			
5	0.305	5.076	98.624			
6	0.083	1.376	100.000			

Source: Primary

The six-question related to working condition can be reduced to two. These two questions can capture 66.991% of the information content of all questions put together. It is necessary to consider those questions whose Eigen values are one and more than one.

5.17.4.3 Analysis of Rotated Component Matrix on work environment

	Component	
	1	2
My physical working conditions are good	0.112	0.910
My general work area is adequately lit	0.491	0.288
My general work area is adequately heated/cooled	0.525	-0.543
My general work area is adequately clean	0.859	0.121
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work	0.882	-0.226
I feel physically safe in my work environment	0.836	-0.070
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		
a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.		

Source: Primary

The two questions for the factor working conditions are related to the adequate noise control to allow one to focus on his/her work and the second factor related to physical working conditions in the organization.

5.17.5 Analysis on Relationships with supervisor

5.158 Analysis on Relationships with supervisor in education sector: Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My supervisor treats me fairly	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	364.00	2.7368	0.71663
My supervisor treats me with respect	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	364.00	2.7368	0.54903
My supervisor handles my work-related issues satisfactorily	133	3.00	2.00	5.00	413.00	3.1053	1.07494
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily	133	3.00	1.00	4.00	413.00	3.1053	1.07494
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	406.00	3.0526	0.68883
My supervisor tells me when my work needs	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	406.00	3.0526	0.68883
My supervisor is open to hearing my opinion or feedback	133	3.00	1.00	4.00	357.00	2.6842	1.03256
My supervisor helps me develop to my fullest potential	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	378.00	2.8421	0.48993
I can trust what my supervisor tells me	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	371.00	2.7895	0.61610
Valid N (listwise)	133						

Source: Primary

Based on the ranking on superiors it is seen that the question related to whether the supervisors are open to hearing opinion and giving feedback gets the least ranking while two questions relating to Supervisors handling personal issues and work-related issues get a higher ranking. Usually the education system follows the top down approach of authority. Therefore, it is evident that employees feel that their opinions are not heard of.

5.17.5.1 Analysis on Communalities of Factor Analysis for Relationships with supervisor

Table No 5.159 Relationships with supervisor in education sector: Communalities of factor Analysis		
	Initial	Extraction
My supervisor treats me fairly	1.000	0.656
My supervisor treats me with respect	1.000	0.782
My supervisor handles my work-related issues satisfactorily	1.000	0.474
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily	1.000	0.712
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well	1.000	0.897
My supervisor tells me when my work needs	1.000	0.897
My supervisor is open to hearing my opinion or feedback	1.000	0.707
My supervisor helps me develop to my fullest potential	1.000	0.793
I can trust what my supervisor tells me	1.000	0.565
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

Communalities result for the superior and subordinate relationship shows that there is one question which has a less value of 0.474 and the remaining have a moderately high value. The two questions which are extracted for the factor on superiors contain about 72.036% of information.

5.17.5.2 Analysis on total Variance of Factor Analysis for Relationships with supervisor

Table 5.160 Relationships with supervisor in education sector: Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.424	49.159	49.159	4.424	49.159	49.159
2	2.059	22.877	72.036	2.059	22.877	72.036
3	0.915	10.164	82.200			
4	0.627	6.971	89.171			
5	0.415	4.616	93.788			
6	0.344	3.821	97.608			
7	0.151	1.674	99.282			
8	0.065	0.718	100.000			
9	1.001E-013	1.010E-013	100.000			

Source: Primary

The Eigen value for two questions is greater than one which signifies that two questions can be considered for the above factor. The questions can capture 72.036% of the information content for the given factor 'Relationship with the Superiors'.

5.17.5.3 Analysis on Rotated Component Matrix of Factor Analysis for Relationships with supervisor

Table 5.161 Relationships with supervisor in education sector: Rotated Component Matrix		
Rotated		
	Component	
	1	2
My supervisor treats me fairly	0.026	0.809
My supervisor treats me with respect	0.647	0.603
My supervisor handles my work-related issues satisfactorily	-0.256	0.639
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily	0.299	0.789
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well	0.947	-0.019
My supervisor tells me when my work needs	0.947	-0.019
My supervisor is open to hearing my opinion or feedback	0.816	-0.202
My supervisor helps me develop to my fullest potential	0.742	0.492
I can trust what my supervisor tells me	0.698	0.277
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.		
a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.		

Source: Primary

The questions which can be considered for the above-mentioned factor could be the one regarding acknowledgement of supervisors for work well done. The second question is regarding how supervisors treats the individual employees. Therefore, two questions can be considered instead of nine components.

5.17.6 Analysis on organizational training and development

Table 5.162 Analysis on organizational training and development: Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Range	Mini mum	Maxi mum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	462.00	3.4737	0.88402

This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	392.00	2.9474	0.76193
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement	133	1.00	3.00	4.00	427.00	3.2105	0.40922
I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	490.00	3.6842	0.56900
This organization provides training or experiences to help me explore other possible opportunities within the company	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	427.00	3.2105	0.52300
There is room for me to advance at this organization	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	420.00	3.1579	0.81503
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay	133	3.00	1.00	4.00	364.00	2.7368	0.71663
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion	133	4.00	1.00	5.00	420.00	3.1579	0.81503
Valid N (list wise)	133						

Source: Primary

The least ranking is related to a question regarding linking of pay and good work. In most of the organizations the pay is directly not linked to performance. Also, it is seen that there is no immediate acknowledgement for the ones who do good work. At the same time, it is observed that organization does consider the career of individuals in this sector. Faculties are encouraged to enrich their knowledge and motivated to attend refresher and faculty development programs.

5.17.6.1 Analysis on Communalities of factor analysis for the factor organizational training and development

	Initial	Extraction
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed	1.000	0.883
This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need	1.000	0.932
Provides enough information, equipment and resources	1.000	0.815
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement	1.000	0.876
I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career	1.000	0.914
This organization provides training or experiences to help me explore other possible opportunities within the company	1.000	0.907
There is room for me to advance at this organization	1.000	0.729
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay	1.000	0.922
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion	1.000	0.829
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The communalities values range from 0.922 to 0.729. These values are quite good. Most of the information is captured by the Principal component analysis. The extraction leads to four questions which can get all the information needed for the factor related to training and development.

5.17.6.2 Analysis on total variance of factor analysis for the factor organizational training and development

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.382	37.575	37.575	3.382	37.575	37.575
2	2.261	25.117	62.691	2.261	25.117	62.691
3	1.113	12.367	75.058	1.113	12.367	75.058

4	1.052	11.686	86.745	1.052	11.686	86.745
5	0.493	5.483	92.228			
6	0.350	3.892	96.120			
7	0.249	2.770	98.890			
8	0.085	0.943	99.833			
9	0.015	0.167	100.000			

Source: Primary

Four questions have an Eigen value of more than one, which is an indication that these can be questions which can be considered for the factor training and development. It is also seen that these four questions can capture 86.745% of information needed for the factor training and development.

5.17.6.3 Analysis on Rotated Component Matrix of factor analysis for the factor organizational training and development

Table 5.165 Organizational training and development: Rotated Component Matrix				
	Component			
	1	2	3	4
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed	0.717	0.044	0.378	-0.473
This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need	0.886	0.142	0.356	0.032
Provides enough information, equipment and recourses	0.894	-0.034	0.110	0.047
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement	0.808	0.296	-0.268	0.253
I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career	-0.631	-0.063	0.705	0.118
This organization provides training or experiences to help me explore other possible opportunities within the company	-0.049	0.815	-0.180	0.456
There is room for me to advance at this organization	0.060	0.802	0.280	0.066
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay	0.138	-0.525	0.329	0.720
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion	0.455	-0.750	-0.208	0.128

Source: Primary

The four questions which can be distinctively asked are the one related to the company clearly identifying what is expected from individuals in terms of advancement, providing adequate initial training for employees in the company, consideration of promotion if good work is done by the employees, and the company providing adequate training facilities.

5.17.7 Analysis on the factor Pay and benefits

Table 5.166 Analysis on the factor Pay and benefits in education sector: Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	469.00	3.5263	0.75457
Sick leave policy	133	3.00	1.00	4.00	378.00	2.8421	0.81503
Retirement plan benefits	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	364.00	2.7368	0.63835
Life insurance benefits	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	357.00	2.6842	0.56900
Tuition reimbursement benefits	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	364.00	2.7368	0.63835
My pay is fair for the work I perform	133	2.00	2.00	4.00	364.00	2.7368	0.54903
Valid N (listwise)	133						

Source: Primary

Respondents in the education sector do not have any complaint towards the amount of vacation given to them, but they are not happy with the life insurance benefits provided to them. Education institutes provide vacations to the employees on a regular basis. Extra benefits like insurance benefits and other perks are not provided to the teaching staff.

5.17.7.1 Analysis on communalities of factor analysis for the factor Pay and benefits

Table 5.167 Communalities of factor analysis for the factor Pay and benefits		
	Initial	Extraction
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)	1.000	0.928
Sick leave policy	1.000	0.680
Retirement plan benefits	1.000	0.380
Life insurance benefits	1.000	0.959
Tuition reimbursement benefits	1.000	0.340
My pay is fair for the work I perform	1.000	0.866
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Source: Primary

The communalities are quite high excepting for the values relating to tuition fees reimbursement and retirement benefits. Therefore, it can be agreed that two questions are enough to draw conclusions regarding pay and benefits in the education sector.

5.17.7.2 Analysis on Total variance of factor analysis for the factor Pay and benefits

Table 5.168 Pay and benefits in education sector: Total variance explained						
Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.137	52.288	52.288	3.137	52.288	52.288
2	1.016	16.938	69.227	1.016	16.938	69.227
3	0.890	14.841	84.068			
4	0.731	12.187	96.255			
5	0.182	3.035	99.290			
6	0.043	0.710	100.000			

Source: Primary

The Eigen values of two variables are greater than one and these two questions can capture around 69.227% of information regarding the factor of pay and benefits. The method of elimination suffices with two questions for pay and benefits. The two questions can generate nearly 69% of the information contained in the six questions which are there in the questionnaire.

5.17.7.3 Analysis on Rotated compound Matrix of factor analysis for the factor Pay and benefits

Table 5.169 Rotated Component Matrix of Pay and benefits in education sector		
	Component	
	1	2
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)	0.007	0.963
Sick leave policy	0.807	-0.171
Retirement plan benefits	0.613	0.060
Life insurance benefits	0.971	-0.130
Tuition reimbursement benefits	0.459	-0.360
My pay is fair for the work I perform	0.929	-0.056
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.		
a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.		

Source: Primary

The two questions that can be extracted include the one which relates to life insurance benefits and the other which includes a question on amount of vacations. Apart from this a question on fairness of pay can be used to get insights into the factors concerning pay and benefits.

5.18 FACTOR ANALYSIS a very useful tool is used to reduce data complexity by reducing the number of variables being used. In this study factor analysis is used to identify decision makers identify what exactly makes employees engaged in the organization where they are working. The table below summaries the number of questions before and after factor analysis for the relevant parameters considered.

Parameter	Number of Questions Before Factor Analysis	Number of Questions After Factor Analysis
Organizations Leadership and Planning	8	3
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	13	5
Individual role at the organization	8	2
Work Environment	6	2
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	9	2
Training and Development	9	4
Pay and Benefits	7	2
Total	50	20

Source: Primary

The questionnaire drafted after factor analysis is annexed for Education Sector (Annexure 2(c)).

Parameters	Questions after Factor reduction
Organizations Leadership and Planning	1. There is adequate planning of corporate objectives.
	2. I have confidence in the leadership of this organization.
	3. There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	1. I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization.
	2. I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially.

	3. This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough.
	4. Safety is a top priority with this organization.
	5. Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation.
Individual role at the organization	1. I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life.
	2. I feel valued and part of a team working toward a shared goal.
Work Environment	1. My physical working conditions are good.
	2. There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work.
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	1. My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well.
	2. My supervisor treats me fairly.
Training and Development	1. This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need.
	2. There is room for me to advance at this organization.
	3. I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career.
	4. I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay.
Pay and Benefits	1. Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off).
	2. Life insurance benefits.

Source: Primary

The above table is the factor reduction table with the parameter and the likely questions that can be asked to elicit the same kind of response in the education sector. The detailed questionnaire need not be used for further study on employee engagement in the service sector in particular to the education sector.

Fig 5.23 Employee engagement model for education sector - Saks Model

The above diagrammatic representation shows employee engagement is an outcome of organizational elements, group elements and individual elements. These elements are considered in the factor analysis and the study identifies the most important factor and the least important factor. Apart from the individual elements certain personal factors also contribute to employee engagement. This can be represented in a diagrammatic representation as below.

Fig 5.24 Individual factors contributing to engagement in the education sector

The above factors contribution towards employee engagement is estimated using the discriminant analysis and also the methods of correlation and regression.

5.19 DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS FOR CLASSIFICATION AND PREDICTION

Discriminant Analysis is used to classify objects into two or more groups based on the knowledge of some variable {Characteristics} related to the. Typically, these groupings would be user/nonuser, engaged/disengaged, high risk/low risk etc. The form of equation in a three variable discriminant analysis is

$$Y=a+K_1X_1+K_2X_2+K_3X_3$$

Where Y is the dependent variable and X₁, X₂ and X₃ are independent variables a, K₁, K₂, and K₃ are constant and coefficients.

Y is a classification into two or more groupings and therefore known as a grouping variable. Groups are formed on the basis of the existing data and coded as 1 and 2. The independent variable is a continuous scale variable and used as predictors of group to which the objects belong.

Then a model is built, which is a linear form and thus use the coefficients of the equation to calculate the Y discriminant score. For any new data points that we want to classify into one of the groups. A decision rule is formulated for this purpose, to determine the cutoff score, which is usually the midpoint of the mean discriminant scores of the two groups.

Table 5.172 Wilks' Lambda value for strength of the Discriminant function.				
Test of Function(s)	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	0.523	83.563	4	0.000

Source: Primary

The statistical significance of the discriminant function is answered by looking at the Wilks Lambda and the probability value of the test given above. The value of Wilks Lambda is 0.523. This value is in between 0 to 1 and a low value indicates better discriminating power. Thus, a value 0.523 is an indicator that the model is a good fit. Also, the probability value of F-Test indicates that discriminating between the two groups is highly significant. This is because the significant value is 00 which means that F test is significant to a confidence level of up to 100%.

Table 5.173 Best Predictor in Education sector: Structure Matrix	
	Function-1
Salary	0.749
Age	0.498
How long have you worked for this organization?	0.425
Gender	0.327
Pooled within-groups correlations between discriminating variables and standardized canonical discriminant functions Variables ordered by absolute size of correlation within function.	

Source: Primary

Better predictor: There are four independent variables namely Age, Salary, Length of service and Gender. From the output table 5.173 of standardized canonical discriminant functions coefficient table it is observed that salary is the best predictor followed by age then followed by the factor length of service and last by gender. The absolute value of the standardized coefficient of each independent variable indicates its relative importance.

Table 5.174 Canonical Discriminant Function Coefficients in education sector	
	Function-1
How long have you worked for this organization?	-0.479
Gender	0.643
Age	0.273
Salary	0.000125
(Constant)	-11.070
Unstandardized coefficients	

Source: Primary

In order to compute the discriminant score for engagement the following discriminant function has to be used

$$Y = a + K_1X_1 + K_2X_2 + K_3X_3 + K_4X_4$$

$$Y = -11.070 - 0.479X_1 + 0.643X_2 + 0.273X_3 + 0.000125X_4 \text{ [Calculated values Annexed]}$$

Where Y is the dependent variable [Engagement], -11.070 is the constant and the respective coefficient are -0.479, 0.643, 0.273, 0.000125 for length of service, gender, age and salary.

	Function-1
Engaged	0.644
Disengaged	-1.395
Unstandardized canonical discriminant functions evaluated at group means	

Source: Primary

The means of canonical variables, gives us the new means for the transformed group centroids. Thus, the new mean for engaged is 0.644 and the new mean for group disengaged is -1.39. This indicates that the midpoint of these two is -0.3755. This is clear with the diagram below.

This also helps in the decision rule for classifying any new case. If the discriminant score of an applicant falls to the right of the midpoint we classify as engaged and if it falls to the left it is classified as disengaged.

		Engaged	Predicted Group Membership		Total
			Engaged	Disengaged	
Original	Count	Engaged	65	26	91
		Disengaged	0	42	42
	%	Engaged	71.4	28.6	100.0
		Disengaged	0.0	100.0	100.0

a. 80.5% of original grouped cases correctly classified.

Source: Primary

The above output table is called the classification matrix or also known as the confusion matrix. It indicates that the discriminant function that is obtained is able to classify 80.5% of the original data to be grouped and classified correctly as per the equation.

5.19.1 Correlation and Regression analysis taking individual independent variables

The regression analysis is judged for its usefulness based on the

1. Overall F-Test for the model. If this is significant say at 95% then the model is a good fit. This shows up as a significant value in the model summary [which should be less than 0.05]
2. The R square value of the model tells the percentage of variation in the dependent variable explained by the independent variable.

Table 5.177 Model Summary and Parameter Estimates for Length of service							
Dependent Variable: Discriminant Scores from Function 1 for Analysis 1							
Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.296	55.187	1	131	0.000	-0.634	0.105
The independent variable is How long have you worked for this organization?							

Source: Primary

The linear model is a good fit between employee engagement and years of working in the organization. The F-test shows that the model is significant. The R square value is 29.6% which denotes the variation in employee engagement explained by the independent factor length of stay in the organization. The Regression equation can be written in the form

$$Y=a+bX_1$$

$$Y= -0.634 + 0.105 X_1$$

Table 5.178 Model Summary and Parameter Estimates for Gender in education sector							
Dependent Variable: Discriminant Scores from Function 1 for Analysis 1							
Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.186	30.028	1	131	0.000	-1.756	1.186
The independent variable is Gender.							

Source: Primary

The linear model is a good fit between employee engagement and gender. The F-test shows that the model is significant. The R square value is 18.6% which denotes the variation in employee engagement explained by the independent factor length of stay in the organization. The Regression equation can be written in the form

$$Y=a+bX_1$$

$$Y= -1.756 + 1.186 X_1$$

Table 5.179 Model Summary and Parameter Estimates for Age in education sector							
Dependent Variable: Discriminant Scores from Function 1 for Analysis 1							
Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.387	82.763	1	131	0.000	-2.592	0.080
The independent variable is Age.							

Source: Primary

The linear model is a good fit between employee engagement and age. The F-test shows that the model is significant. The R square value is also 38.7% which denotes the variation in employee engagement explained by the independent factor age. The Regression equation can be written in the form

$$Y=a+bX_1$$

$$Y= -2.592 + 0.080 X_1$$

Table 5.180 Model Summary and Parameter Estimates for Salary in education sector							
Dependent Variable: Discriminant Scores from Function 1 for Analysis 1							
Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	0.709	319.086	1	131	0.000	-3.188	9.495E-005
The independent variable is Salary.							

Source: Primary

The linear model is a good fit between employee engagement and salary. The F-test shows that the model is significant. The R square value is 70.9% which denotes the variation in employee engagement explained by the independent factor salary. The Regression equation can be written in the form

$$Y=a+bX_1$$

$$Y= -3.188 + 0.000009495 X_1$$

Fig 5.25 Diagrammatic representation for the various individual factors affecting employee Engagement in Education sector

5.20 CONCLUSION

This chapter is an attempt to analyze and interpret the primary data which was gathered after collecting the completed questionnaire from the respondents. The data was coded and analyzed using SPSS Version 21.0. Interpretation of the results for the three sectors has been done separately in the order of Insurance, Banking and Education sector respectively. Association of individual factors with engagement levels was tested with the help of Chi-Square test, Symmetric Lambda value and the Contingency Coefficients. Descriptive statistics for each of the organizational and group factors has helped in identifying the most important organizational factors contributing to increased engagement levels. It has also helped in identifying the factors with which employees have dissatisfaction in the Organization. Factor analysis is used to identify and reduce the number of factors for each of the organizational constrains and this has helped in developing a refined questionnaire to each of the sectors to measure engagement levels. Curve estimation has helped in estimating and predicting engagement levels with individual factors in all the three sectors. The analysis is done with a number of tables and graphical presentation.

CHAPTER SIX

FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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CHAPTER SIX

FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In chapter 5, the analysis of the data was done and results are interpreted to further discuss the findings of the study. The present chapter explores employee engagement across four parameters as age, gender, salary and length of service of the employees. Significant variations are observed across employees of various groups. The chapter also provides an in-depth explanation of the all the constructs of Employee engagement.

- ❖ Organizational leadership and planning
- ❖ Organizational culture and communication
- ❖ Organizational pay and benefits
- ❖ Organizational training and development
- ❖ Individuals work environment
- ❖ Individuals role in the organization
- ❖ Relationship with Immediate supervisors

The chapter also reveals the link between the employee engagement and various personnel factors. Further a relation model is built and individual regression equations are developed. This chapter in addition to the findings also suggests the recommendations, limitations and discusses the concluding remarks for the study.

6.1 MAJOR FINDINGS

The purpose of this study was to examine Employee Engagement in the service sector namely Indian Banking sector, Indian insurance sector, and Indian education sector since these sectors are booming and plenty of employment opportunities lie here. These sectors have contributed to the Indian economic growth. The study has further provided sufficient information on to determine if nature of work influences strongly on employee engagement. It is an attempt to identify if same factors influence employee engagement in the different sectors in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada. Mangalore is a hub of the above-mentioned services, and the people of this region have their own characteristics. The study thus is an attempt to determine the engagement levels (%) particular to the three sectors and group factors as similar and dissimilar

in the sectors studied. The research work has further attempted to identify the strength of association of the various factors of engagement and proceed towards a regression model.

6.1.1 Basic Respondent profile

Variable	Insurance sector	Banking sector	Education sector
No of Respondents	112	119	133
Male respondents [%]	81.2	70.6	51.9
Female respondents [%]	18.8	29.4	48.1
Mean Age	28.4375	31.7899	32.2105
Median Age	26.0000	28.0000	28.0000
Engaged [%]	31.2	72.3	68.4
Disengaged [%]	68.8	27.7	31.6
Mean Length of service in the organization [years]	1.8750	6.3361	6.0316
Mean salary	30500.0000	38957.9832	33578.9474

Primary source

The above table shows the number of respondents in each of the sector. Majority, that is 133 respondents belonged to the education sector followed by 119 in the banking sector and 112 in the insurance sector. The number of education institutions in this region is high and this is shown in the response rate too. Equal number of questionnaires [145] was distributed to each of these sectors but the response rate has been high in the education sector followed by the banking and lastly by the insurance sector. The nature of job and awareness of importance of research work might have contributed to this factor. Academicians are more familiar with the concept of research work and are more generous and acknowledge filling the questionnaire or sparing their valuable time to give their responses.

Comparison of gender across the three sectors shows that the insurance sector is dominated by the male gender, followed by the banking sector and then the education sector. On a closer inspection we still see gender disparity in the insurance and banking sector when it comes to the middle and top-level management. Basically, women are not encouraged to pursue a career in

insurance. Insurance profession is still seen as a boring and pleading profession and firms don't communicate the exciting nature of the work. They work on tremendous targets and pressure. The work culture in the insurance sector may not be suited to women, and women may not be able to balance the work-life as the job is demanding. 29.4% of women represent the banking sector. While some the banks are headed by women it is seen at the middle level management that male domination exists. Whereas the academic sector almost has equal representation of both the genders.

Median age of the respondents in the insurance sector is 26 years while the median age in the banking and education sector is 28 years. The insurance sector has a younger generation of workers when compared to the banking and education sector.

The percentage of engaged workforce is 72.3% in banking followed by education sector which is 68.4 % and least in the insurance sector which is 31.3%. Engagement levels were determined by the answers of multiply questions and a very keen observation done by the researcher. The respondents were asked this question and also explained about what it meant. This was a categorical data which was coded as Engaged =1 and Disengaged =2.

Length of service in the organization showed the highest for the banking sector followed by the education sector and finally Insurance sector. Job hopping is seen as a very common practice with the present generation. It is a stigma which is attached to the insurance sector. Definitely compensation and nature of job is the reason behind job hopping in the insurance sector.

The mean salary levels at the middle level management is around Rs 30,000 in all the three sectors, highest being for the banking followed by education and then by the insurance sector.

6.2 THE OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

6.2.1 Objective 1: To identify the employee engagement levels in the service sector namely Banking, Insurance and Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.

Table 6.2 Cross tabulation: Sector * Engaged				
Count		Engaged		Total
		Engaged	Disengaged	
Sector	Banking	86[72.3%]	33[27.7%]	119

	Insurance	42[31.2%]	70[68.2%]	112
	Education	91[68.4%]	42[31.6%]	133
Total		219	145	364

Source: Primary

The above table clearly shows the engagement level in the various sectors. Engagement is seen highest in the banking sector and least in the insurance sector. The banking sector has transformed rapidly and India is marching towards a digitalized banking era. There is also an upward growth of middle-class customers who demand more services from the banks. Work life has become simpler with the advent of banking software. Also, many new initiatives are put forward by the government which has made the sector grow. It is also seen that 80% of the new age customers use digital modes for their banking needs. The Indian education system too is providing more opportunities. Rapid changes and the advent of private institution in all areas is gaining momentum. Students do prefer to newer courses rather than the traditional ones. It is also usually seen that people who have a passion to teach come into the field of Academics and therefore the engagement levels are high. The insurance sector has seen disengagement among its employees. The work culture, nature of job and targets which are assigned are the main reason for disengagement.

Table 6.3 Chi –Square test Sector * Engaged			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	35.063 ^a	2	0.000
Contingency Coefficient	0.296		
Lambda	0.149		

Source: Primary

The above table shows the application of Chi–Square test to test the relationship between the various sector and employee engagement. The test shows that there is a significant relationship between the variables namely sector and engagement. There is an association but the strength of association is weak which is determined by the contingency co-efficient which is 0.296. Lambda is 0.149 which means 14.9% error reduction. This is a moderate low value leading to 14.9% reduction in error in estimating or predicting one variable from the other.

6.2.2 Objective 2: To build a decision rule to enable the classification of employees into one of the two groups that is engaged or disengaged in each of these sectors.

Discriminant Analysis is used to classify objects into two or more groups based on the knowledge of some variable {Characteristics} related to the factor. Typically, these groupings would be user/nonuser, engaged /disengaged, high risk/low risk etc. The form of equation for a three variable discriminant analysis is

$$Y=a+K_1X_1+K_2X_2+K_3X_3$$

Where Y is the dependent variable and X₁, X₂ and X₃ are independent variables a, K₁, K₂, and K₃ are constant and coefficients.

Y is a classification into two or more groupings and therefore known as a grouping variable. Groups are formed on the basis of the existing data and coded as 1 and 2. The independent variable is a continuous scale variable and used as a predictor of group to which the objects belong.

Then a model is built which is in a linear form and uses the coefficients of the equation to calculate the Y discriminant score, for any new data points that we want to classify into one of the groups. A decision rule is formulated for this purpose to determine the cutoff score, which is usually the midpoint of the mean discriminant scores of the two groups.

In this study the individual factors are considered. The individual factors for classifying the employee into two categories are namely Age, gender, length of service and salary.

The group and organizational factors are not included as it is difficult to quantify them and therefore they are considered for factor analysis.

Table 6.4 Coefficients and cut off scores of Discriminant Analysis

Sector	a [constant value]	Coefficient Age	Salary	Length of service	Gender	Cut off score Upper limit	Cut off score Lower limit
Banking	-6.282	0.073	0.000077	-0.135	1.406	0.342	-0.892
Insurance	-2.940	-0.124	0.000128	0.200	2.844	1.203	-0.722

Education	-11.070	0.273	0.000125	-0.479	0.643	0.644	-1.395
Overall Service sector	-4.652	0.001	0.00012	-0.047	1.460	0.568	-0.857

6.2.2.1 Banking sector decision rule

From the data which is analyzed the upper limit for the discriminant score in the banking sector is 0.345 and the lower limit is -0.892. The mid value corresponding to the values is -0.275. Any value falling to the right of this indicates engagement and a value to the left of the midpoint represents an individual who is disengaged. Substituting these values, the discriminant score is calculated for each of the respondent (Annexure-4(a)).

6.2.2.2 Insurance Sector decision rule

From the data which is analyzed the upper limit for the discriminant score in the Insurance sector is 0.568 and the lower limit is -0.722. The mid value corresponding to the values is -0.2405. Any value falling to the right of this indicates engagement and a value to the left of the midpoint

represents an individual who is disengaged. Substituting these values, the discriminant score is calculated for each of the respondent (Annexure-3(a)).

6.2.2.3 Decision rule for education sector

From the data which is analyzed the upper limit for the discriminant score in the Education sector is 0.644 and the lower limit is -1.395. The mid value corresponding to the values are -0.3755. Any value falling to the right of this indicates engagement and a value to the left of the midpoint represents an individual who is disengaged. Substituting these values, the discriminant score is calculated for each of the respondent (Annexure-5(a)).

6.2.2.4 Decision rule for overall service sector

From the data which is analyzed the upper limit for the discriminant score sector is 0.342 and the lower limit is -0.857. The mid value corresponding to the values is -0.2575. Any value falling to the right of this indicates engaged and a value to the left of the midpoint represents an individual who is disengaged. Substituting these values, the discriminant score is calculated for each of the respondent (Annexure- 6).

6.2.3 Objective 3

To explore the drivers [Factors] of employee engagement in the service sector namely Banking, Insurance and Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.

Factor analysis is the tool used to identify and help the researcher to elicit factors which contributes to employee engagement. The table below summaries the number of questions before and after factor analysis for the relevant parameters considered in the three sectors separately.

6.2.3.1 Banking Sector factor analysis

Parameter	Number of Questions Before Factor Analysis	Number of Questions After Factor Analysis
Organizations Leadership and Planning	8	2
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	13	3
Individual role at the organization	8	1
Work Environment	6	2
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	9	2
Training and Development	9	3
Pay and Benefits	6	2
Total	49	15

The questionnaire drafted after factor analysis is annexed (Annexure 2(b)).

Parameters	Questions After factor reduction
Organizations Leadership and Planning	There is adequate planning and follow up of departmental objectives.
	I have confidence in the leadership of this organization.
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	Safety is a top priority with this organization.
	This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough.

	This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough.
Individual role at the organization	I like the work I do.
Work Environment	My physical working conditions are good.
	My general work area is adequately heated /cooled.
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	I can trust what my supervisor tells me.
	My supervisor tells me when my work needs to be done.
Training and Development	This Organization provides enough information, equipment and recourses.
	My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement.
	I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion and pay.
Pay and Benefits	Amount of vacation (or Paid Time off).
	My pay is fair for the work I perform.

The above table is the factor reduction table with the parameter and the likely questions that can be asked to elicit the same kind of response. The detailed questionnaire need not be used for further study on employee engagement in the service sector in particular to the banking sector.

6.2.3.2 Insurance sector Factor Analysis

Parameter	Number of Questions Before Factor Analysis	Number of Questions After Factor Analysis
Organizations Leadership and Planning	8	4
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	13	6
Individual role at the organization	8	5
Work Environment	6	2
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	9	3
Training and Development	9	3
Pay and Benefits	6	3
Total	49	26

The questionnaire drafted after factor analysis is annexed (Annexure 2(a)) and these are the likely questions which can be included.

Parameters	Questions After factor reduction
Organizations Leadership and Planning	There is adequate planning of departmental objectives.
	There is adequate planning of corporate objectives.
	I have confidence in the leadership of this organization.
	There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization.
	I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially.
	This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough.
	This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done.
	Safety is a top priority with this organization.
	Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation.
Individual role at the organization	I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life.
	I believe my job is secure.
	Deadlines at this organization are realistic.
	I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal.
	My job makes good use of my skills and abilities.
Work Environment	I have a clear understanding of my job role.
	My physical working conditions are good.
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	My general work area is adequately lit.
	My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily.
	My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work

	well.
	My supervisor tells me when my work needs.
Training and Development	This organization provided as much initial training as I needed.
	My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement.
	I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion.
Pay and Benefits	Retirement plan benefits.
	Life insurance benefits.
	My pay is fair for the work I perform.

The above table is the factor reduction table with the parameter and the likely questions that can be asked to elicit the same kind of response. The detailed questionnaire need not be used for further study on employee engagement in the service sector in particular to the insurance sector.

6.2.3.3 Factor analysis in the Education Sector

Parameter	Number of Questions Before Factor Analysis	Number of Questions After Factor Analysis
Organizations Leadership and Planning	8	3
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	13	5
Individual role at the organization	8	2
Work Environment	6	2
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	9	2
Training and Development	9	4
Pay and Benefits	7	2
Total	49	20

The questionnaire drafted after factor analysis is annexed (Annexure 2(c)).

Parameters	Questions After factor reduction
Organizations Leadership and Planning	There is adequate planning of corporate objectives.
	I have confidence in the leadership of this organization.
	There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications	I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization.
	I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially.
	This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough.
	Safety is a top priority with this organization.
	Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation.
Individual role at the organization	I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life.
	I feel valued and part of a team working toward a shared goal.
Work Environment	My physical working conditions are good.
	There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work.
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor	My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well.
	My supervisor treats me fairly.
Training and Development	This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need.
	There is room for me to advance at this organization.
	I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career.
	I trust that if I do good work, my company may

	increase my pay.
Pay and Benefits	Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off).
	Life insurance benefits.

- Based on the same parameters all the sectors have certain questions in common and some relating to the particular sector. The above table provides the necessary details regarding the parameters and the specific questions in each of the sector namely Banking, Insurance and education sector.

6.2.4 Objective 4

To compare the three service sectors in term of employee engagement

Variable	Insurance sector	Banking sector	Education sector
No of Respondents	112	119	133
Male respondents [%]	81.2	70.6	51.9
Female respondents [%]	18.8	29.4	48.1
Mean Age	28.4375	31.7899	32.2105
Median Age	26.0000	28.0000	28.0000
Engaged [%]	31.2	72.3	68.4
Disengaged [%]	68.8	27.7	31.6
Mean Length of service in the organization [years]	1.8750	6.3361	6.0316
Mean salary	30500.0000	38957.9832	33578.9474

Primary Source

The above table gives the respondent profile of the study.

The above table shows the number of respondents in each of the sector. Majority, that is 133 respondents belonged to the education sector followed by 119 in the banking sector and 112 in the insurance sector. The number of education institutions in this region is high and this is shown in the response rate too. Equal number of questionnaires [145] was distributed to each of these sectors but the response rate has been high in the education sector followed by the banking and lastly the insurance sector. The nature of job and awareness of importance of research work

might have contributed to this factor. Academicians are more familiar with the concept of research work and are more generous and acknowledge to fill the questionnaire or spare their valuable time to give their responses.

Comparison of gender across the three sectors shows that the insurance sector is dominated by the male gender, followed by the banking sector and then the education sector. On a closer inspection we still see gender disparity in the insurance and banking sector when it comes to the middle and top-level management. Basically, women are not encouraged to pursue a career in insurance. Insurance profession is still seen as a boring and pleading profession and firms don't communicate the exciting nature of the work. They work on tremendous targets and pressure. The work culture in the insurance sector may not be suited to women, and women may not be able to balance the work-life as the job is demanding. 29.4% of women represent the banking sector. While some the banks are headed by women it is seen at the middle level management that male domination exists. Whereas the academic sector almost has equal representation.

Median age of the respondents in the insurance sector is 26 years while the median age in the banking and education sector is 28 years. The insurance sector has a younger generation of workers when compared to the banking and education sector.

The percentage of engaged workforce is 72.3% in banking followed by education sector which is 68.4 and least in the insurance sector which is 31.3%. Engagement levels were determined by the answers of multiply questions and a very keen observation done by the researcher. The respondents were asked this question and also explained about what it meant. This was a categorical data which was coded as Engaged =1 and Disengaged =2.

Length of service in the organization showed the highest for the banking sector followed by the education sector and finally Insurance sector. Job hopping is seen as a very common practice with the present generation. It is a stigma which is attached to the insurance sector. Definitely compensation and nature of job is the reason behind job hopping in the insurance sector.

The mean salary levels at the middle level management is around Rs 30,000 in all the three sectors highest being for the banking followed by education and then by the insurance sector.

Apart from these basic differences which exists in the three sectors differences specific to employee engagement are as follows;

- The Number of factors elicited after the process of factor analysis is 15 for banking, 26 for insurance and 20 for the education sector. The details of this is as explained in objective 3.
- Correlations between discriminating variables and standardized canonical discriminant functions provide an idea of which is the best predictor for employee engagement.

Better predictor: There are four independent variables namely Age, Salary, length of service and gender. The absolute value of the standardized coefficient of each independent variable indicates its relative importance.

Sectors	Gender	Salary	Length of service in the organization	Age
Banking	0.277	0.787	0.726	0.881
Insurance	0.841	0.560	-0.243	-0.014
Education	0.327	0.749	0.425	0.498
Overall service sector	0.565	0.771	0.539	0.551

It is observed that age is the best predictor followed by salary then followed by length of service and the last factor is gender in the banking sector.

From the output table of standardized canonical discriminate functions co-efficient table, it is observed that gender is the best predictor followed by salary then followed by length of service and the last factor is age in the insurance sector. Age has proved to be an insignificant factor in this sector.

In the education sector salary is the best predictor followed by age, then length of service and finally gender.

In the overall service sector, it can be observed that salary is the key factor after which age follows and the gender and length of service follows respectively.

6.2.5 Objective 5

To develop a relationship model for employee engagement and its causal factors for each of the three sectors.

The discriminant Model for the various sectors is as follows

Sector	Equation
Banking	$Y = -6.282 - 0.135X_1 + 1.406X_2 + 0.073X_3 + 0.000077X_4$ <p>Where Y is the dependent variable [Engagement], -6.282 is the constant and the respective co-efficient are -0.135, 1.406, 0.073, 0.000077 for length of service, gender, age, salary.</p>
Insurance sector	$Y = -2.940 - 0.124X_1 + 0.000128X_2 + 0.200X_3 + 2.844X_4$ <p>Where Y is the dependent variable [Engagement], -2.940 is the constant and the respective co-efficient are -0.124, 0.000128, 0.200, 2.844 for age, salary, length of service and gender.</p>
Education Sector	$Y = -11.070 - 0.479X_1 + 0.643X_2 + 0.273X_3 + 0.000125X_4$ <p>Where Y is the dependent variable [Engagement], -11.070 is the constant and the respective co-efficient are -0.479, 0.643, 0.273, 0.000125 for length of service, gender, age and salary.</p>
Overall service sector	$Y = -4.652 - 0.0000125X_1 + 0.001X_2 + 1.460X_3 - 0.047X_4$ <p>Where Y is the dependent variable [Engagement], -4.652 is the constant and the respective co-efficient are -0.001, 0.000125, -0.047 and 1.460 for age, salary, length of service and gender.</p>

The above table gives the discriminant equation to the individual sector and also considering them together. These equations help in predicting the values of engagement and helps in decision making. Based on these indicators the organization can develop its recruitment and retention strategy.

6.3 CURVE ESTIMATION CONSIDERING INDIVIDUAL FACTORS

Each of the following factors namely salary, gender, age and length of service have contributed to employee engagement individually. Apart from considering them all together, a curve estimation analysis was conducted and an appropriate linear model has been arrived at. With the help of the linear model it is possible to calculate the engagement levels of a person considering the individual factor. Below is a representation of the linear regression equation for each of the sectors [The values are calculated for the given data set (Annexure 3(b), 4(b), 5(b))].

Banking sector

Independent Factor	Linear regression equation
Length of service	$Y = -0.696 + 0.110 X_1$
Gender	$Y = -1.011 + 0.782 X_1$
Age	$Y = -3.5 + 0.110 X_1$
Salary	$Y = -2.108 + 0.00005179 X_1$

Insurance Sector

Independent Factor	Linear regression equation
Length of service	$Y = 0.5888 - 0.307 X_1$
Gender	$Y = -3.747 + 3.155 X_1$
Age	Not significant
Salary	$Y = -3.919 + 0.000128 X_1$

Education Sector

Independent Factor	Linear regression equation
Length of service	$Y = -0.634 + 0.105 X_1$
Gender	$Y = -1.756 + 1.186 X_1$
Age	$Y = -2.592 + 0.080 X_1$
Salary	$Y = -3.188 + 0.000009495 X_1$

Overall Service Sector

Independent Factor	Linear regression equation
Length of service	$Y = -0.551 + 0.113 X_1$
Gender	$Y = -2.208 + 1.661 X_1$
Age	$Y = -2.579 + 0.083 X_1$
Salary	$Y = -2.523 + 0.0000733 X_1$

Thus, it can be concluded that employee engagement has definitely been a HR issue which is gaining momentum in organization. Organizations are striving to retain their employees and at the same time including many practices which are employee friendly. Engagement levels in the organization can be predicted and organization can use the above tools and methods to understand the concept of engagement and apply the same sector wise. Apart from individual factors, group and organizational factors are to be considered. By understanding this organization can still strive to be one of the best places of work. By building an engaged workforce organization can build a brand and can sustain in the ever changing dynamic world.

6.4 PERSONNEL DISCUSSION WITH THE RESPONDENTS

In the light of direct interaction with the respondents the responses indicate that many employees are neutral [62%] about continuing their career in the same work place for the next two years. They are uncertain about the future of the insurance sector. When it comes to the recommendation of the insurance products 50% are not very comfortable with the products and

hesitate to market them. This is something which the insurance sector should take seriously, but may recommend insurance sector for employment as a stopgap arrangement.

In the banking sector too, respondents 64.7% are neutral about their stay in the same organization but with respect to the products they are aware and confident. They recommend the product and also the work environment.

In the education sector 25.6% of employees agree to stay back in the same organization and employees are comfortable to recommend their college to a student as well as friend.

Overall it is also seen that every individual understands his/her role in the organization be it any sector, benefits and salary seem to be the common factor of dissatisfaction.

Many of the respondents in the insurance sector expressed that they should be educated about the products thoroughly as it is very confusing to the employees.

6.5 STRATEGIC RECOMMENDATIONS

The present study has identified engagement levels vary across the various service sectors. All the sectors face a lot of challenges in the dynamic changing world. To meet these challenges organizations should consider necessary modifications in the policies which are there. Engaged employees contribute to the success of the organization. The researcher has reviewed the concepts of employee engagement based on the survey done, drawn out few conclusions and certain recommendations that can be inferred to increase the engagement levels across the service sector.

- The organizations should carefully plan out their Employee engagement policies. The insurance sector in special should be more concerned about their people practices. A common feature seen in the insurance sector is employees are not able to manage their personnel and professional life together. Also, in this sector employees are not guaranteed that if they do well to the organization they will be rewarded. These thoughts need to be removed from the employee's mind.

- It is also seen across the sector that gender has an influence on engagement levels. Engagement levels are significantly high in the female workforce. Therefore, organizations need to focus on the needs and aspirations of the male workforce.
- Age and length of service have an influence on employee. Engagement level increase with age and service. Therefore, it is necessary for the organizations to indulge in activities which will promote the younger generations and provide them with challenging jobs so that they remain in the organization.
- The monetary and non-monetary benefits continue to be key factors of engagement. The present generation also have lesser commitment and loyalty when compared to their superiors. They are more calculative and therefore organizations need to keep up to their standards in financial terms.
- As per the detailed analysis, the relationship between engagement and various individual, group and organization factors are found to be positive. Also, certain other studies prior to this have validated some factors. Therefore, it is analyzed that there are many factors which lead to employee engagement and organizations should consider them seriously so that there is lesser turnover, more commitment, which will further lead to increased productivity and customer delight.

6.6 CONCLUSION

This chapter has provided the answers to the objectives which have been spelled out in the research study. It is observed that there is a clear association between engagement levels and the various sectors. Individual factors which influence employee engagement in the various sectors are elaborated and their contributions are dealt in detail. Further the concept of factor analysis is applied to extract the most important factors contributing to employee engagement in each of these sectors. Also, the personnel opinion of respondents was complied with and certain strategic recommendations are drawn from the study.

CHAPTER SEVEN

RESEARCH IMPLICATION, LIMITATION OF THE STUDY AND SCOPE OF FURTHER RESEARCH

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CHAPTER SEVEN

RESEARCH IMPLICATION, LIMITATION OF THE STUDY AND SCOPE OF FURTHER RESEARCH

7.1 RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS:

This research work has several implications. This can be discussed under the various headings such as

1. Theoretical implications
2. Methodological implications
3. Practical implications

7.1.1 Theoretical Implications:

This study has provided deeper insights to the concept of employee engagement. Apart from being a categorical concept, generally this research study has provided a quantitative measurement for employee engagement. The concept of discriminant analysis is used and helped in generating discriminant scores. Factors contributing to employee engagement in particular to the service sectors have been identified and studied in detail. Further the study provides an understanding of the relationship of the various determinants and engagement levels. Similarly employee engagement level predictions are made possible with the present study. The following constructs were used in drafting the questionnaire.

- ❖ Organizational leadership and planning.
- ❖ Organizational culture and communication.
- ❖ Organizational pay and benefits.
- ❖ Organizational training and development.
- ❖ Individuals work environment.
- ❖ Individuals role in the organization.
- ❖ Relationship with Immediate supervisors.

Within each of these constructs, several sub constructs were developed. But, after the factor analysis only the minimum required questions were elicited and a new questionnaire for each

sector is drafted. These questions will get the same result as done in this study. Therefore further researchers in this area can use this as a validated questionnaire.

7.1.2 Methodological implications:

The research methods and methodology which is used in this study is explained in detail and further researchers can use this as guidelines for a study of this nature and area. The research method, objectives and hypothesis are elaborated. The questionnaire is validated and a new questionnaire is developed. The concept of factor analysis is used. The new questionnaire has lesser number of questions but predicted to give the same result. Therefore it is less time consuming and accuracy of the result can be expected in each of the sectors. Discriminant analysis is used to classify data and the scores can be used for prediction. Also, using the concept of dependent and independent variables, curve estimation is featured in the present research study. Linear regression method has been used in the study to predict the scores of employee engagement. Apart from these methods usual percentage, basic measures of central tendency, standard deviation, correlation, Chi-square test, ANOVA are used to identify the significance and test the strength of the relationships.

7.1.3 Practical implications:

Providing good services and keeping the customers delighted is the top priority of any given sector especially the service sector. The Key findings of this study are not only beneficial to the service sector in India but to other similar service providers in other countries too. The findings help in identifying important determinants of employee engagement in the service sectors which are critical to employees.

The findings of this study will be very useful in predicting the engagement levels in the service sector. The organizations can use the model and apply it to their respective organizations. Based on this study the organizations can also plan their policies which in turn help in engaging employees.

The top management of organizations can proactively use this information and build an environment of commitment. This study will help the industry to develop certain standards

which can be common and thus motivate employees and help in building a positive attitude in the work environment so that organizational and business goals are met.

7.2 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The respondents were very busy in their regular schedule of work. Therefore filling in the questionnaire or responding to the questions was the least interesting thing for them. In spite of this serious limitation the researcher spent a lot of time with the respondents to elicit the right information for them. Observation technique was also used to a great extent.
- Some of the respondents tried to relate it to employee satisfaction and the researcher had to spend a lot of time in explaining the difference between the two.
- The study is limited to the private sector organizations only. The researcher excluded the government and public sector as the comparison would lead to misleading outcome.
- The sample respondents for this study belong to the middle level management. Middle level management is considered in all three sectors to bring about certain commonality.
- The study is limited to the city of Mangalore of Dakshina Kannada. But since at most care was taken to fill in the responses, the study can be definitely generalized.

7.3 SCOPE OF FURTHER RESEARCH

After analyzing the limitations, there are many opportunities for further research in the area of employee engagement with a wider scope. The wider scope may include all service sectors in India and outside. The study also could be including private and public sector. A comparison of engagement practices in these two sectors can be elaborated. The study also can consider all levels of management. The present study has considered age, gender, length of service and salary as individual factors. Further studies can include many more variables and try to develop a relationship model. Factor analysis has identified the various factors and this can be tested and validated in future research work.

7.4 CONCLUSION

The discriminant analysis, Factor analysis and acceptance of all direct hypotheses provide a strong evidence for the generated engagement relationship model. Thus it is clearly evident that

individual factors influence employee engagement. Engagement can also be predicted with personnel factor. The study has generated a strong methodology to measure employee engagement and to classify employees into engaged and disengaged. There has been a significant difference in engagement levels in the three different sectors.

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Annexure 1

Reliability Analysis

Item Total Statistics Employee Engagement Variables

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
I understand the long term strategy of this organisation	201.5625	1069.673	0.845	0.931
There is adequate planning of corporate objectives	201.6875	1132.093	0.150	0.936
There is adequate planning of departmental objectives	201.1875	1094.480	0.961	0.932
There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives	201.5625	1069.673	0.845	0.931
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization	202.2500	1119.806	0.028	0.935
The leaders of this organization care about their employees' well being	201.1875	1094.480	0.961	0.932
The leaders of this organization are open to input from employees	201.9375	1078.254	0.755	0.932
This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough	201.9375	1105.996	0.271	0.934
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially	202.1875	1137.190	0.234	0.936
I can trust what this organization tells	201.8125	1091.641	0.399	0.933

This organization treats me like a person, not a number	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done	200.6875	1039.319	0.959	0.929
Staffing levels are adequate to provide quality products/services	202.3750	1073.532	0.924	0.931
Quality is a top priority with this organization	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
Safety is a top priority with this organization	202.1875	1094.480	0.961	0.932
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
Employees are treated fairly here regardless of race, gender, age, religion or sexual orientation	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
I like the people I work with at this organization	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation	202.1875	1094.480	0.961	0.932
I like the type of work that I do	200.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
I am given enough authority to make decisions I need to make	200.6875	1039.319	0.959	0.929
I believe my job is secure Deadlines at this organization are realistic	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
I feel I am valued in this organization	201.1875	1094.480	0.961	0.932
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal	200.6875	1039.319	0.959	0.929
My job makes good use of my skills and abilities	200.6875	1039.319	0.959	0.929
I have a clear understanding of my job role	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
I understand the importance of	200.6875	1039.319	0.959	0.929

my role to the success of the organization				
My general work area is adequately lit	201.1875	1094.480	0.961	0.932
My general work area is adequately heated/cooled	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
My general work area is adequately clean	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
I feel physically safe in my work environment	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
My supervisor treats me fairly	202.1875	1094.480	0.961	0.932
My supervisor treats me with respect	202.1875	1094.480	0.961	0.932
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well	201.9375	1085.351	0.777	0.932
My supervisor tells me when my work needs	201.9375	1085.351	0.777	0.932
My supervisor is open to hearing my opinion or feedback	202.3125	1092.222	0.474	0.933
My supervisor helps me develop to my fullest potential	202.1250	1088.371	0.963	0.932
I can trust what my supervisor tells me	202.1250	1088.371	0.963	0.932
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed	201.4375	1142.319	0.344	0.936
This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need	201.8750	1154.823	0.635	0.937
provides enough information, equipment and resources	201.8750	1154.823	0.635	0.937
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement	201.6875	1151.190	0.963	0.937

I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career	201.1875	1094.480	.961	0.932
This organization provides training or experiences to help me explore other possible opportunities within the company	201.8125	1135.512	0.396	0.935
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay	202.0625	1121.867	0.010	0.935
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion	202.0625	1121.867	0.010	0.935
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)	201.3750	1099.339	0.480	0.933
Sick leave policy	201.9375	1146.899	0.509	0.936
Retirement plan benefits	202.0000	1103.097	0.669	0.933
Life insurance benefits	202.1875	1118.351	0.104	0.934
Tuition reimbursement benefits	202.3125	1117.512	0.149	0.934
My pay is fair for the work I perform	202.1875	1118.351	0.104	0.934
I am willing to give extra effort to help my company succeed	201.4375	1066.706	0.960	0.931
I plan to continue my career with my company for at least 2 more years	202.1875	1118.609	0.098	0.934
I would recommend my company's products / services to a friend	201.0625	1107.157	0.466	0.933
I would recommend employment at my company to a friend	200.5000	1059.097	0.947	0.930
How long have you worked for this organization?	199.8125	924.544	0.340	0.972

Annexure 2

Employee Engagement and Satisfaction Survey

Please take a few minutes to complete this brief survey which is used for academic purpose only

1 Overall, how satisfied are you with this organization as an employee? (Check one response)

1. Very Dissatisfied	2. Dissatisfied	3. Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	4. Satisfied	5. Very satisfied
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How do you feel about each of the following specific matters? (Please (√)one response for each statement below)

2. This organizations leadership and planning

Particulars	Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
I understand the long-term strategy of this organization					
There is adequate planning of corporate objectives					
There is adequate planning of departmental objectives					
There is adequate follow-through of departmental objectives					
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.					
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization					
The leaders of this organization care about their employees' well being					
The leaders of this organization are open to input from employees					
Overall I am happy with the leadership and Planning in the organization					

3. The organization's corporate culture and communications (Please (√)one response for each statement below)

Particulars	Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough					
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough					
I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially					

I can trust what this organization tells					
This organization treats me like a person, not a number					
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done					
Staffing levels are adequate to provide quality products/services					
Quality is a top priority with this organization					
Safety is a top priority with this organization					
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization					
Employees are treated fairly here regardless of race, gender, age, religion or sexual orientation					
I like the people I work with at this organization					
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation					
Overall I am happy with the organizational culture and communication					

4. Your role at this organization

Particulars	Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
I like the type of work that I do					
I am given enough authority to make decisions I need to make					
I believe my job is secure Deadlines at this organization are realistic					
I feel I am valued in this organization					
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal					
I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life					
My job makes good use of my skills and abilities					
I have a clear understanding of my job role					
I understand the importance of my role to the success of the organization					

5. Your work environment

Particulars	Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
My physical working conditions are good					
My general work area is adequately lit					
My general work area is adequately heated/cooled					
My general work area is adequately clean					
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work					
I feel physically safe in my work environment					
Overall the work environment is good					

6. Your relationship with your immediate supervisor

Particulars	Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
My supervisor treats me fairly					
My supervisor treats me with respect					
My supervisor handles my work-related issues satisfactorily					
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily					
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well					
My supervisor tells me when my work needs					
My supervisor is open to hearing my opinion or feedback					
My supervisor helps me develop to my fullest potential					
I can trust what my supervisor tells me					
Overall the superior subordinate relationship is good					

7. Training and development

Particulars	Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed					
This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need					
This organization provides enough information, equipment and resources I need to do my job well					
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement					
I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career					
This organization provides training or experiences to help me explore other possible opportunities within the company					
There is room for me to advance at this organization					
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay					
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion					
Overall Training and development is good in the organisation					

8. Pay and Benefits

Particulars	Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)					
Sick leave policy					
Amount of health care paid for Retirement plan benefits					
Life insurance benefits					
Tuition reimbursement benefits					
Others please specify					
My pay is fair for the work I perform					
Overall, I'm satisfied with this organization's benefits package					

9. I am willing to give extra effort to help my company succeed. (Tick one box)

Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
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10. I plan to continue my career with my company for at least 2 more years. (Tick one box)

Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
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11. I would recommend my company's products / services to a friend. (Tick one box)

Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
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12. I would recommend employment at my company to a friend. (Tick one box)

Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
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NOTE: We recommend that you do not include your name or other identifying remarks in your responses to the two open-ended questions listed below.

13. What does this organization do that makes it a place where people would want to work?

14. What can this organization do to increase your satisfaction and productivity as an employee?

15 How long have you worked for this organization? Please(√)one response[specify years in particular
Less than one year---0 ,1-2 Years -----1 and so on]

Less than one year	
One year and less than two years	
Two years to less than five years	
Five years to less than ten years	
Ten years or more	

16 Please (√)one response

Gender	Male	Female
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17 Age Please (√)one response [Specify age as completed last birthday]

Less than 21 years	
21-25	
26-30	
31-35	
36-40	
41-45	
46-50	
51-55	
56-60	
Above 60	

18 In which department do you work Please (√) one response

Customer Service/Care/Support	
Development/Fundraising	
Finance/Accounting	
Human Resources	
Information Technology	
Legal	
Marketing/Advertising	
Maintenance/Operations	
Any other	

19 To which sector do you belong to Please (√)one response

Banking
Insurance
Health
Education

20 My monthly income is Rs _____/per month

21 I can consider myself engaged in the organization I am working for [Please (√) the appropriate box]

Engaged	
Disengaged	

Thank You

Annexure 2(a)

Employee Engagement and Satisfaction Questionnaire after factor reduction in the Insurance sector

Questions After factor reduction	Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
This organizations leadership and planning					
There is adequate planning of departmental objectives					
There is adequate planning of corporate objectives					
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization					
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.					
The organizations corporate culture and communications					
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization					
I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially					
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough					
This organization gives me enough recognition for work that is well done					
Safety is a top priority with this organization					
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation					
Individual role at the organization					
I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life					
I believe my job is secure Deadlines at this organization are realistic					
I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal					

My job makes good use of my skills and abilities					
I have a clear understanding of my job role					
Your work environment					
My physical working conditions are good					
My general work area is adequately lit					
Your relationship with your immediate supervisor					
My supervisor handles my personal issues satisfactorily					
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well					
My supervisor tells me when my work needs					
Training and development					
This organization provided as much initial training as I needed					
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement					
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion					
Pay and Benefits					
Retirement plan benefits					
Life insurance benefits					
My pay is fair for the work I perform					

Annexure 2(b)

Employee Engagement and Satisfaction Questionnaire after factor reduction in the Banking sector

Questions After factor reduction	Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
Organizations Leadership and Planning					
There is adequate planning and follow up of departmental objectives					
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization					
Organizations Corporate Culture and Communications					
Safety is a top priority with this organization					
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough					
This organization's corporate communications are frequent enough					
Individual role at the organization					
I like the work I do					
Work Environment					
My physical working conditions are good					
My general work area is adequately heated /cooled					
Relationship with Your Immediate Supervisor					
I can trust what my supervisor tells me					
My supervisor tells me when my work needs to be done					
Training and Development					
This Organization provides enough information, equipment and recourses					
My company clearly tells me what is expected for advancement					
I trust that if I do good work, my company may consider me for a promotion and pay					
Pay and Benefits					
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)					
My pay is fair for the work I perform					

Annexure 2(c)

Employee Engagement and Satisfaction Questionnaire after factor reduction in the education sector

Questions After factor reduction	Disagree strongly	Disagree somewhat	Neutral	Agree somewhat	Agree strongly
Organizations Leadership And Planning					
There is adequate planning of corporate objectives					
I have confidence in the leadership of this organization					
There is adequate follow-through of corporate objectives.					
Organizations Corporate Culture And Communications					
I believe there is a spirit of cooperation within this organization					
I have a good understanding of how this organization is doing financially					
This organization's corporate communications are detailed enough					
Safety is a top priority with this organization					
Changes that may affect me are communicated to me prior to implementation					
Individual role at the organization					
I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between work and my personal life					
I feel valued and part of a team working toward a shared goal					

Work Environment					
My physical working conditions are good					
There is adequate noise control to allow me to focus on my work					
Relationship With Your Immediate Supervisor					
My supervisor acknowledges when I do my work well					
My supervisor treats me fairly					
Training And Development					
This organization provides as much ongoing training as I need					
There is room for me to advance at this organization					
I trust what the company tells me it takes to advance in my career					
I trust that if I do good work, my company may increase my pay					
Pay and Benefits					
Amount of vacation (or Paid Time Off)					
Life insurance benefits					

Annexure 3(a)

Discriminant scores of the respondents in the Insurance sector

Serial Number	Engagement level as per Questionnaire	Discriminant Analysis	Calculation as PER Discriminant Analysis
1.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33748
2.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
3.	Engaged	Engaged	3.51344
4.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.02344
5.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.43833
6.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
7.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.94346
8.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.78009
9.	Engaged	Engaged	.83162
10.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
11.	Engaged	Engaged	2.33841
12.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
13.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.54119
14.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
15.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
16.	Engaged	Engaged	1.83931
17.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33748
18.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
19.	Engaged	Engaged	3.51344
20.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.02344
21.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.43833
22.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
23.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.94346
24.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.78009
25.	Engaged	Engaged	.83162
26.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
27.	Engaged	Engaged	2.33841
28.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
29.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.54119
30.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
31.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
32.	Engaged	Engaged	1.83931
33.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33748
34.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
35.	Engaged	Engaged	3.51344
36.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.02344
37.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.43833
38.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
39.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.94346
40.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.78009
41.	Engaged	Engaged	.83162
42.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319

43.	Engaged	Engaged	2.33841
44.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
45.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.54119
46.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
47.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
48.	Engaged	Engaged	1.83931
49.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33748
50.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
51.	Engaged	Engaged	3.51344
52.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.02344
53.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.43833
54.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
55.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.94346
56.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.78009
57.	Engaged	Engaged	.83162
58.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
59.	Engaged	Engaged	2.33841
60.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
61.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.54119
62.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
63.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
64.	Engaged	Engaged	1.83931
65.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33748
66.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
67.	Engaged	Engaged	3.51344
68.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.02344
69.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.43833
70.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
71.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.94346
72.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.78009
73.	Engaged	Engaged	.83162
74.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
75.	Engaged	Engaged	2.33841
76.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
77.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.54119
78.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
79.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
80.	Engaged	Engaged	1.83931
81.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33748
82.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
83.	Engaged	Engaged	3.51344
84.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.02344
85.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.43833
86.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
87.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.94346
88.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.78009
89.	Engaged	Engaged	.83162
90.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319

91.	Engaged	Engaged	2.33841
92.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
93.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.54119
94.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
95.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
96.	Engaged	Engaged	1.83931
97.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33748
98.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
99.	Engaged	Engaged	3.51344
100.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.02344
101.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.43833
102.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
103.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.94346
104.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.78009
105.	Engaged	Engaged	.83162
106.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.65319
107.	Engaged	Engaged	2.33841
108.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
109.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.54119
110.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.65319
111.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.42301
112.	Engaged	Engaged	1.83931

Annexure 3(b)

Discriminant Analysis Output for individual predictors in the Insurance sector

Engagement level as per questionnaire	Discriminant Analysis considering all four factors	Salary	Length of service	Age	Gender
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.09221	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.86318	.58771	.01059	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	-.33419	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.83522	-1.25608	-.08067	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.34920	-.33419	.01059	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.19274	.09603	-.01114	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	-.64148	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	-.06425	-.02689	.00190	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.06425	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	.28041	-.04590	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.09221	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.86318	.58771	.01059	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	-.33419	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.83522	-1.25608	-.08067	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.34920	-.33419	.01059	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.19274	.09603	-.01114	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	-.64148	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	-.06425	-.02689	.00190	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.06425	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	.28041	-.04590	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.09221	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.86318	.58771	.01059	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	-.33419	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.83522	-1.25608	-.08067	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.34920	-.33419	.01059	-.59163

Disengaged	Disengaged	.19274	.09603	-.01114	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	-.64148	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	-.06425	-.02689	.00190	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.06425	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	.28041	-.04590	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.09221	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.86318	.58771	.01059	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	-.33419	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.83522	-1.25608	-.08067	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.34920	-.33419	.01059	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.19274	.09603	-.01114	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	-.64148	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	-.06425	-.02689	.00190	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.06425	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	.28041	-.04590	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.09221	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.86318	.58771	.01059	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	-.33419	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.83522	-1.25608	-.08067	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.34920	-.33419	.01059	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.19274	.09603	-.01114	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	-.64148	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	-.06425	-.02689	.00190	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.06425	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	.28041	-.04590	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.09221	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.86318	.58771	.01059	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	-.33419	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.83522	-1.25608	-.08067	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.34920	-.33419	.01059	-.59163

Disengaged	Disengaged	.19274	.09603	-.01114	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	-.64148	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	-.06425	-.02689	.00190	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.06425	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	.28041	-.04590	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.09221	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.86318	.58771	.01059	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	-.33419	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.83522	-1.25608	-.08067	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.34920	-.33419	.01059	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.19274	.09603	-.01114	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	-.64148	-.00244	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	-.06425	-.02689	.00190	2.56372
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	.06425	-.02689	-.00244	-.59163
Engaged	Disengaged	-.70672	.28041	.01928	-.59163
Disengaged	Disengaged	-.19274	.28041	.01494	-.59163
Engaged	Engaged	1.47769	.28041	-.04590	2.56372

Annexure 4(a)

Discriminant scores of the respondents in the Banking Sector

Serial Number	Response as per Questionnaire	Predication as per discriminant score	Discriminant values
1.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
2.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
3.	Engaged	Engaged	.68777
4.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
5.	Engaged	Engaged	1.62085
6.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
7.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.43679
8.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31254
9.	Engaged	Engaged	-.06781
10.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
11.	Engaged	Engaged	.61329
12.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.49480
13.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
14.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
15.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
16.	Engaged	Engaged	.58148
17.	Engaged	Engaged	2.42205
18.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
19.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
20.	Engaged	Engaged	.68777
21.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
22.	Engaged	Engaged	1.62085
23.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
24.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.43679
25.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31254
26.	Engaged	Engaged	-.06781
27.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
28.	Engaged	Engaged	.61329
29.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
30.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
31.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
32.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
33.	Engaged	Engaged	.58148
34.	Engaged	Engaged	2.42205
35.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
36.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
37.	Engaged	Engaged	.68777
38.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
39.	Engaged	Engaged	1.62085
40.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
41.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.43679
42.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31254

43.	Engaged	Engaged	-.06781
44.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
45.	Engaged	Engaged	.61329
46.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
47.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
48.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
49.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
50.	Engaged	Engaged	.58148
51.	Engaged	Engaged	2.42205
52.	Disengaged	Engaged	.43332
53.	Engaged	Engaged	.44482
54.	Engaged	Engaged	.68777
55.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
56.	Engaged	Engaged	1.62085
57.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
58.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.43679
59.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31254
60.	Engaged	Engaged	-.06781
61.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
62.	Engaged	Engaged	.61329
63.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
64.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
65.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
66.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
67.	Engaged	Engaged	.58148
68.	Engaged	Engaged	2.42205
69.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
70.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
71.	Engaged	Engaged	.68777
72.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
73.	Engaged	Engaged	1.62085
74.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
75.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.43679
76.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31254
77.	Engaged	Engaged	-.06781
78.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
79.	Engaged	Engaged	.61329
80.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
81.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
82.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
83.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
84.	Engaged	Engaged	.58148
85.	Engaged	Engaged	2.42205
86.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
87.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
88.	Engaged	Engaged	.68777
89.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
90.	Engaged	Engaged	1.62085

91.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
92.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.43679
93.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31254
94.	Engaged	Engaged	-.06781
95.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
96.	Engaged	Engaged	.61329
97.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
98.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
99.	Engaged	Engaged	1.60849
100.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
101.	Engaged	Engaged	.58148
102.	Engaged	Engaged	2.42205
103.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
104.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
105.	Engaged	Engaged	.68777
106.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
107.	Engaged	Engaged	1.62085
108.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
109.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.43679
110.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31254
111.	Engaged	Engaged	-.06781
112.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
113.	Engaged	Engaged	.61329
114.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
115.	Engaged	Engaged	.43332
116.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.33412
117.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.95357
118.	Engaged	Engaged	.58148
119.	Engaged	Engaged	2.42205

Annexure 4(b)

Discriminant Analysis Output for individual predictors in the Banking Sector

Serial Number	Response as per Questionnaire	Predication as per discriminant score	Length of service	Gender	Age	Salary
1.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
2.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
3.	Engaged	Engaged	1.17097	.55166	1.01411	.31294
4.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
5.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04943	-.22986	2.11520	2.12571
6.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
7.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.36633	.55166	-.63752	-.98190
8.	Engaged	Engaged	-.14672	.55166	1.01411	-.36038
9.	Engaged	Engaged	-.25652	-.22986	-.30719	.15756
10.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
11.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	.55166	-.41730	-.46397
12.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.14672	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
13.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
14.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
15.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
16.	Engaged	Engaged	.95136	.55166	.79389	.15756
17.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82982	-.22986	2.33542	2.38468
18.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
19.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
20.	Engaged	Engaged	1.17097	.55166	1.01411	.31294
21.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
22.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04943	-.22986	2.11520	2.12571
23.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
24.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.36633	.55166	-.63752	-.98190
25.	Engaged	Engaged	-.14672	.55166	1.01411	-.36038
26.	Engaged	Engaged	-.25652	-.22986	-.30719	.15756
27.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
28.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	.55166	-.41730	-.46397
29.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
30.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
31.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
32.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
33.	Engaged	Engaged	.95136	.55166	.79389	.15756
34.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82982	-.22986	2.33542	2.38468
35.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
36.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
37.	Engaged	Engaged	1.17097	.55166	1.01411	.31294
38.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
39.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04943	-.22986	2.11520	2.12571
40.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293

41.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.36633	.55166	-.63752	-.98190
42.	Engaged	Engaged	-.14672	.55166	1.01411	-.36038
43.	Engaged	Engaged	-.25652	-.22986	-.30719	.15756
44.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
45.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	.55166	-.41730	-.46397
46.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
47.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
48.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
49.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
50.	Engaged	Engaged	.95136	.55166	.79389	.15756
51.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82982	-.22986	2.33542	2.38468
52.	Disengaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
53.	Engaged	Engaged	.18270	-.22986	.35346	.57191
54.	Engaged	Engaged	1.17097	.55166	1.01411	.31294
55.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
56.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04943	-.22986	2.11520	2.12571
57.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
58.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.36633	.55166	-.63752	-.98190
59.	Engaged	Engaged	-.14672	.55166	1.01411	-.36038
60.	Engaged	Engaged	-.25652	-.22986	-.30719	.15756
61.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
62.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	.55166	-.41730	-.46397
63.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
64.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
65.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
66.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
67.	Engaged	Engaged	.95136	.55166	.79389	.15756
68.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82982	-.22986	2.33542	2.38468
69.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
70.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
71.	Engaged	Engaged	1.17097	.55166	1.01411	.31294
72.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
73.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04943	-.22986	2.11520	2.12571
74.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
75.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.36633	.55166	-.63752	-.98190
76.	Engaged	Engaged	-.14672	.55166	1.01411	-.36038
77.	Engaged	Engaged	-.25652	-.22986	-.30719	.15756
78.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
79.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	.55166	-.41730	-.46397
80.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
81.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
82.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
83.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
84.	Engaged	Engaged	.95136	.55166	.79389	.15756
85.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82982	-.22986	2.33542	2.38468
86.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
87.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
88.	Engaged	Engaged	1.17097	.55166	1.01411	.31294

89.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
90.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04943	-.22986	2.11520	2.12571
91.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
92.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.36633	.55166	-.63752	-.98190
93.	Engaged	Engaged	-.14672	.55166	1.01411	-.36038
94.	Engaged	Engaged	-.25652	-.22986	-.30719	.15756
95.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
96.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	.55166	-.41730	-.46397
97.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
98.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
99.	Engaged	Engaged	.29251	-.22986	.57368	1.34881
100.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
101.	Engaged	Engaged	.95136	.55166	.79389	.15756
102.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82982	-.22986	2.33542	2.38468
103.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
104.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
105.	Engaged	Engaged	1.17097	.55166	1.01411	.31294
106.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
107.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04943	-.22986	2.11520	2.12571
108.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
109.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.36633	.55166	-.63752	-.98190
110.	Engaged	Engaged	-.14672	.55166	1.01411	-.36038
111.	Engaged	Engaged	-.25652	-.22986	-.30719	.15756
112.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
113.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	.55166	-.41730	-.46397
114.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
115.	Engaged	Engaged	-.47614	-.22986	-.30719	.31294
116.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.85774	-.72293
117.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.58595	-.22986	-.74763	-.51576
118.	Engaged	Engaged	.95136	.55166	.79389	.15756
119.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82982	-.22986	2.33542	2.38468

Annexure 5(a)

Discriminant scores of the respondents in the Education Sector

Serial no	Response as per questionnaire	Classification as discriminant analysis	Values as per discriminant analysis
1.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.94896
2.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.57359
3.	Engaged	Engaged	1.64249
4.	Engaged	Engaged	1.28253
5.	Engaged	Engaged	3.01006
6.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
7.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61074
8.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.88234
9.	Engaged	Engaged	1.48298
10.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
11.	Engaged	Engaged	.66639
12.	Engaged	Engaged	.57526
13.	Engaged	Engaged	.42193
14.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.57359
15.	Engaged	Engaged	.94801
16.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82103
17.	Engaged	Engaged	-.06123
18.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
19.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.71352
20.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.59193
21.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
22.	Engaged	Engaged	1.64249
23.	Engaged	Engaged	1.28253
24.	Engaged	Engaged	3.01006
25.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.57359
26.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-2.25371
27.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.88234
28.	Engaged	Engaged	1.48298
29.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
30.	Engaged	Engaged	.66639
31.	Engaged	Engaged	.57526
32.	Engaged	Engaged	.42193
33.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
34.	Engaged	Engaged	1.59098
35.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82103
36.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.70419
37.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.57359
38.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.71352
39.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.59193
40.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655

41.	Engaged	Engaged	1.64249
42.	Engaged	Engaged	1.28253
43.	Engaged	Engaged	2.36709
44.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
45.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61074
46.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.88234
47.	Engaged	Engaged	1.48298
48.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
49.	Engaged	Engaged	.66639
50.	Engaged	Engaged	.57526
51.	Engaged	Engaged	.42193
52.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.57359
53.	Engaged	Engaged	.94801
54.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82103
55.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.70419
56.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.57359
57.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.71352
58.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.59193
59.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
60.	Engaged	Engaged	1.64249
61.	Engaged	Engaged	1.28253
62.	Engaged	Engaged	3.01006
63.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
64.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61074
65.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.88234
66.	Engaged	Engaged	.84002
67.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
68.	Engaged	Engaged	.66639
69.	Engaged	Engaged	.57526
70.	Engaged	Engaged	.42193
71.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.57359
72.	Engaged	Engaged	.94801
73.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82103
74.	Engaged	Engaged	-.06123
75.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
76.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.71352
77.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.59193
78.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
79.	Engaged	Engaged	1.64249
80.	Engaged	Engaged	1.28253
81.	Engaged	Engaged	3.01006
82.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
83.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61074
84.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.88234
85.	Engaged	Engaged	.84002

86.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
87.	Engaged	Engaged	.66639
88.	Engaged	Engaged	.57526
89.	Engaged	Engaged	.42193
90.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
91.	Engaged	Engaged	1.59098
92.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82103
93.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.70419
94.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.57359
95.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.71352
96.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.59193
97.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
98.	Engaged	Engaged	1.64249
99.	Engaged	Engaged	1.28253
100.	Engaged	Engaged	3.01006
101.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
102.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61074
103.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.88234
104.	Engaged	Engaged	.84002
105.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
106.	Engaged	Engaged	.66639
107.	Engaged	Engaged	.57526
108.	Engaged	Engaged	1.06489
109.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
110.	Engaged	Engaged	.94801
111.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82103
112.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.70419
113.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
114.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.71352
115.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.59193
116.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
117.	Engaged	Engaged	1.64249
118.	Engaged	Engaged	1.28253
119.	Engaged	Engaged	3.01006
120.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
121.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61074
122.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.88234
123.	Engaged	Engaged	.84002
124.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
125.	Engaged	Engaged	.66639
126.	Engaged	Engaged	.57526
127.	Engaged	Engaged	.42193
128.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
129.	Engaged	Engaged	.94801
130.	Engaged	Engaged	1.82103

131.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.70419
132.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.21655
133.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.71352

Annexure 5(b)

Discriminant Analysis Output for individual predictors in the Education Sector

Serial No	Response as per questionnaire	Classification as discriminant analysis	Length of service	Gender	Age	Salary
1.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	.61520	-.66062	-1.09943
2.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	.61520	-.66062	-.81458
3.	Engaged	Engaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	1.17939
4.	Engaged	Engaged	1.46858	-.57062	1.83364	1.55919
5.	Engaged	Engaged	.94290	.61520	1.18996	2.22385
6.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
7.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	-1.28933
8.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.04537	-.57062	-.09740	-1.09943
9.	Engaged	Engaged	-.21359	.61520	-.25832	.79959
10.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
11.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	.61520	-.33878	-.33982
12.	Engaged	Engaged	2.09939	.61520	1.91410	2.50870
13.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	-.57062	-.25832	-.24487
14.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	.61520	-.66062	-.81458
15.	Engaged	Engaged	.73263	-.57062	1.18996	.41978
16.	Engaged	Engaged	.31209	.61520	.54628	.79959
17.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	.61520	-.25832	-1.09943
18.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
19.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.21359	.61520	-.49970	-.24487
20.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-1.09943
21.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
22.	Engaged	Engaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	1.17939
23.	Engaged	Engaged	1.46858	-.57062	1.83364	1.55919
24.	Engaged	Engaged	.94290	.61520	1.18996	2.22385
25.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	.61520	-.66062	-.81458
26.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.31873	-.57062	-.49970	-1.28933
27.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.04537	-.57062	-.09740	-1.09943
28.	Engaged	Engaged	-.21359	.61520	-.25832	.79959
29.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
30.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	.61520	-.33878	-.33982
31.	Engaged	Engaged	2.09939	.61520	1.91410	2.50870
32.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	-.57062	-.25832	-.24487
33.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
34.	Engaged	Engaged	.73263	.61520	1.18996	.41978
35.	Engaged	Engaged	.31209	.61520	.54628	.79959
36.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.42386	-.57062	-.25832	-1.09943
37.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	.61520	-.66062	-.81458
38.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.21359	.61520	-.49970	-.24487

39.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-1.09943
40.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
41.	Engaged	Engaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	1.17939
42.	Engaged	Engaged	1.46858	-.57062	1.83364	1.55919
43.	Engaged	Engaged	.94290	-.57062	1.18996	2.22385
44.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
45.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	-1.28933
46.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.04537	-.57062	-.09740	-1.09943
47.	Engaged	Engaged	-.21359	.61520	-.25832	.79959
48.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
49.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	.61520	-.33878	-.33982
50.	Engaged	Engaged	2.09939	.61520	1.91410	2.50870
51.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	-.57062	-.25832	-.24487
52.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	.61520	-.66062	-.81458
53.	Engaged	Engaged	.73263	-.57062	1.18996	.41978
54.	Engaged	Engaged	.31209	.61520	.54628	.79959
55.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.42386	-.57062	-.25832	-1.09943
56.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	.61520	-.66062	-.81458
57.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.21359	.61520	-.49970	-.24487
58.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-1.09943
59.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
60.	Engaged	Engaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	1.17939
61.	Engaged	Engaged	1.46858	-.57062	1.83364	1.55919
62.	Engaged	Engaged	.94290	.61520	1.18996	2.22385
63.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
64.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	-1.28933
65.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.04537	-.57062	-.09740	-1.09943
66.	Engaged	Engaged	-.21359	-.57062	-.25832	.79959
67.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
68.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	.61520	-.33878	-.33982
69.	Engaged	Engaged	2.09939	.61520	1.91410	2.50870
70.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	-.57062	-.25832	-.24487
71.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	.61520	-.66062	-.81458
72.	Engaged	Engaged	.73263	-.57062	1.18996	.41978
73.	Engaged	Engaged	.31209	.61520	.54628	.79959
74.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	.61520	-.25832	-1.09943
75.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
76.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.21359	.61520	-.49970	-.24487
77.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-1.09943
78.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
79.	Engaged	Engaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	1.17939
80.	Engaged	Engaged	1.46858	-.57062	1.83364	1.55919
81.	Engaged	Engaged	.94290	.61520	1.18996	2.22385
82.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
83.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	-1.28933

84.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.04537	-.57062	-.09740	-1.09943
85.	Engaged	Engaged	-.21359	-.57062	-.25832	.79959
86.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
87.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	.61520	-.33878	-.33982
88.	Engaged	Engaged	2.09939	.61520	1.91410	2.50870
89.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	-.57062	-.25832	-.24487
90.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
91.	Engaged	Engaged	.73263	.61520	1.18996	.41978
92.	Engaged	Engaged	.31209	.61520	.54628	.79959
93.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.42386	-.57062	-.25832	-1.09943
94.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	.61520	-.66062	-.81458
95.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.21359	.61520	-.49970	-.24487
96.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-1.09943
97.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
98.	Engaged	Engaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	1.17939
99.	Engaged	Engaged	1.46858	-.57062	1.83364	1.55919
100.	Engaged	Engaged	.94290	.61520	1.18996	2.22385
101.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
102.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	-1.28933
103.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.04537	-.57062	-.09740	-1.09943
104.	Engaged	Engaged	-.21359	-.57062	-.25832	.79959
105.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
106.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	.61520	-.33878	-.33982
107.	Engaged	Engaged	2.09939	.61520	1.91410	2.50870
108.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	.61520	-.25832	-.24487
109.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
110.	Engaged	Engaged	.73263	-.57062	1.18996	.41978
111.	Engaged	Engaged	.31209	.61520	.54628	.79959
112.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.42386	-.57062	-.25832	-1.09943
113.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
114.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.21359	.61520	-.49970	-.24487
115.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-1.09943
116.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
117.	Engaged	Engaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	1.17939
118.	Engaged	Engaged	1.46858	-.57062	1.83364	1.55919
119.	Engaged	Engaged	.94290	.61520	1.18996	2.22385
120.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
121.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.31873	.61520	-.49970	-1.28933
122.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.04537	-.57062	-.09740	-1.09943
123.	Engaged	Engaged	-.21359	-.57062	-.25832	.79959
124.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
125.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	.61520	-.33878	-.33982
126.	Engaged	Engaged	2.09939	.61520	1.91410	2.50870
127.	Engaged	Engaged	-.42386	-.57062	-.25832	-.24487
128.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458

129.	Engaged	Engaged	.73263	-.57062	1.18996	.41978
130.	Engaged	Engaged	.31209	.61520	.54628	.79959
131.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.42386	-.57062	-.25832	-1.09943
132.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52900	-.57062	-.66062	-.81458
133.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.21359	.61520	-.49970	-.24487

Annexure 6

Discriminant scores of the respondents in the Service Sector

Serial Number	Engagement level as per questionnaire	Classification based on score	Discriminant score
1.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
2.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
3.	Engaged	Engaged	2.10597
4.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.85488
5.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.30235
6.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
7.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61829
8.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52986
9.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
10.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
11.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
12.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
13.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.63505
14.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
15.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
16.	Engaged	Engaged	1.81296
17.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
18.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
19.	Engaged	Engaged	2.10597
20.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.85488
21.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.30235
22.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
23.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61829
24.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52986
25.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
26.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
27.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
28.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
29.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.63505
30.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
31.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
32.	Engaged	Engaged	1.81296
33.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
34.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
35.	Engaged	Engaged	2.10597
36.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.85488
37.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.30235
38.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
39.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61829
40.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52986
41.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
42.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062

43.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
44.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
45.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.63505
46.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
47.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
48.	Engaged	Engaged	1.81296
49.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
50.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
51.	Engaged	Engaged	2.10597
52.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.85488
53.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.30235
54.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
55.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61829
56.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52986
57.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
58.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
59.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
60.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
61.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.63505
62.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
63.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
64.	Engaged	Engaged	1.81296
65.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
66.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
67.	Engaged	Engaged	2.10597
68.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.85488
69.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.30235
70.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
71.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61829
72.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52986
73.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
74.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
75.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
76.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
77.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.63505
78.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
79.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
80.	Engaged	Engaged	1.81296
81.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
82.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
83.	Engaged	Engaged	2.10597
84.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.85488
85.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.30235
86.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
87.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61829
88.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52986
89.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
90.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062

91.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
92.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
93.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.63505
94.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
95.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
96.	Engaged	Engaged	1.81296
97.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
98.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
99.	Engaged	Engaged	2.10597
100.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.85488
101.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.30235
102.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
103.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61829
104.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.52986
105.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
106.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
107.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
108.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
109.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.63505
110.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
111.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
112.	Engaged	Engaged	1.81296
113.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
114.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
115.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31261
116.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
117.	Engaged	Engaged	2.45286
118.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
119.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
120.	Engaged	Engaged	.77623
121.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
122.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
123.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
124.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.94943
125.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
126.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
127.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
128.	Engaged	Engaged	1.15109
129.	Engaged	Engaged	2.97329
130.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
131.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
132.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31261
133.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
134.	Engaged	Engaged	2.45286
135.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
136.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.15836
137.	Engaged	Engaged	.77623
138.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430

139.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
140.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
141.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
142.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
143.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
144.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
145.	Engaged	Engaged	1.15109
146.	Engaged	Engaged	2.97329
147.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
148.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
149.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31261
150.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
151.	Engaged	Engaged	2.45286
152.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
153.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
154.	Engaged	Engaged	.77623
155.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
156.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
157.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
158.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
159.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
160.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
161.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
162.	Engaged	Engaged	1.15109
163.	Engaged	Engaged	2.97329
164.	Disengaged	Engaged	.55355
165.	Engaged	Engaged	.69853
166.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31261
167.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
168.	Engaged	Engaged	2.45286
169.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
170.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
171.	Engaged	Engaged	.77623
172.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
173.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
174.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
175.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
176.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
177.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
178.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
179.	Engaged	Engaged	1.15109
180.	Engaged	Engaged	2.97329
181.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
182.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
183.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31261
184.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
185.	Engaged	Engaged	2.45286
186.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062

187.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
188.	Engaged	Engaged	.77623
189.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
190.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
191.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
192.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
193.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
194.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
195.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
196.	Engaged	Engaged	1.15109
197.	Engaged	Engaged	2.97329
198.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
199.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
200.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31261
201.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
202.	Engaged	Engaged	2.45286
203.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
204.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
205.	Engaged	Engaged	.77623
206.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
207.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
208.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
209.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
210.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
211.	Engaged	Engaged	1.92613
212.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
213.	Engaged	Engaged	1.15109
214.	Engaged	Engaged	2.97329
215.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
216.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
217.	Engaged	Engaged	1.31261
218.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
219.	Engaged	Engaged	2.45286
220.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
221.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
222.	Engaged	Engaged	.77623
223.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
224.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
225.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
226.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
227.	Engaged	Engaged	.55355
228.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
229.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.76033
230.	Engaged	Engaged	1.15109
231.	Engaged	Engaged	2.97329
232.	Disengaged	Engaged	.10462
233.	Disengaged	Engaged	.35932
234.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04904

235.	Engaged	Engaged	.14500
236.	Engaged	Engaged	2.43010
237.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
238.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
239.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.56796
240.	Engaged	Engaged	1.66423
241.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
242.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
243.	Engaged	Engaged	2.17097
244.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.63505
245.	Engaged	Engaged	.35932
246.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.54838
247.	Engaged	Engaged	1.43475
248.	Engaged	Engaged	.06079
249.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
250.	Engaged	Engaged	.72827
251.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.35532
252.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
253.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04904
254.	Engaged	Engaged	.14500
255.	Engaged	Engaged	2.43010
256.	Engaged	Engaged	.35932
257.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.61829
258.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.56796
259.	Engaged	Engaged	1.66423
260.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
261.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
262.	Engaged	Engaged	2.17097
263.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.63505
264.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
265.	Engaged	Engaged	.91156
266.	Engaged	Engaged	1.43475
267.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
268.	Disengaged	Engaged	.35932
269.	Engaged	Engaged	.72827
270.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.35532
271.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
272.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04904
273.	Engaged	Engaged	.14500
274.	Engaged	Engaged	.97017
275.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
276.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
277.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.56796
278.	Engaged	Engaged	1.66423
279.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
280.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
281.	Engaged	Engaged	2.17097
282.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.63505

283.	Engaged	Engaged	.35932
284.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.54838
285.	Engaged	Engaged	1.43475
286.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
287.	Disengaged	Engaged	.35932
288.	Engaged	Engaged	.72827
289.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.35532
290.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
291.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04904
292.	Engaged	Engaged	.14500
293.	Engaged	Engaged	2.43010
294.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
295.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
296.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.56796
297.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
298.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
299.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
300.	Engaged	Engaged	2.17097
301.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.63505
302.	Engaged	Engaged	.35932
303.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.54838
304.	Engaged	Engaged	1.43475
305.	Engaged	Engaged	.06079
306.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
307.	Engaged	Engaged	.72827
308.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.35532
309.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
310.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04904
311.	Engaged	Engaged	.14500
312.	Engaged	Engaged	2.43010
313.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
314.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
315.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.56796
316.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
317.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
318.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
319.	Engaged	Engaged	2.17097
320.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.63505
321.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
322.	Engaged	Engaged	.91156
323.	Engaged	Engaged	1.43475
324.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
325.	Disengaged	Engaged	.35932
326.	Engaged	Engaged	.72827
327.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.35532
328.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
329.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04904
330.	Engaged	Engaged	.14500

331.	Engaged	Engaged	2.43010
332.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
333.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
334.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.56796
335.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
336.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
337.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
338.	Engaged	Engaged	2.17097
339.	Engaged	Engaged	.82489
340.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
341.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.54838
342.	Engaged	Engaged	1.43475
343.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
344.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
345.	Engaged	Engaged	.72827
346.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.35532
347.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
348.	Engaged	Engaged	2.04904
349.	Engaged	Engaged	.14500
350.	Engaged	Engaged	2.43010
351.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
352.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-.15836
353.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.56796
354.	Engaged	Engaged	.20430
355.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
356.	Engaged	Engaged	.73930
357.	Engaged	Engaged	2.17097
358.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.63505
359.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
360.	Engaged	Disengaged	-.54838
361.	Engaged	Engaged	1.43475
362.	Engaged	Disengaged	-1.39915
363.	Disengaged	Disengaged	-1.10062
364.	Engaged	Engaged	.72827

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CURRICULUM VITAE

Prof Shailashri V.T. is currently serving as Associate Professor at the College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University. She has a teaching experience of 18 years and undertaken a number of research consultancy work. She has published several articles and presented papers in various conferences and seminars. Her passion is in the subject of Human resource management and interested in learning application packages in research. She has undertaken research consultancy work for the following companies Sriram Chits, DKMUL on an annual basis (feasibility study for homogenized toned milk nandini milk products), Future group, Titan watches, Mangalore SEZ (Govt of Karnataka as per the DC's requirements (Nemmadi center)). On the global front she has visited UK for a week long workshop on productivity and innovation held in Grimsbys Institute of further and higher education, London, UK. She is the Examiner on valuation panel of BCA degree Mangalore University and Examiner on valuation panel of MBA degree of Mangalore University.